

EXPLORING THE PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACT OF PATIENTS LIVING
WITH ADVANCED CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE
ATTENDING PALLIATIVE CARE SERVICES

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of the University of the West of Scotland
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Author's Declaration

I confirm that I, as the named author, conducted the research study detailed in this thesis.

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this dissertation is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Table of Contents

Author's Declaration	i
Acknowledgements	ii
List of Appendices	4
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	6
Abstract.....	7
The Structure of the Thesis.....	9
Chapter 1: Setting the Context of COPD	11
1.1. Definition, Prevalence, Clinical Presentation, Comorbidities, Diagnosis, and Aetiology of COPD.....	11
1.2. Biological and Psychosocial Aspects of COPD and its Effect on Everyday Life and Well-Being.....	14
1.3. Diagnosis and Treatment of COPD	26
1.4. Palliative Care in the Context of COPD	30
1.5. Originality and Rationale for the Study	33
Chapter 2: Overview of the Literature.....	35
2.1. Literature Review Approach and Search Strategy	35
2.2. Quality of Life and Psychosocial Aspects of Living with Advanced COPD.....	38
2.2.1. COPD and Quality of Life	38
2.2.2. Social Aspects of Living with COPD	41
2.2.3. Experiencing Psychological Distress when Living with COPD.....	47
2.2.4. Risk Factors for Presenting Increased Psychological Burden and Lower Quality of Life	50
2.2.5. Mental Health Treatment and Support.....	55

2.3. Palliative Care Services for People with COPD	59
2.3.1. Low Accessibility to Palliative Care Services for People with COPD.....	59
2.3.2. Different Models of Providing Palliative Care for People with COPD	64
2.4. Chapter Summary.....	72
2.5. Aims and Research Questions of the Thesis	74
Chapter 3: Methods.....	77
3.1. Theoretical Perspectives in the Context of this Research.....	77
3.1.1. Theoretical Paradigms and Rationale for Choosing Pragmatism	77
3.1.2. Rationale for a Mixed Methods Design	79
3.1.3. Concurrent Embedded Design	81
3.1.4. Priority of the Approaches in this Research.....	85
3.2. Methodological Process	86
3.2.1. Ethical and Research & Development Approvals.....	86
3.2.2. Sampling	86
3.2.3. Sample Size	87
3.2.4. Data Collection.....	87
3.2.5. Study Location	95
3.2.6. Recruitment screening.....	95
3.2.7. Personal Safety of the Researcher	99
3.2.8. Consenting the Participants.....	99
3.2.9. Debriefing of the Participants	100
3.2.10. Data Storage.....	100
3.3. Data Analysis.....	101
3.3.1. Quantitative Data Analysis	101
3.3.2. Framework Analysis	102
3.3.3. Triangulation of Data	105
Chapter 4: Results.....	107
4.1. Recruitment Pool	107
4.2. Characteristics of the Participants.....	109

4.3. Descriptive Statistics of the Participants	113
4.4. Correlation Analysis of Quality of Life and Mood.....	123
4.5. Results from Framework Analysis.....	125
4.5.1. Adjustment	126
4.5.2. Loss of Identity	138
4.5.3. Support.....	148
4.6. Triangulation of Data	162
Chapter 5: Discussion	170
5.1. COPD and Quality of Life	170
5.2. COPD and Psychological Distress.....	171
5.3. Factors of Healthcare Delivery Affecting Experiences of People with Advanced COPD in Palliative Care	174
5.4. Psychosocial Support for People with Advanced COPD	182
5.5. Palliative Care Provision and its Influence on Patients' Experiences	186
5.6. Carers Involvement in the Care	190
5.7. Strengths and Limitations of the Study	192
5.8. Conclusion	194
5.9. Practice Implications.....	195
5.10. Directions for Further Research.....	197
5.11. Reflection	199
References.....	200

List of Appendices

Appendix 1: Ethics Approval from UWS	247
Appendix 2: Ethics Approval from NHS	248
Appendix 3: Research Passport	253
Appendix 4: R&D Greater Glasgow and Clyde	260
Appendix 5: R&D Lanarkshire.....	262
Appendix 6: R&D Forth Valley	265
Appendix 7: Demographics Questionnaire	267
Appendix 8: McGill Quality of Life – Revised Questionnaire.....	269
Appendix 9: Permission the author of the McGill Quality of Life – Revised	273
Appendix 10: Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale Questionnaire	274
Appendix 11: Permission from a GL Assessment	275
Appendix 12: Interview Schedule.....	282
Appendix 13: Participant Information Sheet	284
Appendix 14: Lone Worker Procedure.....	286
Appendix 15: Flowchart of Personal Safety.....	295
Appendix 16: Consent Form	296
Appendix 17: Participant Debrief Sheet.....	297
Appendix 18: Privacy Notice	298
Appendix 19: GP Notification Letter.....	299
Appendix 20: Coding Strategy	300
Appendix 21: Biographies of the Participants.....	302
Appendix 22: Characteristics of the Participants.....	318
Appendix 23: Test of Normality for HADS total	321
Appendix 24: HADS total Range.....	321
Appendix 25: HADS total Range Scatter Plot.....	322
Appendix 26: HADS total Grade and Point Chart.....	322
Appendix 27: Test of Normality for MQOL-R total.....	323
Appendix 28: MQOL-R total Range	323
Appendix 29: MQOL-R total Range Scatter Plot.....	324
Appendix 30: MQOL-R total Grade and Point Chart	324

List of Figures

Figure 1.1: The biopsychosocial model of COPD	16
Figure 2.1: COPD care pathways in England.....	65
Figure 3.1: Study design	83
Figure 3.2: Framework analysis.....	103
Figure 4.1: Flowchart of the recruitment pool.....	108
Figure 4.2: Informal carer support source	112
Figure 4.3: Additional therapies attended.....	113
Figure 4.4: Age range.....	115
Figure 4.5: Age range scatter plot.....	115
Figure 4.6: Age point chart.....	116
Figure 4.7: FEV1% pred. total point chart	117
Figure 4.8: MQOL-R questionnaire responses.....	118
Figure 4.9: Anxiety scale of HADS.....	121
Figure 4.10: Depression scale of HADS.....	121
Figure 4.11: Triangulation of data	169

List of Tables

Table 1.1: GOLD staging system.....	26
Table 3.1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria.....	96
Table 4.1: Characteristics of the participants	110
Table 4.2: Test of normality.....	114
Table 4.3: Results from MQOL-R	119
Table 4.4: Descriptive statistics of HADS results	122
Table 4.5: Correlation of type of service, gender, age, disease severity, oxygen use, HADS with MQOL-R total score.	124
Table 4.6: Correlation of type of service, gender, age, disease severity, oxygen use with HADS total score.....	124
Table 4.7: Themes and subthemes	125

Abstract

People with advanced chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) experience high physical burden, reduced social activities, compromised mental health and low quality of life. This study explored the psychosocial aspects of people with advanced COPD attending palliative care services.

A concurrent embedded mixed methods approach was employed to examine the experiences of 22 patients recruited from a supportive clinic and hospice day services. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and two questionnaires: McGill Quality of Life-Revised to measure quality of life, and Hospital and Anxiety and Depression Scale to measure mood.

Quality of life decreased with higher psychological distress ($r = -.560$, $p\text{-value} = .00$) and as disease severity increased, psychological distress increased ($r = .346$, $p\text{-value} = .037$). The type of service attended at the time of the study ($r = .283$, $p\text{-value} = .121$), gender ($r = .114$, $p\text{-value} = .531$), age ($r = .026$, $p\text{-value} = .865$) and oxygen use ($r = -.157$, $p\text{-value} = .391$) did not influence quality of life. Three themes emerged: loss of identity, adjustment, and formal and informal support, demonstrating that empathy from healthcare professionals and involvement from informal caregivers, when the latter were encouraged and educated early on, positively impacted patients' experiences by improving their mood. Despite palliative care provision, patients continued to experience high levels of psychological distress and they needed additional support. Early access to palliative care was perceived as a positive factor in developing self-management skills and alleviating psychological distress.

This original study contributed to understanding the experiences of people living with advanced COPD. There is a need to act in the areas of self-management and early education, which can positively influence patients' coping strategies and treatment. Future research should focus on an underrepresented COPD population attending specialist palliative care to overcome barriers to its access.

The Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is presented in the order in which the research was designed and is composed of five chapters.

Chapter 1 introduces and sets the context for this research on COPD: its definition, prevalence and clinical presentation. Leading on from this, it introduces the biological and psychosocial aspects, providing a biopsychosocial model of living with advanced COPD. Then, it offers an outline of diagnosis and treatment, and presents palliative care services in the context of COPD. The chapter ends with a clear justification for the research proposed, presenting its originality and the rationale behind it.

Chapter 2 details a literature review which critically analyses the empirical research on COPD. It examines quality of life (QOL) and psychosocial aspects of living with advanced COPD. Successively, models of palliative care for this population are presented. The chapter concludes with the study aims and research questions posed.

Chapter 3 reports on the methodology used for this study. It outlines the theoretical and methodological perspectives of a concurrent embedded mixed methods design and presents the rationale for choosing it. Subsequently, it describes the participants recruited for this study.

Chapter 4 outlines the results and analysis from the quantitative arm of the study, explicitly exploring depression and anxiety influencing QOL. The qualitative strand findings are then introduced and presented under thematic headings. Finally, the chapter includes a section on triangulation and shows how the data converged.

Chapter 5 offers a wider discussion of the investigation findings, including a review of the research questions presented and a theoretical discussion of the psychosocial impact of COPD. Finally, the limitations of the study are explained, followed by a critical appraisal of this study, providing conclusions and recommendations for practice and further research.

Chapter 1: Setting the Context of COPD

This chapter introduces the literature on COPD aetiology and its clinical presentation in order to understand this disease and its psychosocial impact. Subsequently, the chapter presents a biopsychosocial model of living with COPD, explaining and putting the disease into a biological, psychological and social context. Then an outline of palliative care for people with COPD follows. The chapter concludes with a rationale for the study. Topic-specific literature pertinent to the findings is presented in greater depth in each subsequent section. The literature is demonstrated in this manner in order to facilitate the reader's direct comparison of the study's findings with the relevant literature and to provide a structure to the findings of the study.

1.1. Definition, Prevalence, Clinical Presentation, Comorbidities, Diagnosis, and Aetiology of COPD

COPD is a preventable and treatable disease characterised by progressive and not fully reversible airflow limitation due to airway or/and alveoli abnormalities, typically caused by exposure to noxious gases or particles (GOLD, 2022). The COPD disease trajectory is progressive and debilitating, with alternating periods of deterioration and improvement in function (Lunney, Lynn and Hogan, 2002). Hence, over time the focus of care shifts from life-prolonging therapies to palliative interventions aimed to alleviate symptoms and improve lung function and QOL (Uronis, Currow and Abernethy, 2006; Ferris *et al.*, 2009; Narsavage *et al.*, 2017).

It is now estimated that globally 391 million people live with COPD (Adeloye *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, it is approximated that COPD, contributing to more than 3 million deaths

yearly worldwide (López-Campos, Tan and Soriano, 2016; GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators, 2020), is the third leading cause of death (WHO, 2022). In the UK, COPD is the fifth leading cause of death, with approximately 30,000 people dying from it each year, while 2% of the total population (1.2 million) live with diagnosed COPD (British Lung Foundation, 2016). In Scotland, the prevalence of COPD is higher than the UK average, with 4% of the population diagnosed with COPD (Scottish Government, 2020). People with COPD present a spectrum of respiratory diseases composed of both a clinical diagnosis of chronic bronchitis (excessive mucus production in the bronchial tree) and pathological diagnosis of emphysema (permanent, destructive enlargement of air spaces distal to the terminal bronchioles without obvious fibrosis) (GOLD, 2022; Pahal, Avula and Sharma, 2022; Widysanto and Mathew, 2022). Sometimes, a patient may exhibit a predominance of one or the other, and often these two coexist (Filbin *et al.*, 2004). The trajectory of COPD is lifelong and the onset of symptoms can be misleading and therefore unapparent (Pinnock *et al.*, 2011). People with COPD frequently have other extra-pulmonary comorbidities affecting their everyday lives, e.g., cardiovascular disease, sarcopenia, osteoporosis, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and lung cancer (GOLD, 2022). Other commonly observed symptoms which negatively affect everyday life are: increased fatigue (Schroedl *et al.*, 2014), peripheral muscle fatigue (Maltais *et al.*, 2014), weight loss (Shepherd and Bowell, 2019), reduced appetite (Grönberg *et al.*, 2005), constipation (Sun *et al.*, 2013) and urinary incontinence (Battaglia *et al.*, 2019; Cook *et al.*, 2019). People with COPD usually die from an acute exacerbation (increased cough, phlegm, and dyspnoea) of COPD (Flattet *et al.*, 2017; Haroon *et al.*, 2020) or other systemic complications such as lung cancer or cardiovascular disease (Berry and Wise,

2010; Divo *et al.*, 2012; Haroon *et al.*, 2020). Living with COPD is associated with a certain level of disability. Eisner *et al.* (2011) reported that respiratory impairment measures, namely FEV1% predicted or oxygen saturation, are related to an increased risk of disability. After controlling for respiratory impairments, the non-respiratory ones (body composition or lower extremity muscle strength) and functional limitations, such as exercise performance, mobility-related dyspnoea and lower extremity function, were related to long-term risk of disability.

Various factors can contribute to developing COPD. Tobacco smoking is the most prevalent cause of COPD (GOLD, 2022), with 85-90% of cases worldwide (American Lung Association, 2022), and is also the most significant risk factor in Scotland (Scottish Public Health Observatory, 2022). Occupational hazards can play a vital role in causing respiratory problems with contribution of workplace exposure to dust and chemicals reported in 15-35% of people with COPD (Blanc and Torén, 2007; Caillaud *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, outdoor pollution can develop or worsen COPD symptoms (British Lung Foundation, 2016; Jiang, Mei and Feng, 2016). Other factors, such as genetics, may also be responsible for COPD onset. Hereditary deficiency of alpha-1 antitrypsin (AATD) is a genetic disorder in one in 2,000-5,000 people and contributes to impaired lung and liver function (Greene *et al.*, 2016). Any detrimental effect which influences lung growth during gestation and childhood (low birth weight and many respiratory infections) or airway hyperreactivity, such as asthma, may also be a risk factor (Stocks and Sonnappa, 2013; Lange *et al.*, 2015; McGeachie, 2017)

1.2. Biological and Psychosocial Aspects of COPD and its Effect on Everyday Life and Well-Being

In COPD population, biological functioning is linked with psychological and social functioning. Advanced COPD applies to a later stage of COPD, when symptoms do not respond well to treatment and continue to get worse over time (Zhou *et al.*, 2015). The daily life of people with advanced COPD involves living with a high symptom burden, facing a life that is compromised by limited physical and social activities, resulting in reduced life quality (Sautter *et al.*, 2014; Johansson *et al.*, 2019). The biopsychosocial (BPS) model of health and illness introduced in a paper by Engel (1977) proposes that biological, psychological and social factors play a role in health and disease. The biological factors apply to physiological pathology, the psychological ones to thoughts, emotions and behaviours, such as psychological distress (anxiety or depression) and social ones to socio-economical, socio-environmental, and cultural factors. According to Engel (1980), to fully understand one's health, it is advisable to assess biological and physical factors as well as social, psychological, and cultural ones. Although the model was introduced in the 1970s, it is still relevant today (Deter, 2012; Davies and Roache, 2017; Johnson and Acabchuk, 2018; Bayin Donar and Top, 2020). The BPS framework of disease can be used for people living with COPD, as it corresponds to all aspects of their lives, which actively intertwine and provide a progressive and holistic illness model (Wade and Halligan, 2017). Thus, an improved understanding through a BPS model lens may result in developing a more successful, suitable and effective care pathway for patients with COPD. For this reason, in this study depression, anxiety and QOL are evaluated within the BPS framework.

In the BPS framework, a vulnerability model conceptualises the interface between biological and psychosocial factors in chronic illness, in which minor chronic stressors added to extra daily stressors can promote a disease episode (Ng *et al.*, 2007; Lu *et al.*, 2012; Sinn *et al.*, 2016). Previously, Barlow (2002) suggested that when one believes that they cannot manage stress or anxiety triggers, anxiety may become uncontrollable and escalate. Also, Sperry (2006) introduced the idea that the stress process causes an appraisal of a real or exposed change and an assessment of its significance, referred to as primary appraisal. Subsequently, a secondary appraisal follows, which is an evaluation of the options for coping and includes the scope in which the event can be controlled or changed by an individual.

Benham-Hutchins *et al.* (2017) reported that people with chronic diseases are encouraged to discover ways to adjust their perception and behaviour when experiencing stressful circumstances in order to cope with their already difficult situation. This may mean applying emotion-focused or problem-focused coping, depending on a person's personality. Therefore, appraisal of an event, such as a COPD diagnosis, can be approached differently (Sperry, 2006). Personality traits, specifically optimism, neuroticism and hardiness, can alter a person's appraisal of the threat caused by the illness and their ability to deal with the given stressors, thus reducing or exacerbating COPD symptoms and disease progression (Folkman and Greer, 2000).

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed BPS model of COPD.

Figure 1.1: The biopsychosocial model of COPD

The biological level of COPD is affected by numerous physical symptoms which are correlated with decreased QOL, social and psychological distress (Omachi *et al.*, 2009; Schneider *et al.*, 2010; Hanania, Mullerova and Locantore, 2011). The group of patients attending palliative care services who have severe and very severe COPD are especially burdened with physical symptoms; therefore, it is crucial to understand their impact and correlation with psychological and social aspects of these patients lives.

The most common and universal physical symptom is breathlessness, a subjective experience of breathing discomfort which can vary in intensity and sensations (Parshall *et al.*, 2012). Breathlessness is connected with severity, according to Jones *et al.* (2012). They showed that shortness of breath was a more common complaint in patients with

severe (91.6%) and very severe (99.2%) stage compared with those diagnosed with mild (42.2%) and moderate (69.8%) stage. Breathlessness is the hallmark struggle of patients with COPD, restraining their physical functioning and lifestyle activities due to their complaints of heaviness and increased effort to breathe which affects day-to-day activity, health status and QOL (Ek and Ternstedt, 2008; Habraken *et al.*, 2008; GOLD, 2022). A qualitative study by Kanervisto, Kaistila and Paavilainen (2007) included a small sample of 5 patients with severe COPD and 4 spouses. The participants reported that the smallest efforts could evoke breathlessness and develop other symptoms, preventing patients from participation in social activities. Shortness of breath is described by patients as a distressing and frightening symptom. Avşar and Kaşıkçı (2011), in Turkey, adopted a phenomenological design to capture patients living with COPD (n=14) in all stages and identified three physical and psychological themes: symptoms control, functional disabilities and emotional trauma. The study reported that dyspnoea was associated with overwhelming fear and anxiety as well as changes in lifestyle. It was described as a feeling of suffocation and fear of forthcoming death, resulting in acute and latent anxiety. Another qualitative study investigating the experience of anxiety in patients with severe COPD found that the feeling of suffocation or being strangled contributed to developing a fear of death, which led to restricting their daily activities due to feeling insecure about future attacks (Strang, Ekberg-Jansson and Henoch, 2014). Gysels and Higginson (2008), in their qualitative grounded theory study in the UK, included 18 individuals with moderate and severe COPD from an out-patient clinic and a general practice surgery with an overall aim to investigate the experience of breathlessness. They reported that this symptom was described as elusive, having a sudden onset and disappearing with no

reasonable explanation. It was also a direct cause of interruption of their daily tasks and led to being incapable of completing them in many cases. Gysels and Higginson (2008) suggests that experiencing breathlessness was responsible for the inability to plan activities, which in turn contributed to the increased psychological burden. The peculiar nature of this symptom can lead to delayed help-seeking because of an overall lack of awareness and that breathlessness often does not fit into any traditional medical category (Williams and Carel, 2018). Therefore, the elusiveness of dyspnoea in a clinical assessment could be the reason why patients' experiences were often discredited, which further discouraged them from seeking medical attention (Clancy, Hallet and Caress, 2009).

Chronic pain, specifically of musculoskeletal origin, is another common symptom which affects the everyday life of people with COPD (Lee, Goldstein and Brooks, 2017; Andenæs, Momyr and Brekke, 2018; Latiers *et al.*, 2021). HajGhanbari *et al.* (2012) investigated whether pain was more common in patients with COPD than in healthy people and if it correlated with self-reported physical activity and health-related QOL. The findings from the study with 47 participants with COPD showed that they demonstrated pain 3.7 times more pronounced than healthy subjects of similar age. Interference with daily activities was also 2.5 times higher than in healthy people. The results indicated that pain was also negatively correlated with QOL, leading to avoidance of physical activities. Fear of pain and movement can consequently lead to reduced muscle flexibility, strength or endurance, causing a downward spiral of increased disability (Vardar-Yagli *et al.*, 2019; Tanaka *et al.*, 2022).

Another symptom of COPD is the presence of chronic cough, a prevalent and tiring symptom, with productive cough (sputum) indicating disease progression (Calverley, 2013). Cough and mucus directly affect sleeping quality, another physical symptom which substantially affects the QOL of people with COPD (Cook *et al.*, 2019). Just as breathlessness and chronic cough, the prevalence of night symptoms increases together with disease severity. 74.2% and 82.5% of people with severe and very severe COPD respectively, indicated experiencing nocturnal symptoms (Price *et al.*, 2013). Sleep quality was also found to be correlated with a reduced level of functioning and poor health outcomes. Furthermore, it is particularly associated with higher anxiety and depressive symptoms, negatively impacting QOL (Scharf *et al.*, 2010; Omachi *et al.*, 2012; Kang *et al.*, 2017). In connection with this, Arikan *et al.* (2015) , in a cross-sectional study with stable patients with COPD (n=28), assessing the relationship between cough-specific QOL, abdominal muscle endurance, fatigue and depression, reported that lower cough-specific QOL was related to the poor performance of daily activities because of increased levels of fatigue and depression typically recognised in this population. Other studies added to these results, stating that mornings seems to be the worst part of the day for patients with COPD due to cough and sputum production, leading to reduction of daily living activities, increased risk of exacerbations, poorer health status and reduced health-related QOL (Roche *et al.*, 2013; Deslee *et al.*, 2016; van Buul *et al.*, 2017). Later, Cook *et al.* (2019), in a qualitative study using an Online Patient Communities with 20 people with COPD, explored the effect of cough and mucus and reported that they disrupted their lives on multiple levels, i.e., functional, social, emotional and economical. The patients adjusted their lifestyles and followed newly developed habits to cope with these disruptive

symptoms. Their ability to perform everyday tasks was diminished and interrupted by cough and mucus. Moreover, uncontrollable coughing attacks at night caused sleep disturbances and had a cascade effect on their quality of sleep as the patients felt unrested in the morning, which influenced their bad mood afterwards. The accumulation of sputum in the back of the throat aroused a sensation of suffocating when sleeping, awakened them and induced panic attacks. Cleaning phlegm in the morning became a daily ritual that required time and was physically exhausting. This contributed to a vicious cycle where tiredness implied a decreased capacity to participate in even the least complex everyday tasks. Subsequently, it affected their ability to keep their jobs or forced them to reduce working hours. The uncontrollable coughing and sputum expectoration often caused embarrassment and contributed to experiencing lower self-esteem, preventing patients from engaging in social interactions. This would further lead to isolation and sometimes to depression. Bladder incontinence, which was associated with excessive coughing, resulted in some patients' reduced social engagements, and negatively affected their intimacy and relationships. Finally, the financial aftereffects followed, such as additional costs of incontinence pads and general COPD management. All the aforementioned possible consequences of cough and mucus could negatively impact low emotional social well-being and could have a functional effect on the QOL of people with COPD. However, the findings cannot be extrapolated to a broader COPD population due to a small sample of 20 people and the fact that only patients with internet access took part in this research. Additionally, the research did not specify COPD severity amongst the participants; therefore, it is unknown which group of patients the results refer to.

Living with COPD can also be affected by its unpredictable course, exhibiting symptoms that present high seasonal, weekly or daily variability (López-Campos, Calero and Quintana-Gallego, 2013; Wu *et al.*, 2017), with unremitting and escalating symptoms related to lung function deterioration and concomitant irregularities in symptom demonstration (Miravittles and Ribera, 2017). Other studies of Seamark *et al.* (2004) and Schroedl *et al.* (2014) reported that experiencing physical symptoms prevented people from carrying out everyday activities, forcing them to reprioritise their lives and stop previous activities, such as jobs and home chores. Consequently, being unable to perform home activities, individuals with COPD developed a dependence on their carers.

The physical limitations are challenging as they transform everyday activities into arduous tasks and enforce the necessity of every day being planned. A Swedish phenomenological study by Ek and Ternstedt (2008) in a group of 8 people with COPD, aiming to describe an experience of living with COPD, showed that, because of their loss of physical capacities, every day was related to abstaining from previous activities, with patients experiencing both existential and social loneliness as well as accepting their dependence on other people and numerous assistive devices, therefore losing their freedom. They were experiencing symptoms such as breathlessness, which imposed significant restrictions on daily life. The patients described it as having a job that required planning, oxygen use, gathering strength, and carrying out activities. Participants lived under the stress of experiencing the symptoms, not knowing if they would have enough strength to go through another day. When having worse periods, they felt increased anxiety and thought that life had lost its meaning. Additionally, when not having enough strength and failing to cope with the disease, some wished to die, as their life had lost its

meaning. Whilst a small sample size, with no information on disease severity, this study helps to portray the lived experiences of patients living with COPD, and this narrative is useful in understanding similar situations.

Physical burden is well documented in people with advanced COPD, but less is known about the psychological distress (Atlantis *et al.*, 2013). While the global prevalence of depression is 4.4% and anxiety is 3.6% (WHO, 2017), patients with COPD have a higher prevalence of depression and anxiety than the general population. Studies which investigated the prevalence of anxiety of people with COPD found that 9.1%-28.2% exhibited anxiety symptoms, compared to non-COPD people of whom only 4.1-6.1% presented anxiety (Di Marco *et al.*, 2006; Eisner *et al.*, 2010; Lou *et al.*, 2012; Hsieh *et al.*, 2016). Eisner *et al.* (2010) compared the prevalence of COPD patients' anxiety disorders with healthy matched controls, using the HADS questionnaire anxiety subscale, controlling the healthy subjects for confounding variables, such as the severity of the disease and demographic characteristics. The findings reported that people with COPD were 85% more likely to develop anxiety than healthy subjects.

Correspondingly, a meta-analysis by Matte *et al.* (2016) of eight cross-sectional studies with a pool of 5502 COPD subjects and 5211 controls reported the incidence of depression among COPD patients to be 27.1% compared to 10% in the control group. This meta-analysis found that the high heterogeneity of studies in the analysis pointed to great variability, and therefore, the size of the odds ratio could affect the results, as it could double when the heterogeneity was lowered. Consequently, it is more challenging to present the scale of the psychological burden of people with COPD when the literature

does not provide the exact scale. Another meta-analysis by Zhang *et al.* (2011) also identified a higher prevalence of depressive symptoms among people with COPD (24.6%) compared to the general population (11.7%). Demographic and clinical factors were not the causal factors of heterogeneity in the prevalence of depressive symptoms. Hence, it suggests other possible factors that affect the incidence of depression in people with COPD and exploring patients' narratives could add more information on this matter. In the British-based literature, The National Institute for Clinical Excellence (2004) reported the prevalence of depression in people with COPD at 40% (36–44%). Yohannes, Baldwin and Connolly (2000b) estimated that anxiety symptoms of patients with COPD in the UK have an average prevalence of 36% (31–41%). Moreover, Yohannes, Baldwin and Connolly (2000a), adopting a cross-sectional study with elderly outpatient people with COPD, found that those with depressive symptoms also had more profound anxiety symptoms. In brief, 37% of depressed COPD patients had clinically diagnosed anxiety compared to 5% of non-depressed ones. A recent matched cohort study with 44,362 individuals with COPD and 124,140 subjects without COPD by Siraj *et al.* (2022) found that those with COPD were 42% more likely to have an incidence of depression and 40% more likely to be prescribed an antidepressant, compared to the control group.

The BPS model underpins the biological, psychological, social and other personal factors and joins them in order to yield a holistic outlook on mood disorders generally (Engel, 1980). Both anxiety and depression have been suggested to have BPS model foundations (Engel, 1980; Barlow, 2002). Not only are depression and anxiety a result of biochemical alterations in neurotransmitters in the brain (Werner and Coveñas, 2013; Sheffler, Reddy and Pillarisetty, 2022), but they also strongly connect with social ties

(Kawachi and Berkman, 2001; Thoits, 2011). Likewise, social isolation can be a backwash of depressive symptoms (Elmer and Stadtfeld, 2020). A recent longitudinal mediation analysis by Santini *et al.* (2020), involving older population (3005 adults, 57-85 years old), indicated perceived isolation as an anchor through which social disconnectedness affects mood disorders, and through which depression and anxiety advance social withdrawal. Similarly, in an analysis of internal relations and mechanisms between social support, coping style, adverse life events and depressive symptoms in healthy older adults and older adults with chronic disease, Zhang *et al.* (2017) found that chronic disease negatively affected family interactions and social connections and had consequences in exerting stressful emotions and more negative life events. These results cast a light on the interconnections of social ties and mood, which may help indicate which strategies might be the most beneficial in improving patients' mental health. According to Santini *et al.* (2020), a practical viewpoint, social or gerontological care strategies may build attention on patients' assessments to the degree to which their social connections address their issues for companionship and support. Therefore, in terms of the BPS model, recognising patients' emotional states can facilitate healthcare providers in the effort to give individualised and holistic care.

The literature has acknowledged the BPS impact of living with a chronic condition and suggested that people with chronic diseases, such as COPD, should receive integrated care programmes which are patient-centred rather than solely disease-centred (WHO, 2001; van Dulmen *et al.*, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017). Furthermore, person-centred care is related to the BPS model approach (Kitson *et al.*, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2013; van

Dulmen *et al.*, 2015; Turabian, 2018) and can improve patient outcomes (Weiner *et al.*, 2013).

Other studies with chronic diseases presented a conceptual relationship model, showing that better rapport between healthcare professionals and their patients, as well as the more active involvement of patients, showed enhanced treatment compliance, which, in turn, could improve health outcomes (Alexander *et al.*, 2012; Greene and Hibbard, 2012; Bayin Donar and Top, 2020). Also, in her editorial, Wagg (2012) published a five-factor spectrum of support for people with COPD, which corresponds to the BPS approach and covers its principles. The first step is an action plan about the management of symptom and exacerbation. Next comes educating patients, followed by self-management and pulmonary rehabilitation. The final step is integrative care, which incorporates ongoing support and long-term supervised exercise or a maintenance programme. This leads to forming directions and recommendations on self-management of people with COPD.

To sum up, the BPS framework seems to correspond with the vulnerability model, wherein the stress and coping paradigm embodies facets of psychosocial functioning and physical functioning and provides a comprehensive approach to evaluating and managing a chronic lung disease such as COPD. Experiencing physical symptoms affects everyday life, as it limits daily activities and the individual's independence, while it increases dependence on others, contributing to developing frustration, dismay, and psychological distress. Social aspects of life can also be affected due to patients' being housebound, feeling isolated and unable to participate in previously attended social activities. Finally, these losses force the patients to develop coping and adapting strategies.

1.3. Diagnosis and Treatment of COPD

Early detection of COPD is essential for the prevention of disease progression and clinical management of deterioration (Choi and Rhee, 2020). Kostikas *et al.* (2019) demonstrated that two-thirds of patients with COPD in the UK are not diagnosed in the early stages and that late diagnosis puts people with COPD at higher risk, causing earlier first exacerbation and increased incidence.

The physiological values of COPD patients' diagnostic parameters, normal ranges, therapeutic targets, and alerts differ slightly across countries in the world (Kayyali *et al.*, 2016). Spirometry is the standard respiratory test for both the diagnosis of COPD and assessment of disease severity (Johns, Walters and Walters, 2014; GOLD, 2022). It gives outcomes such as forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1), which are used for assessing the severity of airway obstruction (Graham *et al.*, 2019). The results of a post-bronchodilator FEV1/FVC ratio, called Tiffeneau-Pinelli index, of less than 0.70 certify persistent airflow limitation confirm COPD diagnosis. Next, in order to define airflow obstruction, it is required to find a reduced FEV1 below 80%. Table 1.1. depicts the four severity stages of the COPD staging system (GOLD, 2022):

Table 1.1: GOLD staging system

GOLD stage	COPD severity	FEV1/FVC ratio	FEV1% predicted
I	Mild	<70	≥ 80
II	Moderate	<70	≥ 50 - < 80
III	Severe	<70	≥ 30 - < 50
IV	Very severe	<70	< 30

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The Medical Research Council (MRC) breathlessness scale is another instrument that can help physicians to estimate the extent of the perceived disability, measuring breathlessness on a scale from 1 to 5 (with a higher number experiencing more severe dyspnoea) and allowing the patients to indicate the degree to which their dyspnoea affects their mobility (Williams, 2017). Imaging testing, such as a chest x-ray (CXR), high-resolution computer tomography scan, an electrocardiogram and echocardiogram, is also recommended in COPD diagnosis (Pudney and Doherty, 2016). Blood testing can be conducted to exclude polycythaemia, which is a disease state when the haematocrit, the volume percentage of red blood cells in the blood and/or haemoglobin concentration are elevated in peripheral blood (NHS, 2019a). Transfer factor for carbon monoxide is then advised to identify possible disproportions in spirometric impairment (Quanjer *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, to exclude genetic causes, an alpha-1 antitrypsin or α 1-antitrypsin (A1AT, A1A, or AAT) level testing is advised in early-onset with minimal smoking history and family history of COPD (Miravittles *et al.*, 2017). Another test used in COPD diagnosis is body mass index (BMI), as decreased body mass is correlated with increased mortality in this population (Yang *et al.*, 2010).

Treatment interventions can be divided into pharmacological and non-pharmacological ones. Based on NHS (2019b), the treatment includes: smoking cessation, inhalers and medications, pulmonary rehabilitation, surgery or lung transplant. These treatments will be further explained below. Every individual may demand a particular treatment regimen, as COPD displays a spectrum of disease phenotypes (GOLD, 2022).

Treatment should commence with prevention. Smoking cessation is the most effective intervention, and at every opportunity all patients should be encouraged to quit smoking

and offered additional help, including nicotine replacement therapy, bupropion and smoking cessation clinics (Ambrosino and Bertella, 2018). Also, healthy eating and regular physical activity can be advised (van Eerd *et al.*, 2016; Scoditti *et al.*, 2019).

Inhaled therapy, such as short-acting bronchodilators (SABAs β 2 agonists and/or anticholinergics) may be prescribed for initial treatment as relief of exertional dyspnoea, while long-acting inhaled bronchodilators (LABAs β 2 agonists and/or anticholinergics) should be considered if symptoms persist despite the use of short-acting bronchodilators (Ejiofor and Turner, 2013). Inhaled corticosteroids are another possible treatment to reduce the rate of exacerbations (Zhong *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, long-acting muscarinic antagonists (LAMAs) could reduce the exacerbation risks and improve symptom management of the patients (Karner, Chong and Poole, 2014).

Oral medications which may be prescribed are theophylline (to ease breathing), mucolytics (to reduce phlegm), corticosteroids (to reduce inflammation) and antibiotics (in case of chest infection) (Poole, Black and Cates, 2012; Horita *et al.*, 2014; Devereux *et al.*, 2018; Herath *et al.*, 2018). Other pharmacological interventions are pneumococcal and influenza vaccinations as well as nutritional supplementation (for those malnourished) (Tomczyk *et al.*, 2014; Bekkat-Berkani *et al.*, 2017; van Beers *et al.*, 2020). In people with end-stage COPD, opioids, benzodiazepines, tricyclic antidepressants and major tranquillisers can be considered to relieve breathlessness, when unresponsive to other therapy (National Institute for Clinical Excellence, 2004). Still, the adherence to prescribed therapy of real-world medication use, based on a retrospective analysis, is quite low (from 23% to 43%) (Toy *et al.*, 2011).

When COPD results in a low level of oxygen in the blood, oxygen therapy may be employed. Long-term oxygen therapy (LTOT) improves the QOL of hypoxemic patients (Eaton *et al.*, 2004) and is recommended for patients with PaO₂ < 7.3 kPa (Shebl, Modi and Cates, 2022). Moreover, patients can use ambulatory oxygen outside home (Duck, 2006). Nebulisers and oxygen tanks can be useful for patients as they improve their mobility (Ian Jones, 2004). Short-burst oxygen therapy (SBOT) was also investigated in COPD patients in palliation and it appears to be of great value in physical exercise (Booth *et al.*, 2004). In general, oxygen therapy was typically observed as helpful and had a positive outcome, once patients became familiar with it and learnt how to live with it (Marx *et al.*, 2016). Also, it increased the patients' self-confidence and capabilities (Kanervisto, Kaistila and Paavilainen, 2007). Oxygen use, although beneficial regarding symptom relief and mobility enhancement at home, may cause patients' dependence on it, which in turn could enforce lifestyle restrictions with patients being housebound and going out only with portable oxygen (Landers *et al.*, 2015) or not eager to leave the house too far away (Elkington *et al.*, 2004). For some patients the fact of having oxygen therapy made the disease visible, which was associated with stigmatisation, possibly leading to their social isolation (Williams *et al.*, 2007).

In Europe, it is quite common to use non-invasive ventilation (NIV) for patients who choose to forego or feel too unwell for invasive mechanical ventilation (Crimi *et al.*, 2010). Approximately one-third of patients who have end-of-life care in hospital receive NIV as the most aggressive form of ventilation before their death (Nava *et al.*, 2007). Patients sometimes express distress at the use of this intervention, which is likely to be used towards the end of life (Partridge *et al.*, 2009). Other treatments for COPD may include

nebulised medication which may be prescribed in severe COPD, if inhalers have not worked (NHS, 2019b). Patients with advanced COPD can undergo surgery, such as bullectomy, lung volume reduction or lung transplantation (Meyers and Patterson, 2003; Marchetti and Criner, 2015).

In addition to the above, National Institute for Clinical Excellence (2004) suggests that pulmonary rehabilitation should be offered to all those who consider themselves disabled functionally by COPD (MRC grade 3 and above) This will be further explored in 2.2.5 Mental Health Support and Treatment.

1.4. Palliative Care in the Context of COPD

World Health Organisation (WHO) introduced a definition of palliative care which emphasises the significance of early identification, availability of care at all levels, and thorough assessment and treatment of pain and other problems, and includes physical, psychosocial, and spiritual domains, resonated in the BPS model (WHO, 2021). WHO (2020) stated that palliative care also uses a team approach to address the needs of patients, their caregivers and families, as well as addressing practical needs and bereavement counselling. Palliative care is a patient-centred approach which involves the individuals, incorporating their views into service design in order to improve their QOL, in contrast to disease-oriented care, indistinguishably connected with a feeling of failure alongside patients' deterioration (Mitchell, 2008; Crawford *et al.*, 2013; Lavoie, Blondeau and Martineau, 2013).

WHO (2008) advised the palliative care for patients with COPD should focus on the management of all symptoms, which can lead to improving the QOL through a holistic

approach, excellent communication and psychosocial support of carers and patients. In the past authors showed the benefits of palliative care, such as improving well-being and QOL of patients with advanced diseases such as cancer (Temel *et al.*, 2010; El-Jawahri *et al.*, 2016; Ziegler *et al.*, 2018) or heart failure (Brännström and Boman, 2014; Sidebottom *et al.*, 2015). However, the impact of palliative care on the well-being of the COPD population is yet to be fully researched. A randomised controlled trial (RCT) by Duenk *et al.* (2017) assessed the effects of palliative care on the well-being of these patients and found that it did not improve QOL directly. Nevertheless, it increased the number of patients who made choices of advance care. Similarly, Rush *et al.* (2017) performed a retrospective nationwide cohort analysis from a sample of hospitalisations from 2006-2012 in the US. They reported that those with end-stage COPD (Stage IV) who were referred to palliative care had Do Not Resuscitate (DNR) status more commonly than those who did not receive palliative care. This suggests that patients who received palliative care were more educated and informed about their treatment choices.

A study in Germany by Marx *et al.* (2016) involving four serial semi-structured interviews of 17 participants with severe and very severe COPD who received care from lung care clinic and community care, aiming to explore what it means to patients to live with COPD as an incurable and constantly progressing disease, reported that they often felt at the mercy of the disease and struggled to accept the disease and their life situation. The findings revealed that these patients may benefit from the early integration of palliative care due to its multi-professional person-centred and team-centred approach which may help advise patients about the progress of the disease more effectively. It can further enhance their comprehension of the life situation, often perceived as hopeless, and help

them accept it. The psychosocial support offered through palliative care may improve patients' responsibility and positively affect their action strategies, such as trying to live their daily lives according to their physical capacities. Similarly, as reported in a single-blind randomised trial by Higginson *et al.* (2014), early integration of specialist palliative care provided good support for patients with severe COPD and helped alleviate their breathlessness. The study compared two groups of patients, one receiving usual care (n=52) and the other receiving breathlessness support service (n=53), involving respiratory medicine, physiotherapy, occupational therapy and palliative care. The participants in the study had COPD (54%), cancer, interstitial lung disease, heart failure, or other diseases, and the mean FEV1 predicted was 46%. The results indicated that palliative care integrated via breathlessness support service improved the patients' mastery. The evaluation of mastery included assessment of patients' perception of control over their breathlessness and its impact on the QOL and function. It showed a 16% increase in mastery in the group receiving the breathlessness support service, thus proving its value for people with respiratory problems. However, this trial was conducted in only one centre in an urban area, where usual care at a specialist centre may have been of uncommonly good quality, with healthcare staff motivated to participate in the investigation. Hence, it is unclear how the recorded findings translate to other routine scenarios and settings. Also, the study did not present the differences in patients' mastery with respect to the specific health conditions.

Blinderman *et al.* (2009) reported that it is essential to focus on the symptom-related treatment, given the high prevalence of physical symptoms and distress connected with experiencing them. Thus, addressing this psychological distress may help in the struggle

to preserve social functioning. The authors further suggested that palliative care interventions may yield substantial advantages to this population such as improving QOL. Nonetheless, the study of Blinderman *et al.* (2009) recruited a small sample of participants from two academic urban medical centres; therefore, it cannot be generalised for populations receiving care in community services. Likewise, this study did not consider or include participants' information about symptoms, treatment of the disease itself, caregiver characteristics or psychological resilience; hence, the effect of these factors remains unknown, leaving these aspects still to be investigated. However, it pointed to the importance of efficient symptom management, the potential benefits of addressing psychosocial concerns, and the role of palliative care in improving QOL.

All in all, evidence indicated that palliative care is a valuable source of care for people with COPD, albeit its impact on psychosocial aspects and the most suitable model of care delivery has yet to be determined.

1.5. Originality and Rationale for the Study

People with COPD live with a high physical symptom burden, compromised mental health, limited social life and low QOL. Some research has been carried out on the BPS model in chronic diseases; however, little is known about the implication of the BPS model for people with COPD attending palliative care services. Considering the complex aspects of chronic diseases, more investigation is required to report what factors affect the lives of people with advanced COPD in order to improve their healthcare management.

It appears that there are opportunities within palliative care services which are beneficial to managing and improving the care of individuals living with COPD. The needs,

experiences and psychosocial burden of patients with advanced COPD receiving palliative care services are still not thoroughly explored. To date, there has been little agreement on what level of care is most suitable for patients with COPD, and there is a lack of specific evidence about the needs and experiences of patients with advanced COPD receiving palliative care services, whose role has yet to be thoroughly investigated. Additionally, there is little evidence about which models of care, pathways and practices are most suitable in order to reduce anxiety and depression, improve QOL and enhance outcomes for COPD patients to ensure well-timed and integrated palliative care.

Chapter 2: Overview of the Literature

This chapter presents a narrative review of the literature to determine what is known about the psychosocial aspects of living with COPD and palliative care services in order to support a well-defined rationale for this research study. The chapter begins by recognising a review approach used to explore the literature and shows how the broader literature on psychosocial aspects of living with COPD was identified. This encompasses evaluating the search terms used, the databases searched and the inclusion criteria for the review. The psychosocial aspects of living with COPD and palliative care services are explicitly defined and conceptualised in this review. The chapter further considers the empirical evidence and vital research on the QOL and psychological and social aspects of living with COPD. Then, this literature review examines the evidence regarding people with COPD in palliative care services. The chapter concludes with a clear aim and research questions for the study.

2.1. Literature Review Approach and Search Strategy

This narrative review examines recent literature on the topic of palliative care, QOL and psychosocial aspects of advanced COPD in order to identify what has been published to date, allowing for the summary of evidence and identification of the research gap (Grant and Booth, 2009).

A systematic approach in order to demonstrate replicability and transparency (Hart, 2018). The specific questions posed in this review were 1) What are the experiences of people living with advanced COPD?, 2) What are the factors influencing the experiences and quality of life of people with advanced COPD?, 3) What are the psychological and

social aspects of people living with advanced COPD?, 4) What are the risk factors of people with COPD for presenting increased psychological burden and lower quality of life? 5) What can be offered in palliative care for people with advanced COPD?.

The initial literature search began in January 2018 and annual updates were carried out until April 2022. Both published and unpublished studies were searched in a comprehensive literature review in Medical Literature and Analysis and Retrieval System Online (MEDLINE), PubMed, PsycInfo, Web of Science, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), ETHOS and Dart Europe.

The predefined terms were combined to identify experiences and psychosocial impact (such as quality of life, psychosocial, psychological, social, experiences, anxiety, depression) of living with advanced COPD (COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, advanced COPD, end-stage COPD, severe COPD, very severe COPD, terminal COPD, GOLD stage 3 COPD, GOLD stage 4 COPD) in palliative care (i.e. terminal care, end-of-life care, end of life, terminal, palliative care, hospice, day hospice, breathlessness service, breathlessness clinic, breathe easy).

Coupled with this search strategy, a hand search for cross-reference of relevant papers and narrative commentaries on COPD was conducted. This augmented the number of papers on experiences of living with COPD, palliative care and breathlessness services. Papers were screened for inclusion by reading abstracts and removing duplicates. The remaining papers were evaluated for eligibility based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed below.

Original studies were considered for this review. Publications from 2000 onwards were included due to the advancements in palliative care, and newer data seemed to be more applicable to the proposed study. Studies with adult patients with severe or very severe COPD or caregivers and healthcare professionals who discussed it, with a focus on patients' end-of-life stage in palliative care, were considered. Papers which presented QOL as well as psychological and social aspects of living with COPD were allowed. Studies not published or translated into English were excluded due to the possible struggle to retrieve legitimate interpretations which could have caused a potential language bias. This review aimed to identify and analyse data published on this topic; thus, all study designs were included in the review.

The research strategy produced 1067 possibly relevant papers for the selection process. After removing duplicates, 456 articles were left and abstracts were screened. 278 full articles were retrieved and examined as they met the inclusion criteria. Finally, 85 articles were included in the review, 31 papers were qualitative in design, 52 with a quantitative design and 2 mixed methods. All studies included in this review collected data appropriately to ethical considerations and provided relevant evidence with a transparent description of findings and implications for practical use or further studies. The papers included in the review are presented thematically under the following headings: 1) Quality of Life and Psychosocial Aspects of Living with COPD and 2) Palliative Care Services for People with COPD.

2.2. Quality of Life and Psychosocial Aspects of Living with Advanced COPD

2.2.1. COPD and Quality of Life

Living with COPD substantially affects and impairs the QOL of patients (Giacomini *et al.*, 2012; Zamzam *et al.*, 2012; Brien *et al.*, 2018). QOL is an essential health outcome indicator for healthcare personnel, on basis of which they can make medical decisions (Bullinger and Quitmann, 2014). WHO defined QOL as people's impression of their situation in life with regard to their culture, values, goals and expectations (WHO, 1997). When focusing on health-related quality of life (HRQOL), Hays and Reeve (2010) specified that it only includes factors that are part of a person's health. In fact, as previously mentioned, the BPS model is related to HRQOL as it includes physical and emotional health as well as social aspects (Nicassio *et al.*, 2011; Strober, 2018; Muller *et al.*, 2020).

QOL of patients with COPD can be affected by many factors. Several studies have reported on the association of psychological burden and QOL and indicated that higher QOL was positively correlated with psychological well-being. Hynninen, Pallesen and Nordhus (2007), conducted a study in a subsample of 58 subjects recruited to a RCT of cognitive behavioural therapy intervention in persons with COPD and co-morbid anxiety and/or depression. The results showed no association between severity, measured by spirometry, and disease-specific QOL. In contrast, health status scores were positively correlated with symptoms of anxiety and depression. Notwithstanding, a criterion for inclusion in the study was the presence of co-morbid anxiety and/or depression; therefore, the associations between health status and psychological distress may be different in other COPD samples. Later, Blinderman *et al.* (2009) investigated in a longitudinal

observational study a cohort of 100 patients with severe COPD (FEV1 pred. 24.4%) and reported that they experienced a moderate impairment in overall QOL. A significant model emerged from the multivariate analyses, which involved an extensive collection of measures and instruments. It indicated that two-thirds of the variance in QOL scores were predicted by a mix of general symptom distress, mental health and extent of social behaviour impairment. In the same vein, Jang *et al.* (2019), in their prospective cross-sectional study, enrolled 80 patients with severe COPD and investigated disease-specific QOL, using the St George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ) and the Short Form 36 Health Survey Questionnaire (SF-36) for generic HRQOL and reported that depression was a significant predictor of disease-specific and general HRQOL. They suggested that early screening and addressing depression could improve the HRQOL of people with severe COPD. Nevertheless, the cross-sectional nature of the analysis did not allow them to measure any possible aetiological correlations between depression and COPD-related changes in HRQOL over time.

Similar findings were reported in a study by Brandl *et al.* (2018), which investigated what factors affect HRQOL in a group of 206 participants with all COPD stages (60.7% male, age 65.3) recruited from primary care settings (practices) and secondary ones (hospitals). The largest group had GOLD 4 (34.7%), followed by GOLD 3 (32.1%), GOLD 2 (28.4%) and only 4.7% represented people with GOLD 1 COPD. The physical and mental components of Short Form 12 questionnaire (SF-12) were used to assess HRQOL, while the COPD Assessment Test (CAT) was used to measure COPD symptoms and functional status. HADS was administered for patient-reported anxiety and depression. Significant negative correlations were noted between symptom distress, functional status and mental

HRQOL. The findings suggested that improvements of HRQOL may be achieved by focusing on patient-reported outcomes as well as by screening for depression and anxiety with potential successive treatment. The downside of this study is that the results could be affected by its cross-sectional design, not allowing for an exploration of causal relationships. In this way, the self-reported outcome could be affected by day sensitivities such as mood or stress on a given day. When exploring patients' narratives, Marx *et al.* (2016) revealed that the participants experienced varied physical restrictions and reduced HRQOL, which could have been affected by insufficient knowledge about the disease and vague awareness of the clinical symptoms of the condition. These findings cast a light on the importance of disease-related expectations as well as the need for furthering patients' education.

Another qualitative study by Ek and Ternstedt (2008) found that living with COPD and having living space limitations fundamentally influenced QOL. The participants reported that their physical limitations forced them to stop everyday activities, contributing to social isolation. One of the findings of the study was that the patients viewed their lives differently. Believing that life was meaningful and having a feeling of involvement gave some of them a willingness and energy to continue living and reimagine the future. In contrast, for some participants being unable to perform previous activities contributed to feeling that life was meaningless.

The quality of the healthcare provision was also identified as a potential factor that affects QOL. Habraken *et al.* (2008), a Dutch study with 11 end-stage people with COPD, exploring the silence of COPD and the reasons why patients do not seek help, reported

that impaired QOL of individuals with end-stage COPD could be caused by not receiving adequate assistance from healthcare providers, which in turn could be attributed to patients' lack of knowledge about their condition and potential improvement of some symptoms. Therefore, they rarely discussed their problems with a physician, thus leading to delays in receiving help.

The studies agree that the QOL of people with COPD is impaired and can be affected by many factors such as anxiety, depression, social functioning, education of patients and communication with healthcare workers. However, to date, no study has focused on investigating the QOL of people with advanced COPD, who attend palliative care services leaving a window for researching these aspects.

2.2.2. Social Aspects of Living with COPD

Several studies investigating the social aspects of living with COPD have been carried out on the social limitations of those patients. The review by Gardiner *et al.* (2010) reported that decreased physical activity impairs patients' social functioning abilities, resulting in relative absence of social relationships, social isolation and consequently reduced QOL. In their review of 31 qualitative studies, Russell *et al.* (2018), provided insight into COPD life stresses. The review outlined that reduced mobility, embarrassment and fear of symptoms can considerably disrupt social relationships, increase isolation and loneliness, and place a burden on healthcare providers and social networks. Gysels and Higginson (2008), recognised that social isolation was an indirect result of disease experience. They noted that breathlessness was found to be shameful because it could be self-inflicted and patients were afraid of their social circle's reaction, fearing embarrassment when becoming breathless in front of friends. They also felt

uncomfortable showing others how they depend on breath supporting devices. Moreover, patients described that coughing and bringing up phlegm added to the feeling of anxiety, further contributing to refraining from contact with the outside world. In the same vein, Ek and Ternestedt (2008) described that being unable to perform certain activities was considered a humiliation and a failure, for example, when failing to eat meals in a certain way while having breathing problems. Similarly, Avşar and Kaşıkçı (2011) noted that experiencing COPD symptoms, feeling embarrassed, and being dependent on their carers caused emotional and social distress, preventing patients from attending crowded places.

Loss of social relationships is a complex aspect and has a diverse effect on people's lives. Seamark *et al.* (2004) investigated this aspect in-depth in a group of 10 patients with severe COPD and 8 carers. The study focused on the experience of living with COPD and their current palliative care needs, and pointed to the importance of care surveillance and better information sharing. The results reported that due to the numerous daily activities distress might appear and it can be a reason for refraining from social relationships. Consequently, having missed many social events, patients felt that they lacked topics to talk about. The study stated that patients experienced loss of contact with family and had reduced interaction, especially with their grandchildren. Strang, Ekberg-Jansson and Henoeh (2014), exploring 31 severely ill COPD patients' experience of anxiety and their strategies to alleviate it, reported that social isolation from family members transformed personal contacts into telephone relationships, which enabled them to keep in touch when physically unable to meet and provided the patients with a source of meaning and joy. Lately, Landers *et al.* (2015) investigated living with severe

COPD and end-of-life issues, particularly after a life-threatening event, amongst 15 participants receiving NIV. The study found six emerging milestones of disease progression: loss of recreation, restricted home environment, episodes of acute care, long-term oxygen treatment, panic attacks and assistance with self-care. The study reported that loss of recreation and previous activities such as spending time with friends and family is a milestone of advancing COPD.

As it follows, refraining from social activities leads to feeling lonely and Kanervisto, Kaistila and Paavilainen (2007) reported that patients mentioned both social and existential loneliness. Despite having people around, patients with COPD still felt alone and worthless since they could not join and perform activities as they used to, due to their reduced strength. In addition, Schroedl *et al.* (2014) investigated healthcare needs in a sample of 20 patients admitted to a hospital for an acute exacerbation and identified experiencing loneliness and inability to leave home as a usual consequence of COPD. Nevertheless, this cohort may not demonstrate the needs affecting the day-to-day life of people with stable COPD.

Another factor affecting patients' social lives with COPD was recognised by Strang, Ekberg-Jansson and Henoch (2014) and Landers *et al.* (2015) was the growing dependence on caregivers due to increasing physical restrictions. Patients felt they were a burden for their support system as they required help from friends or family to stay at home. Being able to be responsible for self-care, such as independently using the toilet, shower, bath, and dressing themselves, was essential in maintaining their dignity. Consequently, considering the fact that patients did not want to rely on others, being

helpless and incapable of performing these tasks could cause frustration and disappointment.

Growing dependence on carers can result in different aspects, such as losing freedom. The Cicutto, Brooks and Henderson (2004) study employed a qualitative design, conducting seven focus groups with 42 individuals, 25% of whom used oxygen therapy, and investigated the factors which influenced self-care among those who had or had not attended a pulmonary rehabilitation programme. The findings showed that not being in charge of their own life and schedule while being dependent on others, led to a feeling of losing freedom.

Other authors found that the quality of the relationships with carers was affected by the growing dependence on them. Feeling to be a burden to a family is relatively frequent and common (Seamark *et al.*, 2004). A qualitative study in Sweden Elofsson and Ohlén (2004) was conducted in a small sample of six elderly COPD persons (two of whom lived in their own flats and the rest in nursing homes or service flats) in order to achieve a deeper understanding of the lived experience of elderly (78-88 years old) and severely ill patients. They found that the patients felt neglected by family members despite living with them. Another study which focused on the severe COPD population of Kanervisto, Kaistila and Paavilainen (2007) indicated that patients had an impression that other people did not fully understand their serious condition and felt that relatives avoided them. In turn, patients stayed away from them despite having an opportunity for close relationships, thus creating a vicious circle.

Notably, Cohen (2004) explained the mechanism through which QOL is impacted by social influences. He reported that social networks relate to health outcomes and that social relatedness directly benefits health by supporting social control and information. Hence, it seems that it has the potential to motivate people to boost self-care and accountability for others and stimulate positive attitude and self-worth.

In psychiatry, an expressed emotion measurement of the family environment was discussed as a reliable psychosocial predictor of mental illness exacerbation (Butzlaff and Hooley, 1998). High expressed emotions, which refer to family members being hostile, critical and not tolerant of the patient, can be a source of psychological stress, which exacerbates mental illness according to the vulnerability-stress model, previously discussed with the BPS model (Monroe and Simons, 1991; Amaresha and Venkatasubramanian, 2012). Although this topic has not been debated in a COPD context, it sheds light on the importance of the family environment and the quality of relationships.

A review by Barton, Effing and Cafarella (2015) concluded that for people with COPD adequate perceived social support consistently shows positive effects on mental health, self-efficacy, self-care and treatment adherence. However, what remains unclear are the characteristics of social networks, as well as their influence on the health and well-being of people with COPD. Lett *et al.* (2009) explored and evaluated depression and low social support in a cohort with chronic heart disease with 705 participants. The study suggested that the type of relationship (i.e., partner, friend, extended family, co-worker) and its quality may also affect the way the COPD patient perceives the support or interaction.

Namely, solid support from a significant person may reassure and relieve anxiety more than a colleague's attempts to provide support.

Besides, the quality of the relationship, with its positive aspect, such as emotional support, and its negative ones like conflict and stress, can also impact the interaction experience. Literature acknowledges the importance of these aspects, which can be suppressed by emotional factors, considering the fact that a spouse or a child usually provides care (Gautun, Werner and Lurås, 2012; Cruz, Marques and Figueiredo, 2017; Sigurgeirsdottir *et al.*, 2020).

Although lack of social connections, high social isolation, and poor social relationships are recognised risk factors for mortality in the general population (Holt-Lunstad, 2018), it has not been yet acknowledged in the COPD population. Positive social support was recognised as related to reduced hospitalisations, fewer exacerbations, improved health status and better disease management behaviours (Dinicola *et al.*, 2013). Yet, no consistent evidence exists for these associations.

Social networks, which are social relationships surrounding a person, can also benefit individuals with COPD (Smith and Christakis, 2008). Talking to others and sharing their experiences, especially during support peer groups or pulmonary rehabilitation, seems beneficial to the patients as it gives them the strength to continue living and encourages them to leave home. Cicutto, Brooks and Henderson (2004) pointed out that peer support was essential for various reasons, i.e., confirmation of experiences, feeling not alone, information acquisition and gaining motivational insight. That is, the individuals, through contact with their peers, gained motivation which came from two sources: one, when they

saw a peer successfully coping and living life to the best of their abilities and the other, when they saw another peer in a worse condition than theirs.

Other authors confirmed that interaction with peers gave patients opportunities to enjoy the company of others, a feeling of affirmation of lived experience and a chance to make new friendships (Gysels and Higginson, 2009; Hayle *et al.*, 2013). However, more research on the value and importance of social networks for people with COPD is needed (Lenferink, van der Palen and Effing, 2018).

2.2.3. Experiencing Psychological Distress when Living with COPD

Psychological distress involves non-specific symptoms of stress, depression and anxiety (Viertiö *et al.*, 2021). High levels of psychological distress may incite mental disorders like anxiety and depression (Cuijpers *et al.*, 2009). The symptoms of depression in people with COPD can be characterised as feelings of despair and pessimism, social withdrawal, decreased sleep and appetite, increased apathy, problems with concentration and performing daily life activities, lower self-reported health and poor self-management of exacerbations (Laurin *et al.*, 2012; Aras *et al.*, 2017). Subsequently, it may induce patients' reaction to the losses, including functional effects such as withdrawing from occupational activities, roles rearrangement in the family (Norwood, 2007; Avşar and Kaşıkçı, 2011) and fear of becoming a burden to them (Gysels and Higginson, 2011).

Anxiety, which is common among people with COPD, is a state of uneasiness and worrying about real or perceived future events (Hawken, Turner-Cobb and Barnett, 2018; Domhardt *et al.*, 2019; Chand and Marwaha, 2022). Anxiety disorder is the generalised term for an array of atypical and pathological fear and anxiety states such as generalised

anxiety disorder, panic disorder, agoraphobia, obsessive-compulsive disorder, phobic disorders and traumatic stress disorder (Bystritsky *et al.*, 2013). Generalised anxiety disorder and panic disorder, which manifest themselves in various ways, such as physiological signs of arousal, e.g., tachycardia, sweating, dyspnoea (Gale and Davidson, 2007), exist more often in patients with COPD compared to the general population (Willgoss and Yohannes, 2013).

In people with COPD, anxiety and panic attacks can be provoked by experiencing physical symptoms which aggravate psychological symptoms and vice versa, contributing to developing a vicious circle (Kaptein *et al.*, 2008; Regvat *et al.*, 2011; Doyle *et al.*, 2013). This view is supported by Bailey (2004), who interviewed people with COPD, their family caregivers and nurses, using an ethnographic research design. The study aimed to explore the anxiety, the affective component of dyspnoea, of people with COPD who have undergone acute exacerbation. The findings uncovered a “dyspnoea-anxiety-dyspnoea cycle”, a vicious circle of breathlessness and anxiety, which indicates an emotional response to breathlessness, with anxiety consequently intensifying their feeling of breathlessness. Thus, the results pointed to an interplay between BPS aspects and indicated that anxiety might be a valid indicator of physical disease severity for patients with COPD in acute respiratory distress. Willgoss *et al.* (2012) also wrote on the vicious circle of the deteriorating symptoms and the direct experiences of anxiety, after interviewing 14 community patients with stable COPD. The results revealed three life-changing thematic networks: relationships with breathing, fighting for control and panic attacks. The findings showed a complex and perplexing interaction between anxiety and dyspnoea, leading to deteriorating symptoms and deconditioning, and indicated that there

are two types of anxiety. In one group, individuals became anxious due to experiencing breathlessness (dyspnoea-related anxiety) and in the other group breathlessness resulted from anxiety induced by other triggers. Moreover, Willgoss *et al.* (2012) argued that, irrespective of triggers, it is apparent that anxiety and panic attacks were related to powerful fear, loss of control, and thoughts of hopelessness, leading to loneliness and social isolation, which corresponds to the BPS model. Aggravated anxiety can also be attributed to other psychological causes such as fear of the future and fear of death, reliance on others and loss of control (Gilman and Banzett, 2009; Livermore, Sharpe and McKenzie, 2010; Yohannes and Alexopoulos, 2014a). Likewise, Strang, Ekberg-Jansson and Henoeh (2014) explored experiences of anxiety and interviewed 31 patients with severe and very severe COPD. From the analysis emerged three major themes: death anxiety, life anxiety and counterweights to anxiety. Death anxiety involved fear of suffocation, awareness of death, fear of dying and separation anxiety. Life anxiety concerned fear of living and fear of the future. Consequently, the abovementioned fears, in addition to experiencing breathlessness, can contribute to developing a phobic restraint of physical activity. Counterweights to anxiety included avoiding strategy, coping with suffocation and developing a sense of joy from resisting their vulnerable situation. A broader perspective was outlined in the American Thoracic Society statement by Parshall *et al.* (2012), which argued that patients with COPD may feel anxious about becoming breathless so they avoid activities which can provoke inconvenient symptoms. Finally, individuals with COPD and depression as well as anxiety symptoms tend to have a lower ability of self-management. They can, as reviews reported, manifest a poor ability to cope

with chronic disease and exacerbations (Pumar *et al.*, 2014) due to low self-confidence or self-efficacy (Yohannes, 2008).

2.2.4. Risk Factors for Presenting Increased Psychological Burden and Lower Quality of Life

The physical and psychological burdens of the disease are interconnected (Ozalevli *et al.*, 2017); that is, a higher severity of COPD is related to a higher incidence of anxiety and depression (Omachi *et al.*, 2009; Schneider *et al.*, 2010; Hanania, Mullerova and Locantore, 2011). A study in Netherlands by van Manen *et al.* (2002) showed that 21.6% of patients with severe COPD have depression, with a 2.5 times greater likelihood of exhibiting depression compared to controls (aged 40 or more, without a registered diagnosis of asthma or COPD). The study also reported that oxygen-dependent patients were at a higher risk of depression than controls, with rates up to 62%. In comparison, Xiao *et al.* (2018) indicated that patients with mild COPD in urban communities had much lower prevalence of anxiety (7.6%) and depression (13.1%).

Smoking is correlated with presenting psychological distress (McClave *et al.*, 2010; Fluharty *et al.*, 2017; Skov-Ettrup *et al.*, 2017). Firstly, the role of smoking in lung impairment may cause self-blame, shame and a feeling of guilt. The latter and the knowledge of the nature of the disease and its progressive, incurable character can generate a feeling of helplessness and nihilism, which may cause poor adherence treatment and poor motivation self-care (Sheridan *et al.*, 2011; Strang *et al.*, 2014; Fusi-Schmidhauser, Froggatt and Preston, 2020; Jerpseth *et al.*, 2021). Secondly, smoking not only hastens the progression of COPD (von Leupoldt *et al.*, 2012) but may also worsen the COPD symptoms, such as breathlessness, and increase the frequency of

coexisting exacerbations, which in turn may negatively affect the mood (Milanowska *et al.*, 2017). Finally, the inflammatory consequences of smoking, activation of nicotine acetylcholine receptors, hypoxia, as well as the deregulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system are reported to contribute to the onset of depression and anxiety (Pumar *et al.*, 2014).

The significant socioeconomic burden related to COPD impacts QOL (Miravittles *et al.*, 2011; Rehman *et al.*, 2021). A cross-sectional, observational, multicentre study in Spain by Miravittles *et al.* (2011) showed that lower educational level and belonging to unskilled professional groups results in a poorer HRQOL even in a country where access to healthcare services is universal and free. The financial situation has been identified as another factor impacting the QOL. A number of authors have found that people with COPD with higher income demonstrated a higher level of QOL, particularly in spheres such as mental and social performance; this is because sufficient financial resources, apart from ensuring basic life needs, allow actively spending free time, lively social contacts and greater psychological comfort of the patient (Garrido *et al.*, 2006; Mody and Smith, 2006; Rosińczuk, Przyszlak and Uchmanowicz, 2018). In contrast, retired people with COPD living with financial difficulties find that a higher social disadvantage puts a greater burden on their everyday lives (Himani, Badini and Nanji, 2018). The study conducted in the US and UK, in a population aged 35-74 and an average of 6.5 years since being diagnosed, found that patients were forced to stop working and had to bear the cost of treatment of COPD symptoms, which caused additional expenditure, ergo adding to the economic impact (Cook *et al.*, 2019). As a matter of fact, most participants in the studies on depression and anxiety in people with COPD are retired. Orbon *et al.*

(2005), in a study with 210 COPD patients, with mean age 53.9 and COPD severity of FEV1% pred. 63.5%, with secondary analyses of a RCT, reported that, when considering a similar level of severity of the disease, it turns out that working people have higher QOL than pensioners and those who were forced to retire earlier. However, the cross-sectional design of this study does not allow to discover the cause and consequence of this phenomenon; therefore, it cannot be determined if high QOL facilitates having a working status or if continuing to have a job improves QOL of people with COPD, or is it both.

Additionally, there is an ambiguous relationship between being at risk of mental health problems or psychological distress and having a social network or living alone. The study of Jacob, Haro and Koyanagi (2019), using English nationally representative community-based data of 20503 individuals, reported that the prevalence of common mental disorders was higher in people living alone than in those who did not. That is, the multivariable logistic regression analysis showed that people living alone had a significant 1.39–2.43 times higher odds for having mental health disorders. Correspondingly, considering the physical burden of people with COPD, which already puts them at a higher risk of developing mental health disorders, living alone is another factor which may contribute to developing depression, even in those in earlier stages of the disease (Schane *et al.*, 2008; Lee *et al.*, 2018). The correlation between living alone and depression may be explained as patients have less caregiver's physical and emotional support, thus increasing their feeling of burdensomeness and leading to depression development (Gudmundsson *et al.*, 2006; Himani, Badini and Nanji, 2018), which corresponds to the BPS elements of the disease and makes people with COPD subjects to higher levels of psychological distress. Also, lack of suitable family support seems to

be an essential factor for the pathogenesis of depressive symptoms. Notably, those patients who received support from families or friends presented a lower level of depression than those whose families reacted with anxiety, exasperation, insufficient care and carelessness (Gudmundsson *et al.*, 2006; Himani, Badini and Nanji, 2018). A qualitative study with informal caregivers in Iceland suggested that the education of family members and carers is a strong recommendation for dealing with this disease (Sigurgeirsdottir *et al.*, 2020). Likewise, communities and families should be aware of psychological distress symptoms and connected risk factors in order to prevent further progression, and earlier screening should be carried out to strengthen social networks (Himani, Badini and Nanji, 2018).

Several studies have also attempted to analyse age correlation with the psychological burden. They demonstrated that younger age was another risk factor of higher psychological distress (Hanania, Mullerova and Locantore, 2011; Mi *et al.*, 2017; Phan *et al.*, 2019). Gender may also have an influence on the incidence of psychological distress. Namely, depression and anxiety disorders are more common among females than males (5.1% and 4.6%, respectively) at a global level of a general population, according to the latest estimates (WHO, 2017). This is also true for the COPD population, with previous studies reporting that females have higher rates of depression and anxiety (Hanania, Mullerova and Locantore, 2011; Raheison *et al.*, 2014; Mi *et al.*, 2017; Xiao *et al.*, 2018). Previously Naberan *et al.* (2012), in a Spanish multi-centre cross-sectional observational study including 4574 patients with COPD (n=740, 16.7% females) who attended primary care and pulmonary clinics, reported that although the COPD prevalence in males is higher than in females, it appears that the latter have higher levels of depression, anxiety

and lower QOL. Additionally, in a Hynninen, Pallesen and Nordhus (2007) study with 58 COPD outpatients (FEV1 53.79% pred.) and comorbid anxiety and/or depression, the results showed that females exhibited more anxiety distress measured with the Beck Anxiety Inventory and more comorbid conditions, even when being younger and having less severe COPD. A study by Breeman *et al.* (2015), providing normative data from the UK sample, confirmed that HADS scores vary by gender, namely that females present higher results in its both scales. Buist *et al.* (2007) in a population-based a study with 9425 participants reported that COPD is a disease mainly affecting elderly males. However, recently the disease has a growing prevalence among females, who present the condition differently from males, especially in disease mechanisms, comorbidities and symptom profile (Martinez *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, there are factors in delaying diagnosis and treatment in the care of females. Specifically, females remain twice less likely to be diagnosed with COPD than males, as spirometry and referral to pulmonologists are less accessible to them (Han *et al.*, 2007). Correspondingly, a delay in the COPD diagnosis has been observed for the female population, partly due to the reported insufficiencies in the quality of the care provided for their COPD, but also as a result of voluntary postponement and suffering symptoms of fatigue and depression (Martinez *et al.*, 2012). This highlights the importance of gender-tailored symptom management. In a study with 371 participants in China, Zhang *et al.* (2021) reported the importance of gender-tailored symptom management. They showed that in order to improve fatigue, sleep quality, frailty and symptom management strategies, anxiety and depression should be closely looked at in females, and breathlessness and chest tightness in males. Attention should be paid to smoking cessation in males because a

higher number of males smoke than females, and they are more prone to cough and sputum.

2.2.5. Mental Health Treatment and Support

Previous research has indicated that people with COPD with depression and anxiety symptoms tend to have these untreated, regardless of the recommendation for providing psychological support for these patients (Yohannes and Alexopoulos, 2014a; Hart *et al.*, 2021). Kunik *et al.* (2005), in a cross-sectional study with 1334 patients with COPD in the US, reported that mental health treatment was offered only to half of the patients with COPD with anxiety or depression diagnosis. In the same vein, a retrospective study in the UK by Elkington *et al.* (2005), based on surveys about deceased patients with COPD, recorded that a troubling mere 18% of 209 patients with end-stage COPD received treatment for low mood. A cause evidenced in the literature was that healthcare professionals' paucity of mental health knowledge and training might restrain them from diagnosing and admitting patients to suitable treatment interventions (Dury, 2016). Likewise, Hart *et al.* (2021), in their qualitative study in the US, showed that pulmonary clinicians claimed that they lacked training and resources to support these patients, and that they focused more on the physical symptom management rather than on emotional distress.

Anxiety and depression management can be separated into pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment. Based on the literature, several treatment options are available for people with COPD. Antidepressant medications are an option for treating the mood of patients with COPD. Yet, there have been few studies on the effectiveness of

antidepressants in the COPD population and they have been inconclusive; therefore, the efficacy of antidepressants cannot be determined (Fritzsche, Clamor and von Leupoldt, 2011; Yohannes and Alexopoulos, 2014b).

A review by Cafarella (2012) summarised possible non-pharmacological treatment options for mental health problems in COPD: Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), self-management programmes, pulmonary rehabilitation and self-help groups. It also mentioned relaxation therapy, palliative care, interpersonal psychotherapy, more extensive disease management programmes and supportive therapy.

Regarding psychological interventions such as CBT, a Pakistani study by Himani, Badini and Nanji (2018) recognised that clinicians should advise individual and group counselling for patients at psychological risk in order to support positive mental health outcomes and ameliorate the patients' QOL. In a RCT in the UK, involving 279 people with mild to very severe stages of COPD, Heslop-Marshall *et al.* (2018) found that CBT led by a respiratory nurse effectively reduced anxiety symptoms and was cost-effective. The CBT group had lower hospital admissions and attendance at the emergency departments, compared to the group which received self-help leaflets. Therefore, CBT as well as patient education should be included in self-management plans. Currently National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2018) recommended that self-management plans should include patient education and cognitive behavioural treatment for breathlessness. The purpose of self-management programmes is to recognise symptoms, teach skills required to carry out medical regimens, particularly for chronic disease, and to guide health approach changes in order to aid patients to manage their disease with its physical and

psychological consequences in order to enhance their well-being (Effing *et al.*, 2012; Mitchell *et al.*, 2014). In the palliative care domain, self-management denotes providing patients and carers with abilities to take care of the medical aspects of disease, be in charge of life roles and adapt to the irregular dynamics generated by disease and its progression (Davidson, Whyte and Richardson, 2012). In their definition of self-management, a review by Barlow *et al.* (2002) explained that it affects one's capacity to monitor their condition, which can further generate behavioural, cognitive and emotional reactions vital for preserving QOL. Self-management interventions have been primarily related to an approach centred on healthcare professionals teaching patients how to employ a prepared action plan in case of an exacerbation (Effing *et al.*, 2007; Walters *et al.*, 2010). For instance, educational interventions such as breathing exercises, which improve exercise capacity, were found to positively affect HRQOL and reduce subsequent hospitalisations (Effing *et al.*, 2007; Holland *et al.*, 2012; Zwerink *et al.*, 2014).

Pulmonary rehabilitation is an encompassed exercise training and an integral part of the rehabilitation of pulmonary function. It focuses on maintaining muscular strength, education and self-behavioural management, which helps to lower anxiety and depression symptoms for patients with moderate to severe COPD (GOLD, 2022). Furthermore, pulmonary rehabilitation combined with psychological intervention is reported to reduce depressive symptoms more significantly than pulmonary rehabilitation intervention alone (Pollok *et al.*, 2019), especially when introduced in the early stages of the condition (Coventry, 2009). A Canadian survey indicated that a mere 16% of patients with COPD were referred to pulmonary rehabilitation, and only 60% of them attended (Hernandez *et al.*, 2009). Data from a national audit of COPD care, which included people

with COPD in England and Wales, found that 16% of people with diagnosed COPD were referred to pulmonary rehabilitation from primary care and that lower odds of referral were attributed to those who were older, females, more deprived, or had comorbidity of diabetes, asthma or painful condition (Stone *et al.*, 2020). A following study by Stone *et al.* (2021) informed that 66% of those referred to pulmonary rehabilitation completed it. They reported factors contributing to low odds of pulmonary rehabilitation programme completion by patients such as living in the most deprived quintile, being underweight, severely obese or with more severe COPD and breathlessness. Previously, Keating, Lee and Holland (2011), conducted a qualitative study in Australia with 19 participants who declined to uphold pulmonary rehabilitation (2 with mild, 2 with moderate, 12 with severe and 3 with very severe COPD) and 18 who failed to complete the programme (7 with moderate, 8 with severe and 3 with very severe COPD). They reported that low completion of pulmonary rehabilitation programme might be attributed to lack of perceived benefits due to the fact that the stage of the disease was too severe, with patients feeling tired and not expecting any improvement. Telerehabilitation, which is a rehabilitation service delivered using communication technologies (Lundell *et al.*, 2015), has also been found to be beneficial for patients with COPD (Tsai *et al.*, 2016). Neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) can relieve breathlessness and improve exercise capacity in patients with severe COPD by enhancing quadriceps muscle mass and function (Vieira *et al.*, 2014). NMES can be used for those unwilling or unable to participate in pulmonary rehabilitation (Maddocks *et al.*, 2016), as during home-based training, it showed significant improvements in depression and overall HRQOL (Coquart *et al.*, 2016).

Another available service for patients with COPD is self-help groups, which are small voluntary groups constructed for reciprocal help and peer support which meet for a particular aim (Hashem and Merritt, 2018). Improved perceived social support and associated psychological assets were reported as benefits of self-help groups (Farquhar *et al.*, 2016; Bausewein *et al.*, 2018; Hashem and Merritt, 2018). Namely, in a review by Russell *et al.* (2018), the group meetings were reported to provide learning opportunities and encourage patients to expand peer networks, interact with peers, make friends, have the opportunity for social comparison, and therefore, they validated their experience.

Despite the availability of treatment, Cafarella (2012) concluded that there is a shortage of knowledge about a range of treatment options in the COPD population across care settings and recognised the need to assess the actual benefits of psychological support and healthcare delivery and to implement care for mood and anxiety disorders of patients with COPD. This indicates a necessity to understand the various treatments available for people with COPD and their effect on their psychological distress and QOL.

2.3. Palliative Care Services for People with COPD

2.3.1. Low Accessibility to Palliative Care Services for People with COPD

Recent studies showed that contact with health services usually consists of visits by the primary care team (general practitioner or a nurse) and emergency admissions to hospitals due to exacerbations (Elkington *et al.*, 2005). Other supports, such as specialist respiratory nursing, district nursing, community matron teams as well as specialist palliative care, are likely to be limited or even unavailable for people with COPD (Elkington *et al.*, 2005; Goodridge *et al.*, 2008; Rosenwax *et al.*, 2016; Rush *et al.*, 2017). Specialist

secondary care is often limited to the patients admitted to a hospital with exacerbations or referred because of uncontrolled disease (Worth *et al.*, 2011; Public Health England, 2015). Extra components added to the disease experience are lack of services or difficulties with accessing them, and it is crucial to understand what causes them.

WHO (2020) estimated that 10.3% of adults in need of palliative care suffer from chronic respiratory diseases. The United Kingdom has a relatively high palliative care services ratio of 15 service providers such as hospital units, palliative care teams, home care services per million (Centeno *et al.*, 2007). While there is the availability of palliative care services, studies show that they are not effectively utilised for people with COPD. The focus on the insufficient palliative care for people with COPD was initially reported in an English study by Gore, Brophy and Greenstone (2000), it was one of the first studies of medical and social care aspects of people with severe COPD (n=50, mean age of 70.5), which noticed the underuse of palliative care in a study that compared the COPD group with lung cancer patients. In the last decade, the literature still mentions the fact of low accessibility of palliative care services and unmet needs of the patients at the end-of-life care (Schroedl *et al.*, 2014; Vermeylen, Szmilowicz and Kalhan, 2015; Halpin, 2018). Bloom *et al.* (2018), in a cohort study, using electronic healthcare records from 2004-2015 retrieved from 674 primary care clinics in the UK, with 92,365 eligible COPD patients, of which 26,135 died, found that only 21.4% of the deceased cohort received any palliative care. Less than half of those who got palliative care received it only during the last six months of their lives and one-third in the last month before they died. Also, patients with both COPD and lung cancer were 40% more likely to receive palliative care than those with just COPD. In any case, the study observed a progressive use of palliative

care within the decade, identifying increasing awareness and use of palliative care and advocating a critical need to improve all parts of palliative care services, as opposed to mere terminal treatment for COPD patients in the UK. However, as noted by Halpin (2018), since the study used electronic records, there was a possibility of under-recording palliative care approaches, as some of the clinicians considered them to be an element of standard care (previously explained in 1.3. Diagnosis and Treatment of COPD) and did not code them. Nevertheless, the likelihood of under-recording was relatively little, and the results indicated that the vast majority of patients dying of COPD did not receive palliative care.

According to Halpin (2018), regardless of the considerable burden of COPD, there are no guidelines for palliative care implementation. Still, The Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management, and Prevention of Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) 2017 report advised that all clinicians overseeing patients with COPD ought to know about the adequacy of palliative care to control symptom management and implement palliative care services in their practice (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017). Previous literature found that in order to avoid prognosis paralysis, early use of palliative care is recommended alongside disease-oriented care (Epiphaniou *et al.*, 2014). However, recognising the most suitable moment for transition to palliative care can be challenging and is not precisely defined (Murray, Boyd and Sheikh, 2005). For one thing, Spathis and Booth (2008) in their review reported that the conventional model of care of patients with advanced disease, including COPD, is established on the foundation which involves an abrupt shift from life-sustaining care to palliative care. It also indicated that this model should not be applied to patients with COPD for various reasons. One of them is that COPD does not have an apparent

onset, the timing of death is unpredictable and it is challenging to decide on the time for the transition (Casanova *et al.*, 2011; Pinnock *et al.*, 2011; Giacomini *et al.*, 2012).

Another possible reason for delayed transition to palliative care reported in the literature is that health and social services flounder to recognise the problem of breathlessness and address it appropriately (Gysels and Higginson, 2008; Hasson *et al.*, 2008). Gysels and Higginson (2008) suggested that social and health workers' lack of expertise to manage this symptom discourages patients from sharing complaints, as they are often ignored. This may be caused by the fact that currently, healthcare workers of people with severe COPD have insufficient information to deal with them (Nurmatov *et al.*, 2012).

In order to facilitate this process for physicians in the UK, the "surprise question" was created. Initially, it was used for patients with various diagnoses. The question is: "Would you be surprised if your patient were to die in the next 12 months?" (Murray, Boyd and Sheikh, 2005). The answer "no" to the question indicates that the patient should be referred to palliative care services (Murray, Boyd and Sheikh, 2005; Seamark, Seamark and Halpin, 2007). The UK national policies follow "the surprise question" as a supplemental screening tool for primary care physicians to help identify COPD patients who would benefit from early and proactive palliative care (Murray and Boyd, 2011).

All national guidelines should promote early palliative care (Strutt, 2020). The UK follows recommendations by National Institute for Clinical Excellence (2004), which supports the idea that people with end-stage COPD and their caregivers should be able to access all the services provided by multidisciplinary palliative care teams, including hospice admission. There are suggestions in practice guidelines by the American Thoracic

Society, which are followed e.g. by Netherlands, to start palliative care earlier, during the curative/restorative phase of care (Lanken *et al.*, 2008). Some general recommendations have been acknowledged to facilitate the early recognition of COPD patients who would benefit from palliative care interventions. The recommendations are as follows: advanced age of more than 75 years (Bustamante-Fermosel *et al.*, 2007; Steer, Gibson and Bourke, 2010), comorbidities such as diabetes, cardiovascular and end-stage chronic renal disease (Steer, Gibson and Bourke, 2010; Ho *et al.*, 2014; Maters *et al.*, 2014), a change in a 6-min walk by 50m (Benzo *et al.*, 2013), FEV1 <30% pred. (Curtis, 2008) and low body mass index (BMI) (Hallin *et al.*, 2007). Poor functional status, HRQOL (Waschki *et al.*, 2011; Benzo *et al.*, 2013; Higginson *et al.*, 2014) and hospitalisation within last year (McGhan *et al.*, 2007) are other indicators. A review by Rajnoveanu *et al.* (2020) summarised that palliative care implementation should be started on the presence of refractory symptoms, patients' unmet needs and preferences. In Scotland in 2022, the following recommendations for palliative care referral are respected by NHS Lothian: patients who are in the palliative phase of their illness (the "surprise" question) and have at least two of the following: severe or restrictive airway obstruction and deficit (vital capacity 60%, transfer factor 40%), meeting the requirements for LTOT, have breathlessness at rest or on minimal exertion between exacerbations, persistent severe symptoms despite optimal tolerated therapy, symptomatic right heart failure, a BMI of less than 21, and, finally, more than three emergency admissions for infective exacerbations or respiratory failure in the last year (NHS Lothian, no date). It is recommended to plan decisions regarding a patient's end of life when indicators permit the identification of an estimated survival of less than six to twelve months (Braço Forte and Sousa, 2017).

2.3.2. Different Models of Providing Palliative Care for People with COPD

Within healthcare there are diverse services which provide palliative care for the COPD population (Radbruch and Payne, 2009; Scheerens *et al.*, 2018a). Palliative care services are organised differently in various regions of the world (Kayyali *et al.*, 2016; Centeno and Rhee, 2019). In the UK they can function as specialist services, with specialists exclusively providing palliative care (Gamondi, Larkin and Payne, 2013; Faull and Blankley, 2015), and non-specialist services, also known as generalist palliative care services, occasionally providing palliative care (Coyle and Paice, 2015).

Generalist palliative care can be provided by primary care professionals and specialists treating patients with life-threatening diseases who have fundamental palliative care skills and knowledge, with palliative care not being the focal point of their work (Gamondi, Larkin and Payne, 2013). Generalist palliative care is an essential and routine form of clinical practice which focuses on promoting physical and psychological health despite the diagnosis and prognosis (NHS England, 2016), and can be provided in various services, such as secondary or primary care. In fact, primary care providers are the main source of contact for COPD patients, administering about 80% of their care (Perez *et al.*, 2012), and their main focus is to provide treatment to reduce patients' symptoms and improve their QOL (Spyratos, Chloros and Sichletidis, 2012; van Boven *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 2.1. presents typical services in the pathway of COPC care in England. In the UK, community services incorporate respiratory teams and community nurses providing specialist support and basic care, such as respiratory team clinics, pulmonary rehabilitation and smoking cessation (Kayyali *et al.*, 2016; Scottish Government, 2017).

General Practitioners (GPs) start the pathway of care for people with COPD and have an essential impact on the community provision of end-of-life care (Kayyali *et al.*, 2016; Kjellstadli *et al.*, 2020). The follow-up is provided through GP visits, community services, hospital chest clinics, and special clinical teams, involving GPs, consultants, physiotherapists and nurses (Kayyali *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 2.1: COPD care pathways in England.

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The Picker Institute Europe (2008) suggested that community support yields considerable improvement for patients with COPD and their carers, such as enhancing their coping with the condition and reducing a need for emergency hospital admissions. A letter by Baxter and Cooper (2012) mentioned that the access to health service provision at a community level for COPD patients varies from only prescription contact to routine check-ups by a respiratory nurse specialist who works as a link between primary and secondary care. At the same time, severe exacerbations of COPD can be challenging to manage and are often beyond the skills and resources of the community team (Wong *et al.*, 2014).

The special clinical teams, which operate through local respiratory teams, are hospital based but provide services in the community (Kayyali *et al.*, 2016). Specialist respiratory services, managed from secondary care level, for patients with non-malignant and malignant respiratory conditions, involve healthcare professionals specialised in respiratory care and consist of respiratory nurse specialists, respiratory consultants and allied health professionals (Public Health England, 2015). Although it has not been explored in a palliative care context yet, integrated respiratory care has the potential to provide high-quality respiratory care (British Thoracic Society, 2019). According to Patel (2021), the integrated respiratory team is a concept of care for patients with respiratory diseases which is patient-centred, proactive, easily accessible and provided through clinical management and a multidisciplinary team. This model of care includes consultants, physiotherapists, specialist nurses, lung function technicians, and pharmacists collaborating across hospitals as well as communities and generic teams. Integrated respiratory care seems to correspond to the BPS approach of patient care. However, considering the fact that integrated respiratory care is likely to be determined

by the local prevalence of disease, available resources and patient demand, team members ought to understand the broader determinants of health and acquire abilities and knowledge regarding the management of chronic conditions and shared care planning, in order to navigate local health and social care system.

Chest physicians play an essential role in providing good quality end-of-life care (Duenk *et al.*, 2017; Goodridge and Peters, 2019). The majority of patients with advanced COPD initially receive secondary care services in the form of outpatient clinics (Hermiz *et al.*, 2002; López-Campos *et al.*, 2016). Seamark, Seamark and Halpin (2007) reported that some patients and carers benefit from the supervision provided by outpatient clinics and specialist nurses. However, several individuals perceived the experience of attending a hospital too exhausting, the consultation being routine, impersonal, cursory with deficiencies in treatment continuity.

Another available service presented in a technical report for NHS are supportive clinics, which are provided to aid patients with chronic diseases to manage their breathlessness in the context of palliative care (Aspinall, 2014). Every service tends to provide a different model and profile of supportive clinic, from different levels of palliative care, generalist or specialist, and is offered to patients with diverse conditions or focusing only on patients with COPD. Supportive clinics can be approached in various ways in a form such as Breathlessness Intervention Service (BIS) (Booth *et al.*, 2011), Breathe Easy groups (Hashem and Merritt, 2018), or a breathlessness support service (Higginson *et al.*, 2014). They all aim to improve the QOL of people suffering from breathing problems connected

with any life-limiting illness (Higginson *et al.*, 2006; Solano, Gomes and Higginson, 2006; Bausewein *et al.*, 2018).

Breathlessness services are multidisciplinary specialised services, nurse or physiotherapist run, held weekly or monthly, depending on service. These services are usually assisted by consultants in palliative care or respiratory medicine, depending on a service (Booth *et al.*, 2006; Farquhar *et al.*, 2016). A review of six RCTs published in 10 papers by Bausewein *et al.* (2018) showed that breathlessness services are a relatively new concept, appearing in the last 10-15 years, mainly in the UK. Consequently, till now, there has been little discussion in the literature about this service for people with COPD. So far, the breathlessness service was only discussed with a broader population of people with breathing difficulties. Higginson *et al.* (2014) reported that the breathlessness service provided to the experimental group included one point of access for patients, combined palliative care and respiratory medicine, and acted to the need for shared care at a stage in disease earlier than typically. They showed that breathlessness service supported and provided patients with coping strategies and interventions, helping them master their breathlessness while accepting that the disease cannot be cured.

Breathe Easy support group is a support network run by volunteers for people with respiratory conditions, supported by British Lung Foundation and Asthma+ (British Lung Foundation, no date). A study by Hashem and Merritt (2018) found social and educational benefits of attending a Breathe Easy group for people with respiratory conditions. Breathe Easy members were able to share their experiences and gain peer support from their support network. Likewise, the Breathe Easy sessions helped the group members adapt

and transform their lives, and understand the disease through self-education; thus helping them self-manage their condition. However, these results were based upon data from regular Breathe Easy group members who suffered from diverse respiratory health conditions, healthcare professionals, clinical commissioning group representatives and British Lung Foundations steering group members. Therefore, they did not analyse data from COPD patients separately, and it is not known how the findings could translate only to this population.

Farquhar *et al.* (2016) investigated BIS versus standard care for breathless patients with non-malignant conditions and their carers in a single-blind mixed methods RCT. The predominant disease group was represented by COPD patients, with 3rd and 4th GOLD stage. The study showed that BIS had a favourable impact on patients and carers in aspects of feeling distress caused by breathlessness. Also, they described experiencing less fear, anxiety, worry and feelings of panic, and they felt more confident about breathlessness. However, the effect was not significant compared to standard care and the study involved patients with various diagnoses. The authors advised conducting studies with mixed methods design only for COPD populations.

Specialist palliative care can be organised in different services, such as inpatient wards or consultation teams within hospitals, hospices or palliative care at home (Gaertner *et al.*, 2012; Hayle *et al.*, 2013; Véron *et al.*, 2018). The specialist palliative care services provide needs-based care instead of diagnosis-based one (Lockett *et al.*, 2014). Generally, hospices attendance was reported to bring patients positive experiences, such as end-of-life communication being more common there (Hench *et al.*, 2021). Hospice

care presents an entity with a friendly, informal, peaceful, compassionate and relaxed atmosphere, making patients feel safe and secure (Hayle *et al.*, 2013; Tornøe *et al.*, 2014; Sandsdalen *et al.*, 2016). A social asset of attending day hospice was noted, as it allowed patients to leave their home, provided opportunities to socialise and compare their experience of the disease with others (Fisher, O'Connor and Abel, 2008; Hayle *et al.*, 2013).

In contrast, review of Spathis and Booth (2008) recognised some drawbacks of hospices for the COPD population, as specialists sometimes are not well informed about the management of non-malignant diseases, and respiratory specialists lack guidance in palliation skills. In fact, the research to date has not tended to focus on specialist palliative care for patients with COPD, and the generalisability of the published research on this issue is limited. Hayle *et al.* (2013) presented the only study that examined the COPD patients who received palliative care in a day hospice. This English-based study reported various beneficial aspects of attending a hospice. It was recognised for its holistic approach in aiming to improve QOL and day-to-day symptom management. Most participants presented improved psychological well-being, including enhanced confidence, mood and self-esteem. Although it was hard to distinguish a specific factor responsible for these improvements, patients agreed on the staff's positive effect, which helped them be more open and express their feelings honestly. Additionally, some patients noticed a social asset of attending a day hospice, as it empowered them to leave their homes, giving them opportunities to socialise. Furthermore, participating in a day hospice allowed them to compare their experience with other COPD patients to validate their lived experience. Thus, specialist palliative care service in a hospice seems to

positively influence the social life and well-being of COPD patients. Although the sample in this study was small (n=8) and recruited from one service, disallowing to generalise the results due to the possibility of a standpoint bias, the findings still shed some light on the experiences of this underrepresented group of patients in the specialist palliative care settings.

Another study which explored patients with COPD receiving specialist palliative care was a qualitative study by Véron *et al.* (2018), with 18 people with severe and very severe COPD, investigating the usefulness of a RCT comprising of intervention of early palliative care in specialist palliative care. The early palliative care intervention involved a visit of experienced nurses specialised in palliative care once a month for one year. The study reported no major differences between the group receiving standardised general care and the intervention. However, the study has weaknesses that could have affected the credibility of such results. The data were recollected after patients' participation in a trial and some participants, due to their cognitive difficulties, functional limitations, overwhelming anxiety, focus on the present or perceived helplessness could have had problems recollecting the intervention. Therefore, the delay between the intervention and the interviews may have contributed to participants' problems with recollecting the intervention. Despite the weaknesses of this study, the results implied a need for collecting data from these patients in the shortest period of time and left a need for further exploring this underrepresented population in the literature.

2.4. Chapter Summary

This review is directed towards an in-depth discussion of living with COPD in a palliative care context. It includes a discussion of service options, available to COPD and non-COPD populations, and the potential role and applicability of these interventions to the management of patients with COPD. This review highlights the most common issues of the day-to-day life of patients with advanced COPD and examines the experiences of attending healthcare services, including specialist and generalist palliative care.

People with COPD live with compromised mental health, decreased QOL, limited social life and unmet needs. Overall, evidence indicates the need to achieve an agreement on the most appropriate time to initiate palliative care in order to reduce patients' unmet healthcare needs. This review was not able to establish the most suitable model of care for patients with advanced COPD. Each of the presented models in this review reported disadvantages and advantages, therefore no conclusive statement can be reached, and there is no one standard model of care for patients with advanced COPD. Supportive care is essential for lessening the psychosocial burden of patients with advanced COPD. Previous studies suggested that specialist palliative care could be the optimal supportive model of care. However, this review revealed that there may be other ways of incorporating supportive care into daily care, which should be the major focus in order to improve patients' QOL.

People with advanced COPD have comparatively low access to palliative care services, and the reasons behind this may be linked both to patients and healthcare professionals. Patients' lack of knowledge about the diagnosis and about the availability of services may

influence their reluctance to communicate with healthcare professionals about their problems. Not all healthcare professionals, though, have sufficient knowledge about this chronic disease, which can discourage patients from confiding in them. Changes in approaches and practice upheld by education and training are required to tailor individual care, concentrating on the needs of patients and their families. Broader policies for symptom management are desired, such as support and facilitation for patients, so they can live their lives more actively instead of merely existing until the end of their lives.

Previous studies failed to consider the diversity of services or provide a more general outlook on people with COPD. The majority of studies which explored the mood and experiences of people with COPD recruited them through generalist palliative care services, and only two recruited subjects from specialist palliative care. None of the studies identified strong evidence about people with advanced COPD attending diverse palliative care services. Additionally, there is no reliable data on specialist palliative care for COPD patients or breathlessness clinics designed only for the COPD population. Hence, this study is timely, original and it contributes to the existing body of knowledge by exploring the psychological and social aspects of living with advanced COPD of patients from different levels of care: a generalist palliative care service from a breathlessness clinic and a specialist one from hospices, in order to obtain a broader outlook on this population.

Studies included in this review were conducted in several countries with different healthcare policies and services available, and therefore, they may not be entirely comparable. The evidence in this review is variable, with most of the empirical research using qualitative methodologies, cross-sectional surveys, retrospective analyses, and 12

RCTs in the field. Some qualitative study sample sizes were notably small, with transferability and generalisability bias evident. There seems to be an apparent lack of studies, especially of mixed methods design; therefore, employing this approach would address a methodological gap in this area and would aim to present more information concerning this group of patients.

2.5. Aims and Research Questions of the Thesis

This mixed methods PhD study focused on the psychosocial aspects of living with advanced COPD while attending palliative care services. This study aims to inform how to manage the healthcare system in order to overcome patients' anxiety by identifying a range of factors which patients find helpful. Such management has the potential to improve their experiences of attending healthcare services and living in the advanced stages of COPD.

This principal objective of the study was to examine factors which affect the QOL and to explore narratives of the participants describing what affected their experiences while attending palliative care services. The aim of merging the results from both strands was to have a more thorough understanding of the psychosocial aspects of living with advanced COPD as well as to explain the role of palliative care in the context of COPD and to explore management factors affecting patients' experience and satisfaction.

This mixed methods study is guided by the following research questions:

Primary research question posed in the study:

- What affects the quality of life of people living with advanced COPD?

This research question examined how people with advanced COPD portray their experiences and psychological distress when attending palliative care services. This was addressed in the methodological triangulation, which combined the findings from quantitative results with the qualitative ones in a narrative where similarities, differences, and contradictions were demonstrated.

Secondary research questions employed separately in the quantitative and qualitative components of this research:

- What are the experiences of people living with advanced COPD who attend palliative care services?

This question was addressed in the qualitative arm of the study and aimed to explore the experiences of people with advanced COPD, a change in their lifestyle, receiving treatment and living beyond their diagnosis.

- What are the factors influencing the experiences of people with advanced COPD who attend palliative care setting?

This question from qualitative arm focused on exploring what people with COPD perceived as a positive or negative experience of receiving palliative care.

- What are the psychological and social needs of people living with advanced COPD, and how are these met?

This question aimed to investigate, in the qualitative arm, the psychological and social needs which were or were not met when attending palliative care services.

- What are the factors which correlate with the quality of life and psychological distress of people living with advanced COPD?

The last question sought to determine, in the quantitative arm of the study, if generalised anxiety and depression and demographic information were correlated with the quality of life.

Chapter 3: Methods

This chapter presents the theoretical foundation for this research study, providing justification for the choices made as well as capturing the strengths and weaknesses of the approaches taken. This chapter also chronicles the development of the methods used in the design, data collection and data analysis of the research process.

3.1. Theoretical Perspectives in the Context of this Research

3.1.1. Theoretical Paradigms and Rationale for Choosing Pragmatism

There are many different kinds of research, and all emerge either from ontology, that is, different ways of knowing, beliefs about the nature of reality, or epistemology, which relates to assumptions about how we know the world, how we gain knowledge, and the relationship between the knower and the known (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017; Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Žukauskas, Vveinhardt and Andriukaitienė, 2018). The philosophical assumptions or fundamental beliefs which guide the researcher's actions and define their worldview are referred to as the "paradigm" (Lincoln and Guba, 2005). Modern research is structured and organised by several paradigms or worldviews, including positivism, interpretivism, constructivism and pragmatism.

Žukauskas, Vveinhardt and Andriukaitienė (2018) stated that positivism separates the researcher from the study participants. Typically, values and biases are controlled while objectivity is sought. A deductive method is aligned with positivism, as it is used to acquire knowledge, emphasising distinct and unambiguous concepts. The opposite of the positivist paradigm is interpretivism, in which a researcher asserts that it is challenging to comprehend the social world based on principles. Žukauskas, Vveinhardt and

Andriukaitienė (2018) showed that the idea that the researcher plays a specific part in observing the social world is the foundation of interpretivism. According to this approach, research is based on the researcher's interests. Interpretivists strive for transferability, whereas positivists search for generalisations. Therefore, positivism is pertinent to quantitative studies, while interpretivism is to qualitative ones.

The constructivism paradigm, from qualitative designs, in some taxonomies of paradigms is termed the "interpretative paradigm" (Fazlıoğulları, 2012). Robson (2011) argues that in constructivism individuals seek to understand the world in which they live and, as a result, develop subjective meanings of their experiences. They also claim that social actors hold a crucial part in constructing meaning. In constructivism, knowledge involves conceptual structures bounded by relative agreements which are realist, experiment-based, local and specific.

Pragmatism is a contemporary worldview that aims to connect the gap between the naturalistic method and wide-ranging orientation, and the scientific method and structuralist orientation (Creswell, 2012; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017; Creswell and Creswell, 2018). When looking for what is meaningful in both positivism and constructivism, pragmatism bridges the gap and establishes a connection between them (Shannon-Baker, 2015). Additionally, interpretivism and pragmatism emphasise the importance of understanding. An interpretive perspective strives for understanding, which is valued for being interesting, while a pragmatic approach seeks useful knowledge, which is appreciated for its practical application (Goldkuhl, 2012).

This study embraced pragmatism as the optimal paradigm for mixed methods research. Pragmatism draws on multiple ideas, including “what works”, using different approaches and appraising subjective and objective knowledge (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). When adopting a pragmatic lens, the world is not seen as an absolute unity; therefore, collecting and analysing data from different approaches rather than from one approach alone is preferable (Murphy, Murphy and Rorty, 1990; Morgan, 2007). Additionally, Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010) argued for pragmatism, claiming that qualitative and quantitative approaches could be used in one study to manage the merging of two designs into one more comprehensive understanding. Taking a pragmatist view means that the problems studied and the questions asked about them are more important than the method or philosophical worldview that guides the approach. Accordingly, the research questions direct the choice of methodology, instruments and data analysis.

3.1.2. Rationale for a Mixed Methods Design

A mixed methods design was chosen due to the need to examine what people reported in the QOL and the psychological distress with their lived experiences. A mixed methods design was employed, using questionnaires and interviews, allowing for the exploration of patients’ experiences and enhancing comprehension of their feelings, discernments and activities (Morse, 2016). The chosen approach allowed linking the themes regarding COPD patients’ experiences in palliative care with personal characteristics and measures of QOL, anxiety and depression. The reason for collecting both types of data was to converge, diverge, compare, and corroborate the results of the two forms of data to bring a greater understanding of the experience of living with advanced COPD. Obtaining data

from two validated questionnaires aimed to examine objective rates of QOL and psychological burden, while the principal focus of conducting interviews was to contextualise outcomes from questionnaires by providing a deep insight into patients' lived experience. Hence, the interviews allowed to understand what experiencing advanced COPD meant to them. The mixed methods approach corroborated the results by linking the themes regarding COPD patients' palliative care experiences with personal characteristics and QOL, anxiety and depression.

This study employed a mixed methods design so that the advantages of one approach compensated for the disadvantages of the other. A quantitative method allowed objectivity and provided an opportunity for generalisation and precision (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Creswell, 2015). Applying only quantitative methods would not allow for adequately investigating the personal stories of patients with COPD or deeply probing into perspectives of individuals (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Creswell, 2015). In the quantitative approach, the interviewer was in the background, so personal bias and interpretation were not a concern. As it constitutes a weakness of the qualitative method, creating bias by a researcher was considered unsatisfactory due to personal interpretations, while quantitative research did not show such weakness (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). Therefore, qualitative methods were applied to answer other research questions in order to explore the in-depth experience of individual perspectives (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Creswell, 2015). In addition, it allowed the researcher to inquire about patients' experiences, enhancing comprehension of their feelings and activities (Holloway, 2005).

The research underpinning this thesis involved individuals with advanced COPD, placing importance on understanding the impact of living with COPD and on the effect of receiving palliative care on their lives. Quantitative measures would not answer most of the research questions for these purposes. The qualitative items yielded noteworthy quotes, which were employed to enrich the quantitative findings. Therefore, insights obtained went beyond separate quantitative results; by combining the results, new knowledge could be gained as an equivalent of equation $1+1=3$ (Fetters and Freshwater, 2015).

Considering one of the most recent definitions of mixed methods study proposed by Creswell and Plano Clark (2017), qualitative and quantitative data were collected and strictly analysed to receive feedback about research questions and hypotheses, and then integrate the two types of data and their results in the analysis. The researcher was responsible for designing the stages of the study, framing the procedures within theory and philosophy; considering mixed methods as “multiple ways of seeing and hearing”, thus giving opportunities for this research study to obtain thorough and corroborated findings of patients with advanced COPD attending palliative care services. The principal focus of the qualitative arm was to help contextualise the outcomes from the quantitative findings by giving insight into the lived experience of those with advanced COPD.

3.1.3. Concurrent Embedded Design

A concurrent embedded (or nested) mixed methods one-phase design was used in this study with a parallel variant. Embedding refers to an approach in which the secondary arm is blended within a primary arm, involving a collection of different but complementary data on the same phenomena, and it is usually connected with other methodologies (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Plano Clark *et al.*, 2013). Two parallel strands were

gathered and analysed independently and separately, and were only joined during the interpretation (Edmonds and Kennedy, 2013). This study is referred to as one-phased because data were collected and analysed individually but not simultaneously. Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) argued that a concurrent design is appropriate for collecting each type of data in one phase, reporting participants' voices, and providing statistical analysis to measure feelings and behaviour. This study was designed as a quantitative, cross-sectional study with two questionnaires and correlation analysis, embedded within a primary qualitative research design, which was a descriptive study with semi-structured interviews.

Given that the COPD trajectory is progressive, with functional deteriorations alternating with periods of improvement (Uronis, Currow and Abernethy, 2006), the concurrent embedded design was selected, meaning that questionnaires and interviews were collected in one phase, aiming to capture the current state of a patient. Collecting data at different periods could have presented confusing results, given that patients with COPD may present different symptoms and have different experiences depending on the period.

A concurrent embedded design limitation recognised in the literature is the possibility of focusing on different concepts in each study arm (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). On that account, both designs were linked with the same research question and focused on the same concepts, as presented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Study design

3.1.3.1. Quantitative Design

The cross-sectional study design was chosen for this study, where data exposure and condition (i.e., COPD) are evaluated simultaneously at a given time for each participant selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria (Haslam and McGarty, 2014; Setia, 2016). The advantage of a cross-sectional design study in a COPD population is that data is collected once, so participants are less likely to quit the study before the data is fully collected (Wang and Cheng, 2020). This is crucial considering the nature of COPD, with unexpected exacerbations and worsening periods. Nevertheless, this design has weaknesses, such as not determining causal relationships (Savitz and Wellenius, 2022). Still, considering the research questions posed, it was appropriate for this study.

3.1.3.2. Qualitative Design

The qualitative strand of the study employed a descriptive approach which is often used in mixed methods studies in healthcare and nursing research descriptive in nature (Doyle *et al.*, 2020). Patients' narratives aimed to provide a comprehensive and precise description of lived experience, following closely and describing the experiences of people with advanced COPD; therefore, it did not involve developing a deeply theoretical context. For this reason, a qualitative descriptive approach was adopted, and other qualitative designs, such as grounded theory, phenomenological and ethnographical research, were not chosen. Their final product results from researchers' in-depth interpretations, reflections and transformation of data; they may present a theory, a description of the meaning or essence of lived experience, and a thorough narrative description of a particular culture (Streubert and Carpenter, 2011). However, this was not sought in this research.

This study aimed to provide a detailed description of the experiences and perceptions of people living with advanced COPD. The qualitative descriptive design allowed to recognise the subjective nature of the investigated problem and the diverse difficulties of the participants, with results presented in order to reflect on the posed research questions (Bradshaw, Atkinson and Doody, 2017). Therefore, the qualitative descriptive approach was appropriate in this study, considering the fact that it focused on the broad phenomena of how patients experienced illness and attending healthcare interventions.

3.1.4. Priority of the Approaches in this Research

When choosing this design, attention was paid to whether one part of the study had priority or greater emphasis. Plano Clark and Ivankova (2015) described unequal priority of designs, where the primary method has higher priority, and the secondary is associated with inferior weight. The priority in this study was unequal, employing higher priority of qualitative strand and lesser priority of quantitative arm, which means that the latter was a secondary supplementary method in service to the primary method. It is also described as QUAL(quant) upon presentation of the notation system for mixed methods procedural diagrams (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). The weighting was chosen based on a theoretical drive of a pragmatic worldview (Heppner *et al.*, 2015). The primary focus and efforts of this research design related to the qualitative portion of this study; thus, the qualitative foci were prioritised. The quantitative data were collected and analysed to further explain and complement the findings from the interviews. Additionally, Greene (2007) explained that nesting one approach into another requires the nested method to follow the key parameters of the primary method, such as sampling. Hence, having a

qualitative design of primary priority, the study sample for questionnaires included the same individuals as the interviews and therefore was expected to be small.

3.2. Methodological Process

3.2.1. Ethical and Research & Development Approvals

Independent requests were applied to the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee and subsequently to Integrated Research Application System (IRAS). Approval was obtained from the Faculty of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Sub-Committee at the University of the West of Scotland, Hamilton (Appendix 1) and the London Stanmore NHS Ethics Committee (Appendix 2). Research Passport was granted from NHS in order that the investigator could involve in research activities on NHS premises (Appendix 3). The study was also granted permissions from the Research & Development (R&D) Department of NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde, NHS Lanarkshire and NHS Forth Valley (Appendices 4-6). The study was guided by the key ethical principles of respect for persons' autonomy, non-maleficence, informed consent, confidentiality, data protection, honesty and integrity. The adoption of these ethical principles is further presented in the next sections.

3.2.2. Sampling

Purposeful sampling was selected in this project to focus on a specific population. Individuals and localities for the study were determined in order to explore the experiences of people living with advanced COPD and attending palliative care services (Patton, 2015; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). Criteria were employed in the form of sampling chosen, which means that all selected participants needed to meet the

predetermined criteria for quality assurance (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). Purposeful sampling was also selected in order to narrow the sample to a precise group of patients and to avoid potential bias. This approach may bring limitations, such as errors in the recruitment process. Multiple individuals were involved in patient selection, which could have led to a potential bias and delays in recruitment. Therefore, it is challenging to evaluate the reliability of authority in purposive sampling.

3.2.3. Sample Size

The sample size was equal for both qualitative and quantitative arms of the study, that is, 22 participants. The sample size was decided according to Creswell (2015) recommendations of 5-25 participants for qualitative studies with interviews. The secondary embedded method was designed to match the methodological requirements of the qualitative design. In this way, the sample for collecting questionnaires was purposeful and small since it was restricted only to individuals who participated in the interviews. Participants were recruited until the discussed issues were fully understood (Hennink, Kaiser and Marconi, 2017) and data saturation was obtained, which is when repetition of responses occurred, along with inductive thematic saturation, which is when in the analysis no new codes or themes emerged (Saunders *et al.*, 2018).

3.2.4. Data Collection

The study was conducted in person. A demographic questionnaire and two validated questionnaires were administered and the interviews were conducted subsequently. To ensure the correctness of questionnaire completion, participants completed two questionnaires in the presence of a researcher. Some participants preferred to complete

the questionnaires themselves, and afterwards it was double-checked whether all items were answered.

3.2.4.1. Demographic Questionnaire

The demographic questionnaires were collected in order to have a better understanding of the sample, and the items were specifically selected to answer research questions. With the help of the researcher participants completed the self-report questionnaire, in which they were asked for information such as age, gender, smoking status, marital status, level of education, working status, family support, additional therapies and current medications (Appendix 7).

3.2.4.2. Validated Questionnaires

Two validated questionnaires were administered to the participants to receive information about QOL scores, depression and anxiety. Validated questionnaires aid in collecting data of higher quality and comparability, thus reducing effort and increasing data credibility (Tsang, Royse and Terkawi, 2017). The primary outcome measure was QOL, measured with The McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire-Revised (MQOL-R), scored in line with the manual. The secondary outcome measures were depression and anxiety level results from HADS, scored according to the authors' instructions (Zigmond and Snaith, 1983).

3.2.4.2.1. The McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire-Revised

The McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire (MQOL) was explicitly developed to measure the QOL of people with a life-threatening illness. Its brevity and generalisability characterise MQOL. The original MQOL contains 16 items measuring five subscales: psychological,

existential, support, physical symptoms and physical well-being (Appendix 8). Work to improve MQOL proceeded throughout the years, and a revised version (MQOL-Revised) was developed (Cohen *et al.*, 2017). The changes included rewording, replacing, adding new items, removing redundant ones, and replacing subscales. Also, the social scale, thanks to rewording, focused more on relationships, while the physical scale added items on reduced physical function.

MQOL-R contains 14 items measuring four domains: physical, psychological, existential and social, capturing preceding 48-hour period (Cohen *et al.*, 2017). The tool starts with a single item assessing overall subjective QOL. The MQOL-R total score is the mean of the four subscale scores. Each subscale score is the mean of the items founding that subscale. All MQOL-R items range from '0' to '10', with '0' indicating the worst situation and '10' the best situation. Questions 1, 3-7, and 10 have a reverse score. The MQOL-R scale indicates that the lower the score, the lower the reported QOL.

Instead of focusing on the severity of symptoms, this questionnaire centres on how the physical condition affects one's QOL. Most of the other end-of-life QOL assessment tools do not contain an existential or a spiritual domain, focusing primarily on physical symptoms, and include numerous additional items. There are other questionnaires in the field; however, due to their focus on COPD symptoms, design for cancer patients, lengthy characteristics, lack of psychometric evaluation and too broad scope, they were not chosen for this study (Cella *et al.*, 1993; Hearn and Higginson, 1999; Webster, Cella and Yost, 2003; Groenvold *et al.*, 2006; Meguro *et al.*, 2007; Jones *et al.*, 2009; Lyons *et al.*, 2009).

A further advantage of the MQOL-R is that it can be completed in either an online or self-administered format in between 5 and 10 minutes. It is an essential factor in this research, considering the advanced stage of COPD of the participants and common disease-related factors such as breathing problems, additional emotional distress and difficulty focusing.

The acceptability, internal consistency, reliability, and validity of the MQOL and MQOL-R have been assessed in patients receiving palliative care (Cohen *et al.*, 1995; Cohen *et al.*, 1997; Cohen *et al.*, 2017). Cohen *et al.* (2017) indicated that MQOL-R has good internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's alpha) for the overall scale ($\alpha = 0.94$) and acceptable ($\alpha > 0.7$) for the majority of subscales (Psychological $\alpha = 0.85$, Existential $\alpha = 0.78$, and Social $\alpha = 0.87$). The Physical subscale, on the other hand, is slightly less reliable ($\alpha = 0.66$). To construct the validity of the MQOL-R, the structure and relationship to global QOL (measured using a single item) were examined. The Physical domain, measured as latent factor, has the strongest correlation with the global QOL ($r = 0.65$), which correlated with other subscales: at 0.43 for the Psychological one, 0.52 for the Existential one, and 0.29 for the Social one, and the overall MQOL-R second-order factor gave a correlation of 0.67.

MQOL-R has not been used yet in the COPD population. What supported the choice of this instrument was the rapid growth of palliative care, the lack of appropriate instruments to evaluate QOL, and the focus of this study being on the advanced stage population and not strictly on the COPD one. Permission was sought to use the questionnaire and approval was granted by the author (Appendix 9).

3.2.4.2.2. Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), developed in 1983 by Zigmond and Snaith, is a self-assessment 14-item questionnaire which measures depression and anxiety in non-psychiatric groups. HADS has two 7-item subscales assessing depression and anxiety in the preceding week (Appendix 10). Each HAD-D (depression) and HAD-A (anxiety) has a score from a total of 0 to 21, which can be tallied to give a total anxiety-depression (HADS total) score with a maximum of 42 points. HADS lower number indicates lower psychological distress. Items are placed on a 4-point Likert scale, with zero denoting not present to 3 representing severe symptoms. Zigmond and Snaith (1983) have recognised three cut-off levels: a score between 8 and 10 indicating a mild case, 11–14 a moderate case, and 15 or above a severe case. Recommended cut-off values are composed of both HAD-D and HAD-A subscales. However, in the COPD population the following cut-off scores were used in the studies: >4 for HAD-A, >5 for HADS-D, and >9 to >15 for HADS-total (Cheung *et al.*, 2012; Bratås, Grønning and Forbord, 2014; Nowak *et al.*, 2014; Phan *et al.*, 2016; Baker *et al.*, 2018). HADS is validated explicitly in the COPD population. Studies in the past examined the criterion validity of HADS and reported a wide range of specificity (71%-85%) and sensitivity (63%-79%) values of the HAD-A (Cheung *et al.*, 2012; Nowak *et al.*, 2014; Phan *et al.*, 2016; Baker *et al.*, 2018). For HAD-D, values reported were 62.6%-81% for specificity and 61%-78% for sensitivity (Nowak *et al.*, 2014; Phan *et al.*, 2016), and for HADS-total, 55.2% for specificity and 75.9% for sensitivity (Nowak *et al.*, 2014). Internal consistency was reported as good $\alpha = 0.94$ (Bratås, Grønning and Forbord, 2014). However, for people with COPD, the methodological quality and level of evidence for criterion validity and other

measurement properties have not been critically evaluated yet (Larsen, Bendstrup and Neergaard, 2021).

Recent systematic reviews discussed instruments which are used for evaluating anxiety in depression in the COPD population; nevertheless, not all have been validated in the COPD population or have cut-off valued defined, they have more items, and therefore, are time-consuming (Bock *et al.*, 2017; Larsen, Bendstrup and Neergaard, 2021). HADS was validated for COPD and is easy and fast to complete, taking 2 to 5 minutes. The ethics principles of this study aimed to minimise any risk of further fatigue or distress, as patients who participated in this study were expected to be very ill, with a high level of breathlessness, comorbidities and psychological distress; thus, the short time completing the questionnaire was a factor of choosing this instrument. HADS has acceptable internal consistency regardless of gender, and it was recommended in the literature to assess psychological distress among a general population of 65 to 80 years old (Djukanovic, Carlsson and Årestedt, 2017). HADS was chosen as the instrument to measure psychological distress considering all the abovementioned facts, including the validity of the questionnaire, its versatile use in the COPD population, its easy and fast way to complete it and the focus of this study on psychological distress. Permission was sought to use the questionnaire and approval was granted by the publisher (Appendix 11).

3.2.4.3. Interviews

All interviews were audio-recorded following consent from the participants, enabling the researcher to concentrate on the conversation (Creswell, 2012; Morris, 2015). The recording device used was an Olympus VN-732PC 4GB digital voice recorder model. Semi-structured interviews with an interview guide using open-ended questions were

conducted (Robson, 2011). The rationale behind choosing this instrument was that other forms would not help answer the research questions. For example, an unstructured interview might have provided more abundant information and this would have presented challenges when comparing the two sets of data in mixed methods (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). Also, the semi-structured interviews are more informal compared to structural interviews, which, by asking only precise questions, could have led to a lack of details of individuals' experiences and ergo they may not have met the aims of the study (Wildemuth, 2016). Therefore, semi-structural interviews were conducted, based on the need to hear what participants had to say about topics and areas recognised by the inquirer (DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019).

The interviews were scheduled ahead. The transition from the questionnaires to the interview was usually fluent, with an extended discussion over the topics touched on during questionnaire completion. It appeared that having completed the questionnaires prepared the participants for the upcoming interview and made them consider aspects of their lives they had never, or rarely, explored before, thus allowing them to have a deeper conversation about their mood and needs.

3.2.4.3.1. Designing the Interview Schedule

The direction of the interviews was not dictated, although the study aims guided it. To provide a natural flow of the interview, it began with a narrative approach, asking the interviewee to talk about the story of their disease. Then an interview schedule was used to capture data on key areas of interest (Appendix 12). The interview commenced with general items to break the ice and create a comfortable atmosphere and then moved on to more emotional and in-depth themes (Whiting, 2008; Baumbusch, 2010; Rabionet,

2011).The interview schedule had a rundown of key points with leading questions to concentrate on, yet it enabled the participant to raise issues that were not envisioned. Even though they had been ordered in a sequence, questions were asked according to the progression of the interview. Sometimes, when appropriate, unplanned questions were asked to the interviewee based on their responses. Adams (2015) supports this adopted method and concurs that the researcher in the semi-structured interviews should be guided by the individual telling their story. The questions should be organised in a way that can be reordered, allowing the researcher to return later to pick up the skipped ones.

The interview guide incorporated key aspects, concentrating on the individuals' general story of COPD and the experience of everyday living with this disease in order to make them feel comfortable and present the study areas in a relaxed manner. Other areas centred on social life and relationships, psychological needs, experience and satisfaction from healthcare service, general needs of the patients and additional suggestions of the participants.

The repetitious and adaptable structure of the interviews implied that analysis started after several first interviews (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Seidman, 2006). This impacted the guide inquiries as key topics and additional questions arose. The interview guide was assessed and adjusted according to supervisory team's opinion in September 2018, after the ninth interview, with suggestions to incorporate more open questions. Moreover, after analysing the first interviews, together with field notes, it was agreed with supervisors to audio-record the questionnaire component as well. It was noticed that during the completion of demographics and the validated questionnaires, conversations

and the narrative started, and some participants mentioned valuable information that could have been omitted in the field notes due to its abundance. Hence, from the ninth meeting, the decision was taken to ask participants to consent to allow recording from the moment they started completing the demographic questionnaires, HADS and MQOL-R.

3.2.5. Study Location

The study was carried out in the West of Scotland in three NHS board areas: Greater Glasgow and Clyde, Lanarkshire and Forth Valley. Participants were recruited through a respiratory clinic and three hospices by an appointed person from the medical team from June 2019 until November 2019. Two other hospices also agreed to participate in this study but did not have any eligible patient.

3.2.6. Recruitment screening

Potential participants were screened by an appointed person from the medical team, for the following inclusion and exclusion criteria prior to being approached for voluntary participation in the study (Table 3.1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria).

Table 3.1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification of airflow limitation severity in COPD: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Moderate II GOLD (50% ≤ FEV1 < 80% pred.), ○ Severe III GOLD (30% ≤ FEV1 < 50% pred.), ○ Very severe IV GOLD (FEV1 < 30% predicted). • Speaking English. • Attended a respiratory clinic or a hospice as an out-patient and/or in-patient at least 2 times. Patients with moderate II GOLD were recruited if attended the service for several years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diagnosed psychiatric or cognitive disorders other than depression, anxiety and panic attacks. • Diagnosed progressive neurological or neuromuscular disorders. • Active cancer. • Another uncontrolled or unstable disease. • Any other respiratory disease, such as interstitial lung disease, cystic fibrosis, lung cancer or active tuberculosis.

The Breathe Easy clinic offered a disease-specific support group. Their meetings took place on a monthly basis and were attended by people with COPD and run with the support of a local respiratory team. A day hospice was attended by patients with a wide range of malignant and non-malignant diseases for a 12-week programme supported by clinical nurse specialists. Both services offered information and advice on different aspects of a patient’s disease, including symptom management control and educational sessions involving looking after themselves and planning for the future and a chance to meet others in a similar situation. Moreover, they offered emotional support and complementary therapies run by expert volunteers, specialist programmes for people with

breathing difficulties, and activities including gardening, gentle exercise and crafts. Patients could make an appointment for a manual massage, and hospice goers could make beauty treatments, including hairdressing and manicures. Also, participants were recruited from weekly pulmonary therapy sessions offered by the hospice.

In the generalist service (a Breathe Easy clinic) the respiratory consultants identified potential participants and informed them about the study. If patients expressed the willingness to participate, they had an opportunity to discuss further details with the researcher, who was in the clinic on the same day. The potential participants received from the researcher a Participant Information Sheet (Appendix 13), as well as brief oral information about the study, and they could ask questions in case of any doubt. The Participant Information Sheet advised them on the study design and its aims. It also informed that there would be no direct financial benefit to the participants. The Participant Information Sheet explained that the study was conducted by a PhD student from the University of the West of Scotland. Subsequently, if patients initially showed interest in participation, phone numbers were collected with their permission to be contacted by the researcher in the following days to check whether they wanted to proceed or not.

In the specialist services (day hospices), eligible participants were initially identified by the care team. They were approached directly by an appointed medical team member and received a Participant Information Sheet. Later, the appointed member contacted the researcher, providing the phone numbers of the potential participants. All patients approached by the specialist and generalist palliative care services were reassured that no change of care would occur, whether they participated or not.

All potential participants were telephoned by the researcher a minimum of 24 hours after being introduced to the study by an appointed person from the medical team in order to give them sufficient time to consider whether they wanted to participate. The maximum time from the initial approach by the clinical team to the scheduled interview and questionnaire was around three weeks, depending on the participants availability.

After agreeing to take part, the patients were met in the place and time chosen by them (either at their home, hospital or hospice premises) to ensure the most comfortable and appropriate place and time for the patients. For the interviews conducted in a clinical setting, the clinical team identified a suitable room which ensured the privacy needed for the meeting. This was to guarantee the ideal environment regarding their condition in order to limit any possible distress. Throughout the interview and questionnaires, the participants could choose to be accompanied by a carer, relative or friend. This happened twice in this study, when spouses accompanied male participants, adding some additional information and supporting their partner when they hesitated.

The sensitivity of the topic discussed, which is living with advanced disease, was handled by being mindful of the problems addressed. Discussing the experiences was challenging at times, especially when some individuals had little understanding of their prognosis. When it occurred, it was ensured that these situations were approached with sensitivity. The researcher debriefed the supervisory team when required. When the meeting took place at a healthcare service, the healthcare personnel was debriefed and informed by the researcher if the participants became distressed psychologically or physically during the meeting. In case of feeling distressed or doubtful about their diagnosis during or after

the interview process, participants received advice to report concerns to their healthcare team or contact an external organisation, such as the British Lung Foundation.

Finally, participants were expected to have only one visit for both questionnaire and the interview. However, two patients after completing questionnaires asked to have another meeting for the interviews, after one week for one patient and two for the other. This was because of the participants' other planned activities and a lack of time for an in-depth interview after completing the questionnaires.

3.2.7. Personal Safety of the Researcher

Ahead of scheduling a meeting with the participants, a safety risk assessment was undertaken while visiting them at their homes or healthcare services (Robson, 2011; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017), and a lone working procedure and flowchart were produced (Appendix 14), which were approved by Health and Safety Services (Appendix 15). Before meeting with a participant and right after leaving their home, a supervisor or an appointed substitution when supervisors were unavailable was contacted and informed via text message about arriving at the appointed address and safely leaving the premises. If a meeting was in a healthcare service, the abovementioned were informed via e-mail at the end of the working hours of that day.

3.2.8. Consenting the Participants

Completed informed consent forms were received from all the participants before the data collection (Appendix 16). The informed consent was provided to the patients to ensure their voluntary participation in the study, educating them about the aims of the study, its activities and participants' rights (Shah *et al.*, 2022). Each participant was informed about

the right to withdraw from the study at any time. The participation of the individual could be discontinued from the study at any time, if considered necessary for any reason, including ineligibility (either arising during the research or retrospectively having been overlooked at screening), significant protocol deviation, significant non-compliance with study requirements or withdrawal of consent. None of the aforementioned issues appeared in this study. All data were collected and retained following the General Data Protection Regulation (Information Commissioner's Office, 2018).

3.2.9. Debriefing of the Participants

At the end of all meetings, all participants received a Participant Debrief Sheet (Appendix 17) and a Privacy Notice that informed about data protection (Appendix 18). The participants' GPs received letters informing about their patients' participation in the study (Appendix 19).

3.2.10. Data Storage

After the interview the recordings were immediately transferred onto an encrypted laptop on Microsoft OneDrive and deleted from the digital recorder. Consequently, scores from questionnaires were also input to OneDrive on an encrypted computer, which was accessible only to the interviewer. Subsequently, the interviews were transcribed verbatim. Finally, a master copy with data is kept on a university hosting file system, Microsoft OneDrive.

Participant characteristics, questionnaires and any identifiable data are stored separately from anonymised versions of the data. They are both stored separately in locked filing cabinets within locked offices at the University of the West of Scotland. Contact details for each participant were kept in an encrypted university server until the study was

completed. Identifiable patient details will be kept for one year post study completion and then destroyed according to the data protection legislation (Information Commissioner's Office, 2018). This will ensure a clear audit trail for the study and subsequent publications. All personal and medical data were handled as confidential. Information was anonymised to a feasible extent and as early in the process of the study as possible. Once potential participants signed a written consent form, they were allocated a random participant number used for all future data. Transcripts of interviews with participants only contained a name synonym; no individually identifiable data were recorded on the transcripts.

3.3. Data Analysis

3.3.1. Quantitative Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical analyses were used to assess the spread and distribution of the data to determine the types of tests that can be conducted (Edmonds and Kennedy, 2013; Armstrong and Kraemer, 2016). The data are presented as frequency, count and percentage of the variables contained in the demographic and validated questionnaires. The results of the analysis were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) calculated in SPSS software version 25.0.0.0. A regression analysis was originally planned; however, this was not performed due to the small sample size achieved. A series of correlations were run to determine whether there were any significant relationships between the QOL scores (dependent variable) and other variables, such as demographic information and psychological distress (independent variables) (Field, 2018). A two-tailed p-value of less than 0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance. Values between 0.05 and 0.1 were seen as a trend. It was hypothesised that there would be a

significant relationship between QOL and anxiety and depression among COPD participants.

3.3.2. Framework Analysis

All 22 interviews were analysed using Framework Analysis. This approach was adopted to help the researcher to undertake a systematic and rigorous approach to the analysis of the qualitative data. The Framework Analysis is characterised by its defining highlight, the matrix output: lines (cases), segments (codes) and cells of summed up data, giving a construction wherein data to examine by case and code can be efficiently diminished (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013). The Framework Analysis was created in the UK (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013) and it is now commonly used in areas of health research (Engel *et al.*, 2021; Mulla, Orton and Kendrick, 2021; Ozkaynak *et al.*, 2021), and also in studies of COPD population (Linde *et al.*, 2018; Nightingale *et al.*, 2020; Fu *et al.*, 2021). Gale *et al.* (2013) stated that the Framework Analysis is appropriate for analysing interviews in mixed methods health research. It has easy-to-follow steps; therefore, it is justified for use with novice researchers. The Framework Analysis belongs to a large group of analysis techniques which are frequently referred to as qualitative content analysis or thematic analysis. Smith and Firth (2011) have criticised thematic analysis for fragmenting the original data, increasing the likelihood of data misinterpretations, and lacking clear guidelines; therefore, there can be a lack of transparency, and findings can be subjective. Gale *et al.* (2013) highlights the strengths of the Framework Analysis, which produces a systematic model for managing and mapping the data and offers transparency. Researchers can concentrate more efficiently on participant observations thanks to the detailed outline. Charting the data into the matrix allows the researcher to consider a specific participant

(row) while still considering how themes emerge across interviews (columns). In contrast, other qualitative analysis techniques can cause overlooking the individual case as cross-interview themes are created. Therefore, this method was chosen for analysis, considering that this study, conducted in healthcare, was of mixed methods design, and the researcher had little experience in qualitative data analysis.

Data analysis was conducted with NVivo 12 software, designed for multimedia data in order to assist in rich text analysis progress with hierarchical coding aid (Grbich, 2013). The process of analysis included seven stages outlined below in Figure 3.2. Framework analysis.

Figure 3.2: Framework analysis

Following the procedure of analysis presented by Gale *et al.* (2013), the interviews were transcribed verbatim in the first step. The next stage was familiarisation with the

transcripts, recordings and any additional reflective notes. During this step, the researcher immersed themselves further in the data by relistening to the audio-recordings and rereading the transcripts and fieldnotes.

After the familiarisation stage, the transcripts were read row by row in NVivo12, labels and codes were applied in passages throughout every transcript. The primary coding was an open process wherein everything was labelled. Guaranteeing the significance of keeping the encompassed information was crucial (Bryman, 2016). Coding was carried out carefully, not merely from a couple of key models (Braun and Clarke, 2013). In this study, it was applied by distancing from the aims of the study to ensure capturing the participants' experiences which were enclosed in themes in the results chapter (Table 4.8.). The notes on the emerging themes from the first few interviews served as a summary. After consulting with supervisors, who read these first interviews, a coding strategy was developed, and it covered the topic guide and new emerging themes. In NVivo, the transcripts were coded into themes using the coding strategy. The interviews delivered plenty of data, which was divided into more user-friendly sections, which could be analysed by coding into general themes. The NVivo software allows for additional analysis, but framework templates have not yet been developed for each code at this stage. The coding strategy is included in Appendix 20.

The following step, per Gale *et al.* (2013), was developing a working analytical framework, which involved initial indexing and systematic application of codes to the whole data set as well as to distinctly determined categories. Codes which emerged until the coding of the last interview were enclosed in the framework. The coding strategy included eight categories, each with numerous subcategories.

Subsequently, the working analytical framework was applied by indexing transcripts, using the existing categories and codes. Each code was assigned an abbreviation to facilitate its identification and then added to the transcripts in NVivo 12.

The next step involved charting the data in a matrix in the form of spreadsheets using an Excel document which, in turn, was updated regularly. Data were beforehand outlined by identifying categories from every transcript. Proper charting required a capacity to find a balance between condensing the data but still holding the original expressions and voice of participants. Thus, the chart incorporated descriptive quotations and captured references.

The final step was interpreting, which involved seeking correlations and mapping the codes. Manual tables were created to physically examine the associations among the concepts and typologies evolved from them as well as relationships between the concepts. Finally, the analysis produced short summaries of the participants' biographies, which presented their experiences (Appendix 21).

3.3.3. Triangulation of Data

Methodological triangulation was employed in this study (Denzin, 2010; Bekhet and Zauszniewski, 2012). Separating data and their analysis was carried out with triangulation that searched for positive findings from two strands (Greene, Caracelli and Graham, 1989). In this way, triangulation gave more opportunities for a more integrative way to make conclusions from data (Andrew and Halcomb, 2009). Also, by applying triangulation, it was attempted to reduce the "deficiencies and biases that stem from any

single method” (Mitchell, 1986) (p. 19) and constitute “the potential for counterbalancing the flaws or the weaknesses of one method with the strengths of another” (p. 21).

In the integration of data, the results from the statistical analysis were compared with the interview findings and brought together. Following the approach outlined by Creswell and Creswell (2018), the integration was conducted using “a side-by-side comparison” and was presented in a narrative, opposing data from both arms, where similarities and differences were demonstrated. In this approach, the comparison was made within a discussion, presenting the first set of findings and then the other. In this manner, the analysis started by discussing quantitative statistical results and by comparing them with the qualitative findings.

Chapter 4: Results

This chapter presents the overall results of the study with concurrent mixed methods design. Firstly, the characteristics of the participants are presented. Then, it outlines the descriptive statistics of the sample characteristics. Subsequently, quantitative results from the analysis of the questionnaires are offered. Next, the findings from the interviews are presented, based on the Framework Analysis approach. Finally, it provides triangulation, presenting how data from two different methodologies converge.

4.1. Recruitment Pool

Of the twenty-two subjects who agreed to participate in this study, sixteen were from the generalist palliative care service. In total, twenty-six patients with advanced COPD in the Breathe Easy clinic, who fit the inclusion and exclusion criteria, were approached. Five patients declined to participate because of unspecified reasons. One person refused due to previous participation in a different study and showed no interest in being a part of the study. Another one could not be reached on the phone number provided. Three other patients were interested in this study but were undergoing infection or wanted to be contacted later. However, it was impossible to reach two of them by phone later, and one patient died shortly after being approached after the initial phone call.

One hospice recognised four eligible patients from the pool of specialist palliative care services, out of whom only one participated. One patient could not be reached by phone and did not attend the hospice any longer. Another one died before being approached, and one was between hospital admissions; therefore, the hospice team did not approach them. The second participating hospice found two eligible patients who participated in this

study. The third participating hospice identified five patients who matched the criteria, and three participated in the study. Two other hospices agreed to participate; however, they did not find any patient in their database who would respond to the criteria. Figure 4.1. presents the pathway of patients' recruitment.

Figure 4.1: Flowchart of the recruitment pool

4.2. Characteristics of the Participants

Table 4.1. presents relevant demographic information about all 22 participants and the lung function characteristics of 20 participants. The table offers sections dividing the whole group on the basis of gender and service attended.

Thirteen (n=13, 59.1%) participants attended a generalist palliative care service, and six (n=6, 27.3%) were recruited from a specialist palliative care service. Three participants (n=3, 13.6%) attended generalist palliative care at the time of recruitment and had previously accessed day hospice care.

Twelve (n=12, 54.5%) participants in this study were female, and ten (n=10, 45.5%) were male. Eleven (n=11, 50%) participants were married, five (n=5, 22.7%) divorced or separated, four (n=4, 18.2%) widowed, and two (n=2, 9.1%) were single. Fourteen participants (n=14, 63.6%) had attained a general secondary level of education, and five had a vocational one (n=5, 22.7%). Two (n=2, 9.1%) participants graduated from higher education. One participant (n=1, 4.5%) did not recall their educational level. Eighteen participants were retired (n=18, 81.8%), three were unemployed (n=3, 13.6%), and one was employed (n=1, 4.5%). Eighteen participants were ex-smokers (n=18, 81.8%), three still smoked tobacco (n=3, 13.6%), and one was an ex-smoker and continued being in the company of smokers, experiencing second-hand smoke (n=1, 4.5%).

Table 4.1: Characteristics of the participants

Outcome measures	All participants (n=22)	Males (n=10)	Females (n=12)	Generalist palliative care (n=16)	Specialist palliative care (n=6)
Service (generalist/specialist)	16/6	9/1	7/5	-	-
Gender (male/female)	10/12	-	-	9/7	1/5
Age (mean, years)	67.23 ± 8.67	70.30 ± 2.74	64.67 ± 2.23	66.69 ± 1.54	68.67 ± 5.71
Smoking status (ex-smoker/smoker)	19/3	8/2	11/1	13/3	6/0
Educational level					
Secondary	14	6	8	9	5
Vocational	5	4	1	5	0
Higher	2	0	2	1	1
Did not recall	1	0	1	1	0
Marital status					
Married/partnership	11	5	6	8	3
Divorced/separated	5	1	4	5	0
Widowed	4	3	1	2	2
Single	2	2	1	2	1
Antidepressants (yes/no)	13/9	4/6	9/3	9/7	4/2
Therapies attended					
Group pulmonary rehabilitation	16	8	8	13	3
Individual pulmonary rehabilitation	8	6	2	7	1
Self-management programme	8	7	1	8	0
Relaxation therapy	8	3	5	5	3
Self-help group	6	3	3	5	1
Counselling	3	3	0	3	0
Massage	3	2	1	2	1
No therapies	3	1	2	1	2

Type of carers					
Children	14	6	8	12	2
Spouses	10	5	5	7	3
Grandchildren	8	4	4	8	0
Friends	7	2	5	7	0
Parents	1	0	1	0	1
Other family members	2	1	1	2	0
No carer	1	1	0	0	1
Oxygen therapy (yes/no)	12/10	5/5	7/5	7/9	5/1
FEV 1% predicted (n=20)*	36.92 ± 13.79	35.89 ± 4.41	37.75 ± 4.46	36.25 ± 3.81	39.58 ± 2.52
GOLD stage (n=20)*					
Mild	3	1	2	3	0
Severe	10	4	6	6	4
Very severe	7	4	3	7	0

*- missing data

Twenty-one participants (n=21, 95.5%) received informal caring support from family members or friends (Figure 4.2.). The most common carers were children (n=14, 63.6%) and spouses (n=10, 45.5%), followed by grandchildren (n=8, 36.4%) and friends (n=7, 31.8%). Other family members such as cousins (n=2, 9.1%) or parents (n=1, 4.5%) were also reported as carers. One participant (n=1, 4.5%) did not have any carer involvement. Whilst not uncommon or a significant finding, this may mean that the support clinic and hospice services cannot see the true nature of the daily needs of those living with COPD, as informal caregivers cover these needs.

Figure 4.2: Informal carer support source

More than half of the participants were currently on antidepressant medication (n=13, 59.1%), most of whom were female (n=9, 40.9%). Also, the majority of participants (n=12, 54.5%) were oxygen-dependent, including seven females (n=7, 31.8%) and five males (n=5, 22.7%). In the demographic questionnaire each participant could select the therapies they had attended or received. Most common was group pulmonary rehabilitation with sixteen participants (n=16, 72.7%), followed by individual pulmonary

rehabilitation, self-management groups and relaxation, each of which was participated in by eight individuals (n=8, 36.4%). Six participants frequented self-help groups (n=6, 27.3%), while counselling and massage were provided to three participants (n=3, 13.6%). Finally, three individuals (n=3, 13.6%) did not receive any of the abovementioned therapies or other additional treatment (Figure 4.3). Appendix 22 presents more detailed characteristics of each participant.

Figure 4.3: Additional therapies attended.

4.3. Descriptive Statistics of the Participants

Descriptive statistics were used to characterise the sample. The first step in the data analysis process was to outline the data and carry out statistical tests based on the results of the test of normality, in which the shape of dispersion and measures of central tendency to the shape of a normal curve were compared (Field, 2018). In order to verify it, the

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were conducted. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is more generic and regarded as less powerful. Field (2018) recommended the Shapiro-Wilk test for samples under $n=2000$ and referred to it as the explicit test for normality. In addition to carrying out the test of normality, data were also graphically analysed for the goodness of fit. Both of the aforementioned tests determine skewness and kurtosis (Kim, 2013). Nolan and Heinzen (2011) advised skewness to measure symmetry and kurtosis to measure the peak of distribution or pointiness. A skew value of zero indicates a normal or symmetric distribution. Whereas positive skew implies that the tail on the right is longer than the left and the values are situated to the left of the mean, analogically, a negative skew denotes the tail is on the left and values lie on the right of the mean. In turn, testing in SPSS software specifies kurtosis as excess kurtosis, and a score of zero indicates a normal distribution. Both kurtosis and skewness with a score above or below zero are described as a deviation from the norm, implying that the sample distribution is not shaped like a normal curve (Field, 2018). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests for normality were not significant for age and FEV1% pred., and were normally distributed (Table 4.2). Field (2018) advises that it is important to characterise the data by presenting the measures of variability, including the spread and range of data, showing any outliers as well as the standard deviation and distance between the highest and lowest points.

Table 4.2: Test of normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Shapiro-Wilk	
	Statistic	P	Statistic	P
Age	.145	.200	.963	.560
FEV1% pred.	.153	.200	.901	.044

Age is normally distributed, as shown in Figure 4.4. and Figure 4.5. They present the distribution of data for age against the shape of a normal curve.

Figure 4.4: Age range

Figure 4.5: Age range scatter plot

Figure 4.6. displays that the mean age of participants was 67.23 ± 8.67 , ranging from 45 to 85. Table 4.1. adds that the mean age of males in this study is notably higher than

females, 70.30 ± 2.74 compared to 64.67 ± 2.23 . Participants from the generalist palliative service were younger (66.69 ± 1.54) than those from the specialist ones (68.67 ± 5.71). The data also revealed one outlier, a 45-year female participant with severe COPD (FEV1% pred. 34%).

Figure 4.6: Age point chart

A test of normality was computed separately for the clinical measurement FEV1% pred. due to missing data of two ($n=2$, 9.1%) participants attending a hospice. Data were normally distributed. The results show that the mean FEV1 pred. of 20 participants was $36.92\% \pm 13.79\%$, as presented in Figure 4.7 and Table 4.1. It also highlights that the lowest score was 20, and the highest was 72. The mean FEV1 pred. of males was $35.89\% \pm 4.41\%$ and $37.75\% \pm 4.46\%$ of females. One outlier, a woman, 70 years old with FEV1 pred. of 72%, attended the clinic for several years after lung cancer and more than 20 years of COPD diagnosis. The results for both males and females demonstrate that their COPD is classified as severe. The hospice group ($n=4$, 18.2%) presented slightly less

severe FEV1% pred. $39.6\% \pm 2.5\%$ compared to a respiratory clinic participant (n=16, 72.7%) with $36.25\% \pm 3.81\%$.

Figure 4.7: FEV1% pred. total point chart

When completing the MQOL-R questionnaire, participants chose answers on a scale from 0 to 10, with a higher number noting a higher QOL score. The results from the MQOL-R questionnaire are presented in Figure 4.8. It explains that the items from a social subscale received the highest score with “Feeling supported” followed by “Easiness of communication with the people one cares about”. The participants responded the lowest to two items from the physical subscale, “Problem-free of inability of doing things due to physical symptoms” and “Problem-free of physical symptom”, with succeeding “Not fearing the future” from the psychological subscale.

Figure 4.8: MQOL-R questionnaire responses.

MQOL-R mean score was 5.84 ± 2.17 , while the lowest score was 1.71 and the highest 8.88 (Table 4.3). Table 4.3. illustrates that patients had the highest scores in the social subscale (7.74 ± 2.39), followed by the existential (5.93 ± 2.59) and the psychological dimension (5.48 ± 3.04). The lowest scores were noticed in physical aspects (4.30 ± 2.28). The results demonstrate that this sample was most affected by physical aspects and least by social factors. The self-assessed QOL was 4.95 ± 3.04 . Table 4.3. presents results of

MQOL-R total score and its subscales for the whole sample and then divided by gender and service attended.

Table 4.3: Results from MQOL-R

	MQOL-R	Physical subscale	Psychological subscale	Existential subscale	Social subscale
All participants (n=22)	5.84 ± 2.17	4.30 ± 2.28	5.48 ± 3.04	5.93 ± 2.59	7.74 ± 2.39
Females (n=12)	5.72 ± 1.89	3.75 ± 2.09	5.33 ± 3.02	5.72 ± 2.06	8.08 ± 2.30
Males (n=10)	5.99 ± 2.56	4.93 ± 2.46	5.55 ± 3.23	6.17 ± 3.22	7.33 ± 2.56
Hospice (n=6)	4.65 ± 2.71	2.61 ± 2.25	4.04 ± 3.21	5.04 ± 3.26	6.94 ± 3.53
Hospice males (n=1)	1.7 ± 0	1 ± 0	1.75 ± 0	1.75 ± 0	2.33 ± 0
Hospice females (n=5)	5.25 ± 2.57	2.90 ± 2.36	4.5 ± 3.36	5.7 ± 3.17	7.87 ± 3.03
Respiratory clinic (n=16)	6.29 ± 1.83	4.91 ± 2.00	5.95 ± 2.89	6.26 ± 2.33	8.04 ± 1.88
Respiratory clinic males (n=9)	6.47 ± 2.20	5.33 ± 2.17	5.97 ± 3.12	6.67 ± 2.99	7.89 ± 2.20
Respiratory clinic females (n=7)	6.07 ± 1.36	4.44 ± 1.78	6.07 ± 2.82	5.75 ± 10.31	8.24 ± 1.36

Females scored lower than males in QOL measured with MQOL-R. Participants from the respiratory clinic presented higher QOL than those attending solely hospice service. As presented in Table 4.3, respiratory clinic males had higher QOL than females, compared to a hospice, where females scored higher than males. However, it is essential to note that the hospice group was represented by only one male, an outlier and had the lowest QOL results of all the participants; therefore, the results are not representative and are not proportionally distributed. Males scored higher than females in all subscales except the social subscale. When comparing the hospice and respiratory clinic groups, the latter presented higher scores in all subscales of MQOL-R.

Males in a respiratory clinic presented higher scores than females from the same service in a physical subscale. This was confirmed in the results of females in hospice. Males in a respiratory clinic also scored higher in an existential subscale than females in a respiratory clinic with and in hospice. Interestingly, females in a respiratory clinic scored higher in a social subscale, followed by males in the same service and females in a hospice.

These results reveal that participants in a respiratory clinic presented better results than those from hospice, except females in a social subscale of MQOL-R. Males generally scored higher than females on a physical, psychological and existential scale. On the other hand, females in the respiratory clinic scored higher when looking at a social subscale.

When completing the HADS questionnaire, participants chose answers on a scale from 0 to 3, where a higher score denotes higher depression or anxiety. The results from the HADS scale are presented in Figure 4.9. and Figure 4.10. They confirm that two questions on all HADS questionnaires received the highest score with “I feel as if I am slowed down” first, followed by “I still enjoy the things I used to enjoy”, both from the depression scale. Moreover, the two highest responses on the anxiety scale were “I feel tense or ‘wound up” and “I feel restless as if I have to be on the move”. Still, the participants responded the lowest on all HADS scale to three from the depression scale: “I can enjoy a good book or radio or television programme”, “I can laugh and see the funny side of things”, with succeeding “I feel cheerful”.

Figure 4.9: Anxiety scale of HADS

Figure 4.10: Depression scale of HADS

The mean results from the HADS questionnaire were 18.95 ± 7.88 (the lowest being 5 and the highest 34). HAD-A score mean was 10.14 ± 4.79 , with a range of 16 from 2 to 18, and HAD-D mean was 8.81 ± 4.29 , with a range of 29 from 5 to 34. Table 4.4. presents the results of HADS and its subscales as a whole sample, divided by gender and service attended.

Table 4.4: Descriptive statistics of HADS results

	HADS	HAD-D	HAD-A
All participants (n=22)	18.95 ± 7.88	8.81 ± 4.29	10.14 ± 4.79
Females (n=12)	18.9 ± 7.54	8.5 ± 4.12	10.4 ± 4.50
Males (n=10)	19 ± 8.67	9.2 ± 4.68	9.8 ± 5.35
Hospice (n=6)	21.5 ± 9.9	9.7 ± 5.78	11.8 ± 5.49
Hospice males (n=1)	34 ± 0	17 ± 0	17 ± 0
Hospice females (n=5)	19 ± 8.80	8.2 ± 5.07	10.8 ± 5.45
Respiratory clinic (n=16)	18 ± 7.08	8.5 ± 3.77	9.5 ± 4.53
Respiratory clinic males (n=9)	17.3 ± 7.31	8.3 ± 4.03	9 ± 5.00
Respiratory clinic females (n=7)	18.8 ± 7.24	8.7 ± 3.72	10.1 ± 4.14

Females had slightly lower anxiety and depression than males (Table 4.4.). When comparing the hospice group with the respiratory clinic group, the former presented higher HADS scores in both subscales. In a respiratory clinic group, females had higher anxiety and depression scores than males. Females in a hospice group scored higher in anxiety and depression than males and females in the respiratory clinic. In the hospice group, only one male was recruited, who scored the lowest of all participants in this study on both scores' dimensions, anxiety and depression, as well as in QOL; therefore, he is

an outlier. These results may imply that the hospice group experiences a higher psychological burden than the respiratory clinic group.

The results of this study could be yielded by the symptom profile and burden of the patients, and the aim was not to evaluate the difference between service attended and gender on QOL and psychological distress and data were collected and analysed to present a complete picture of the recruited sample. Nonetheless, the current study was limited by a small number of participants, which may have affected these results.

4.4. Correlation Analysis of Quality of Life and Mood

Tests for normality were conducted for mood and QOL variables. The tests confirmed that HADS-total score (Appendices 23-26) and MQOL-R total score (Appendices 27-30) were normally distributed and therefore, it was justified to employ them in correlation. Correlation tests were conducted to examine if there was a significant relationship between QOL and anxiety and depression among COPD participants. Kendall tau correlation was computed with demographic data, including type of service, gender, age, severity measured with FEV1% pred. and GOLD classification, oxygen use, and with scores of HADS, its subscales as well as with the total score and subscales of MQOL-R (Table 4.5.). The findings indicate that the type of service attended at the time of the study, gender, age and oxygen use were not correlated with QOL. There was a trend of severity, measured with FEV1% pred. and GOLD classification, of p-value 0.69 and 0.62, respectively. MQOL-R total score was significantly correlated with the HADS total score ($r = -.560$, $p\text{-value} = .000$), with its subscales HAD-D ($r = -.689$, $p\text{-value} = .000$) and HAD-A ($r = -.325$, $p\text{-value} = .040$). HADS total score will be used further for examination.

Table 4.5: Correlation of type of service, gender, age, disease severity, oxygen use, HADS with MQOL-R total score.

	Kendall's tau correlation coefficient	P-value
Type of service	.283	.121
Gender	.114	.531
Age	.026	.865
FEV1% pred.	-.298	.069
GOLD classification	.344	.062
Oxygen use	-.157	.391
Anxiety (HAD-A)	-.325	.040
Depression (HAD-D)	-.689	.000
Anxiety and depression (HADS total)	-.560	.000

Correlation relationships of HADS total and type of service, gender, age, oxygen use, and severity, measured with FEV1% pred. and GOLD classification, revealed that no significant relationship existed between the type of service attended, gender, age, or severity classified with GOLD stages (Table 4.6.). The results, however, showed that severity measured with FEV1% pred. was significantly related to HADS total ($r = .346$, p -value = .037). The findings demonstrate that as severity increased so did HADS total; however, it is a weak association. GOLD classification had a negative association, meaning a more advanced stage was related to a higher HADS total score.

Table 4.6: Correlation of type of service, gender, age, disease severity, oxygen use with HADS total score.

	Kendall's tau correlation coefficient	P-value
Type of service	-.198	.284
Gender	-.030	.869
Age	-.062	.691
FEV1% pred.	.346	.037
GOLD classification	-.336	.072
Oxygen use	-.152	.409

It is not a surprising outcome, but it indicates other underpinning factors affecting QOL and psychological distress. The small sample size and purposive sampling could affect

these outcomes. After the analysis of participants' experiences is presented, it will be examined whether other aspects, besides the reported anxiety and depression related to the severity of the disease, emerge as factors affecting the experiences of living with advanced COPD and QOL.

4.5. Results from Framework Analysis

This section of the chapter reports the findings from the qualitative component of this mixed methods study. 22 interviews were conducted and their duration ranged from 25 to 105 minutes, with an average time of 42 minutes. The following table 4.7. presents the final themes and subthemes, which will be further discussed and presented in this chapter.

Table 4.7: Themes and subthemes

Theme	Subthemes
Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiencing physical symptoms • Experiencing anxiety, panic attacks and depression • Interrelationship of physical and mental experiences • Changes in lifestyle • Coping strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Accepting the disease ○ Looking for purpose ○ Trying to maintain a normal lifestyle
Loss of identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loss of social life • Loss of social roles • The importance of social connections • Loss of independence
Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The experience of healthcare <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Empathic attitude of healthcare professionals ○ Opportunities for having social connections ○ Missing aspects of healthcare • Support from informal caregivers

4.5.1. Adjustment

The first presented theme is adjustment, which includes experiencing physical symptoms, anxiety, panic attacks and depression and their interrelationship, as well as changes in lifestyle and coping strategies, involving accepting the disease, looking for purpose, and trying to maintain a normal lifestyle.

Living with COPD had a significant impact on the lives of the participants in the study and led to a change in their lifestyle. Physical symptoms substantially contributed to the increase in their life limitations. Individual attitudes towards their compromised life depended on participants' understanding of the diagnosis and, consequently, their coping strategies. All participants experienced symptoms of dyspnoea daily, and its intensity varied from day to day. Shortness of breath reduced the individuals' mobility and considerably prevented them from doing what they were previously able to do. Usually, it started when participants tried to get up and started walking, when walking uphill or upstairs. For instance, James AC14 experienced breathlessness daily and constantly:

The shortness of breath is the biggest thing, the constant shortness of breath, it used to be for a certain length of time, now it's as soon as I get up and start walking.

James AC14

The experience of dyspnoea was described as gasping for breath, catching last breath, suffocating, drowning or a frightening event. This was expressed by Alexander AC21 as:

It's as if you're drowning, and you're just waiting on somebody to grab you and pull you out of the water. That is the feeling that you've got. That it's your last breath. Scary.

Alexander AC21

All participants experienced other physical symptoms relevant to everyday life, which were coughing and tiredness. Pain in joints was bothersome to eight participants, especially in the back and hips. Two individuals experienced pain from other sources connected with their comorbid diseases, adding extra burden to their mobility. Sleeping problems for six participants were caused by difficulties in lying down comfortably enough to fall asleep and by increasing cough or anxiety. Loss of appetite afflicted four participants, and this was related to taking morphine. Moreover, urinary incontinence was a problem raised by five participants, and it was attributed to increased coughing, which considerably reduced the participants QOL, as they became more housebound. Other comorbidities negatively affecting the lives of two other individuals were tremor and cough syncope.

Living with COPD often entailed polypharmacy, and various medications had a diverse effect on the patients. Namely, they brought beneficial effects as well as substantial side effects. On the one hand, oxygen therapy provided relief in symptoms and breathing facilitation. James AC14 explained:

I think the oxygen's helped more than the inhalers and the drugs. I can do more. (...) With the oxygen on, then I'm fine. I'm out of breath, but I'm not anywhere near.

James AC14

On the other hand, oxygen therapy was mostly connected with limited mobility, reduced social contact, "becoming a shut-in" and an embarrassment. Oxygen bottles were described as heavy to carry, making it impossible for the participants to leave home alone.

Many participants pointed to the mind-body connection of experiencing physical symptoms and psychological distress. Anxiety, as well as panic attacks, were common for all participants. Dyspnoea tended to appear abruptly, inducing anxiety or panic attacks. Cynthia AC3 described experiencing panic attacks when not being in control of her breathing. Keith AC12 and his wife described an association between problems with breathing and panic attacks:

The only symptom is my breathing. It's climbing up the stairs. If I get too excited I, I panic, and that will result in... heavy breathing.

And I think with his breathing now, I think sometimes when his breathing's bad, he panics, 'cause he maybe thinks something else is gonna happen to him, too.

Keith AC12 and his wife

April AC15 explained that she experienced panic when she could not breathe:

It's when you can't breathe right you just panic. And it then it interrupts your breathing pattern. It's... if you... you're not breathing the way you should be breathing, it's horrible and I know myself, when I'm like that, I've got no control over my bladder.

April AC15

April AC15 recounted that this feeling was repellent and she did know how to deal with it. Her problem with bladder incontinence was related to problems with breathing, and she showed her regrets for smoking and for being responsible for the health consequences that smoking caused:

For some strange reason, I don't know what, the doctor doesn't know what it is, and I haven't got a urine infection or anything, but it's just when my breathing's erratic, for some reason I wee. It's horrible. So I've got to watch what I'm doing when I'm going anywhere, you know, to make sure I go to the toilet and... even that, even doing that, I can still feel it. You know, if it's, if my breathing's no' right, and I'm quite sure I'll no' be the only one. (...) Unbelievable. You never thought

years ago when you started smoking all this would happen, but there you go. My own fault. Can't blame anyone for it.

April AC15

Similarly, Alastair AC9 mentioned that anxiety worsened his breathlessness, and it was challenging to cope with it and to be able to control it:

Well, sometimes you just go into your shell, you know you're not wanting to talk, 'cause if you're anxious, that's one of the worst things you can do if you're having COPD and once you get anxious that's when you're breathless and properly bring on the attack.

Alastair AC9

Likewise, Graham AC20 learnt to cope with anxiety by calming himself down utilising self-management strategies provided by his occupational therapist:

The only way I know is to really get rid of that anxiety because it can become quite frightening. Try to sit down and talk to yourself. That you knew what's happening. You know why it's happening. And to try and would be like a kind of self-meditation where you're the only person that can do that.

Graham AC20

All participants experienced a sense of loss, as they could not continue undertaking previous social and everyday activities and needed to change their lifestyle because of COPD. Colin AC2 spoke of the impact of his physical symptoms of COPD, resulting in him no longer being able to care for himself at home and being admitted to a care home. He describes his life now as being limited to the walls of his room, which has led to him feeling frustrated and angry.

Inability to breathe normally forced individuals to become housebound and dependent on others, and they needed to plan whenever they wanted to leave the house. Being

housebound was universal; they had a more sedentary lifestyle, limited to their house or a room. Participants gave up activities such as gardening, travelling, going for a stroll, shopping, and cleaning their homes. Giving up their job was common due to suffering physical symptoms and being immobile. In turn, being physically unable to be as active as in the past was related to increased frustration, anxiety or depression. In fact, frustration was universal and was mentioned by almost all participants. It was commonly caused by being unable to carry out previous activities and now needing to plan everything. For instance, Ellen AC6, Davis AC7, and Keith AC12 could not take care of themselves any longer or do simple activities as in the past, which led to frustration. Ellen AC6 reported that not being able to do anything frustrated and upset her. She struggled every day with the disease, but it made her more aggravated than depressed:

It's a frustration the disease! Not being able to do anything! And that what I find so frustrating, so upsetting. It's a fact, but you just can't do the things I used to do. You need to plan everything. (...) but I'm not depressed. That's the disease – that's what is. And you just have to live with that.

Ellen AC6

Everyday chores took much longer to do than usual, which destroyed having a regular daily pattern. Also, Alastair AC9 noticed that his mood and patience was different after the onset of COPD. Namely, it made him angry and frustrated with considerably less patience:

You get frustrated when you cannot do it. When you feel as if you need to get a bath, you've got to, you cannot just say right I'm going to have a bath. You say, right, will I manage it...all they wee stupid thing you take for granted or you should take for granted.

Alastair AC9

The need for planning was another required adjustment when living with COPD. For example, leaving home was related to asking someone for help, usually relatives, and arriving at the destination earlier to rest if they felt tired. Also, going from place A to B required planning in case there were stairs on the way or the place was uphill. Being dependent on others and forced to adjust to physical limitations meant activity planning was necessary and this could induce anxiety and frustration. Alexander AC21 needed to prepare, plan and leave in advance in order to avoid anxiety when leaving the house. He usually got anxious about everything connected with going out, such as not being late, feeling tired, using stairs, or going to the toilet. He explained his normal process when going out:

I've got to be early.

...and hour or two before we go out, to get organised, he gets anxious about going somewhere. We could get to the bottom of the stairs, and he's got to come back up again.

For the... for the toilet. Aye.

For the bathroom and things like that. He gets anxious just going anywhere that you and I wouldn't think anything different. He does get anxious.

I've got to be early. I've got to be early for everything. Everything.

Alexander AC21 and his wife

The incurable nature of the disease could yield a feeling of hopelessness. Loss of hope for improvement in their lives was common and contributed to the feeling of having no purpose in life. Some participants did not believe that anything could ameliorate their life and mood. For instance, James AC14, Susan AC8 and Graham AC20 said it was impossible to improve their mood because it was directly connected with the disease.

Additionally, Beth AC16 was forlorn and did not believe that anyone or anything could help her, and she saw no use in going on because she was unable to get involved in any activity in her life. Also, Ellen AC6 was hopeless about her future and saw no purpose in her life because she was not happy with it any longer as she explained:

I'm great believer it's not the quantity of your life; it's the quality of your life. And if you don't have quality of life, you don't have anything.

Ellen AC6

When living with COPD, most participants developed coping strategies allowing them to participate in limited activities and experience adjustment to the new life. Acceptance was the most common way of coping with the disease. Participants usually accepted the diagnosis, the progressive disease with no cure, and adjusted to the limitations. In fact, understanding the symptoms of the disease and its nature was the first step to acceptance. Usually, participants were satisfied with the knowledge provided by healthcare professionals, which helped them to feel cared for.

Education was provided either directly by a leading doctor, nurses, or educational sessions via self-management programmes, pulmonary rehabilitation sessions, educational sessions and leaflets as well as self-help groups. Knowing what to expect in the disease progression allowed the participants to acknowledge what would happen to them and minimalised psychological distress. As in the case of Susan AC8, who was aware of the diagnosis and felt that her understanding and knowledge about the disease was satisfying and helped her accept the disease. She commented on her knowledge of the disease:

I know what caused it. I know that I'm not gonna get any better, and it's just gonna be a deterioration over the months or years, whatever how long it takes, I understand all that. I understand what's gonna happen at the end, and I'm quite aware of it.

Susan AC8

Frances AC4, who had never had problems with anxiety and depression before having COPD, started developing them after her COPD diagnosis and the associated hospital admissions. Recognising the limitations of living with oxygen therapy helped Frances AC4 with her anxieties and depression. After accepting her disease, she was "out of the dark". Conversely, not understanding the diagnosis contributed to increased psychological burden and frustration. Colin AC2 was the only participant still struggling with accepting the diagnosis. With minimal understanding of the disease, he hardly understood what had caused it:

I don't know what's causing that. I don't know when it started. I don't know, because I had always fresh and open air. And every deep breathing exercises... And this is a really, really a big shock. Asthma and that, and this whatever, you know. I don't know where this is come from. I don't know.

Colin AC2

Those participants who accepted the diagnosis, coming to terms with the fact that the symptoms would not improve and their life would be limited, took the day and life as it was. Also, attending support groups, a day hospice and being surrounded by people in a similar situation was supportive and aided them in their journey of acceptance.

Additionally, some participants tried to avoid overthinking and dwelling on their disease because there was no good in it so they fought their anxieties. Others tried to make the

most of their situation, as did James AC14, who approached his anxiety with an acceptance that helped him not to ponder on his life:

I'm not down, as such. I've relegated myself to feeling this way, because there's no point in being happy or sad about it, you can just.. it's... this is your life, do you know, this is the way things are gonna be. It's not gonna get any better.

James AC14

Also, Mike AC22 tried not to fret about the future and not give in. He believed that he was in control of his mood, able to manage possible anxiety and commented:

It's all now down to a state of mind, how you feel. You're gonna have your downs and you're gonna have your ups. And it's just a question of overcoming them. By saying, you've got no control over it, so just get on with it.

Mike AC22

Accepting the situation helped to adjust to new life situations and find new hobbies such as plant potting, gardening, pottery or yoga. For example, Jane AC1 mostly stayed at home, read a book or did pottery. Although she missed going out, she accepted her situation. Likewise, Mark AC5 adjusted his lifestyle by moving to a house with a garden so that he could spend a more pleasant time indoors and outdoors. April AC15 tried to make the most of what she had, adjusting to the restrictions by using walking aids, a wheelchair or a mobility scooter in order to have some parts of her old life and activities.

Another technique noted was maintaining a normal lifestyle and adopting an attitude of living day by day. For the majority, trying to maintain a normal lifestyle and following the day-by-day strategy was the most crucial in order to cope. The unpredictability of the disease was a problem for many as it required planning, and it sometimes led to

frustration, when it was impossible to adhere to the plan. Some days seemed better, and some were worse, so it was not easy to predict what the next day would look like. Therefore, due to this unpredictability in terms of experiencing symptoms and mood fluctuation resulting from them, the one day at a time approach seemed to be the best and the most effective and helpful to some of them. For instance, Frances AC4 described having good and bad days. When having a tough day, she mostly stayed in bed, but she also had good days, which she appreciated. She described her days:

A difficult day is when you live in bed. You basically can get up, but you're so breathless. And it's a struggle. (...) I got to used to believe that to say lately: "today it's a good day", but I started again to fear that. So now when a good day is coming I grab it with my both hands and enjoy them.

Frances AC4

COPD was related to all participants' lack of independence, which affected their lifestyle, making it more restricted. Hence, holding onto the activities they still were able to perform, for many, was a way to maintain some degree of normality. Engaging in these activities was essential in order to stay mentally acute and not depressed. Some still tried to go for walks or visit shopping malls with necessary planning in advance, attempting to maintain their previous lifestyle and social life within their capabilities. Only one working participant in this study, James AC14, decided to go back to work because being there made him more mentally alert. Before his COPD diagnosis and after, he worked in an office, in a hospital. His social life diminished compared to before having COPD, and his life mainly revolved around his work; and his everyday encounters with his co-workers helped him preserve his mental acuteness. James explained his experiences:

I was a year off because of it when I was diagnosed with the COPD. And the doctor signed me off for a year. I detested it. I wanted to get back after three months. I hate not working. It's just the way I am, the way I was brought up. I need something to mentally keep me alert. Work does that for me.

James AC14

Taking care of himself helped Davis AC7 to lessen the burden of living with COPD. He commented:

I mean, the likes of me... as I say, the good bits of my body I look after as best I can, make sure they're working well. And that helps to keep the pressure off.

Davis AC7

Also, Alexander AC21 upheld some of his old social activities, such as meetings in the church, where he still had many friends. Similarly, Abigail AC13, the only participant who still regularly attended outside activities, continued some of her hobbies, went out, met her friends in restaurants, went to a golf club with her partner. When talking about it, she was excited and happy that she did not have to stay at home all the time. Yet, getting out of the house to the restaurant needed to be well-organised. She explained:

I like to know about the place that I'm going, because it's always in the back of my mind that there might be a situation where I'm gonna... if it's a lot of stairs, it's gonna be too much for me.

Abigail AC13

In conclusion, experiencing physical symptoms of COPD, such as breathlessness, cough, pain, and others led to life limitations and adjustments in everyday life. The patients became housebound and dependent on informal and formal carers. The progressive and incurable nature of the disease caused in some a feeling of hopelessness, as some participants felt that nothing could be done to improve their physical and mental health.

The need for oxygen use contributed to living space limited to their homes only. Their lifestyle needed to be adjusted, activities planned according to their restricted physical capacity, the unpredictable nature of the disease, and the necessity to use and carry oxygen bottles. These limitations could, in turn, increase frustration, anxiety, panic attacks and depression. Experiencing physical symptoms such as breathlessness induced panic attacks. Everyday activities were in some way connected with anxieties, whether it was having to live with restrictions, experiencing breathlessness when walking or fearing to leave home. Furthermore, being unable to perform as they used to do before the diagnosis and letting go of their lifestyle greatly contributed to frustration and depression. However, some patients developed coping strategies in order to manage to live with this chronic condition. It was noticed that understanding the disease and acknowledging their limitations could help cope with living with the disease and ease the apparent psychological burden. Healthcare professionals usually provided education about the condition, though not always. Acceptance was the most important strategy when living with COPD, and a proper understanding of this disease facilitated it. When acceptance was reached, it could be followed by lifestyle adaptations such as trying to maintain a normal lifestyle with adjusting activities according to their physical limitations. Early education of the participants was noted as a contributing factor both to accepting the limitations caused by the condition and to better disease management. Finding new ways to enjoy their lifestyle within their limitations could be another positive consequence of acceptance. Finally, taking one day at a time was mentioned as another result of coming to terms with their restrictions. It meant choosing to focus on happy moments and not dwelling on the past and their losses due to the restricted lifestyle. It also meant

recognising their own needs and not asking too much of themselves. Therefore, education about the disease should be introduced early to help patients follow subsequent steps such as acceptance and adjustments.

4.5.2. Loss of Identity

The second recognised theme is loss of identity. It includes subthemes such as loss of social life and roles, importance of social connections and loss of independence.

COPD impacted the participants' ability to move around, be active in their own homes and engage in social and community activities. Participants described this as being housebound and unable to walk long or short distances, missing family parties and relying on relatives and friends to visit them. This led to feelings of loneliness and isolation. Cynthia AC3 recalled being an active person who used to go out every day. At the time of the interview, she could not go out anymore, which upset her and she complained:

I don't have social life. Only a time ago was going for the appointments now. I was out every single day before I got really bad. Now I don't go anywhere. Nowhere whatsoever.

Cynthia AC3

The use of oxygen also impacted the participants' ability to be active and socialise effectively. The participants acknowledged that oxygen was beneficial in terms of reducing breathlessness, but in general, it still restricted their lifestyle. For example, going out to the cinema, theatre, or restaurant became impossible. Carrying heavy oxygen bottles as well as the whole process of planning and getting to a place was reported to be tiring physically and emotionally. Lorna AC10 described previously enjoying going to the theatre but now being oxygen dependent stopped her from going out, due to the heavy

weight of the oxygen bottle and its noise. Susan AC8 also refused to go to the cinema because of oxygen and the abovementioned burden connected with it. Lorna AC10 described the process of going out as exhausting:

I've not set foot inside a theatre for years. Well number one you have to get from here to the theatre. That takes time. That's finding your seat, and sitting down and watching the play. Being there at the interval watching the second half of the play and then getting out and coming back. It's at least three and a half hours.(...) Oxygen. So how long does a bottle of oxygen last? Not that long. And also there's the weight of either as an bottles of oxygen which they know they're not light. Or you could do what I do which is a mobile oxygen concentrator which isn't silent. So it's a theatre and it makes the noise and of course that is dependent on battery life. So batteries don't last that long.

Lorna AC10

Similarly, Davis AC7 described being housebound as “stuck like in prison”, and his social contact was limited to his family and friends. He mentioned that his life pleasures were non-existent and described himself as “persona non-grata”. Additionally, because of the help he needed with the oxygen bottle, he felt dependent on others, which impacted his ability to leave home on his own. Although he learnt how to live with this disease, being unable to perform previous activities or being slow when doing them led to developing frustration and annoyance. He explained:

It's annoying that you cannot get out and do things. Very frustrating. Simple wee jobs that you used to do, you... it's an operation trying to get things done. (...) I'm very slow in getting things done. But the body just won't... It won't take it, and you've just got to sit and wait until oxygen levels catch up with you.

Davis AC7

Having to plan affected the participants' social life as every activity needed to be carefully thought through, thus making it impossible to go out spontaneously. This impacted the

person emotionally as they felt uncomfortable and worried about spoiling the occasion.

Graham AC20 reflected:

Before you go anywhere you have to plan. We're going to visit somebody's house; you find out that there is a toilet upstairs. Or to the restaurant, it's the same. If there is a toilet downstairs, upstairs, are there stairs, is it easy to get to. That kind of thing it takes away the spontaneity of going somewhere. You really think where you're going. Because you know at some point, you're going to feel breathless, and you'll feel there is not much you can do and it's gonna make you feel uncomfortable.

Graham AC20

Some participants reported losing their sense of identity associated with social roles they previously held, such as being the principal breadwinner and handyman in the case of the male participants and for some females taking care of the household. Some participants also complained of losing their role as a grandparent as they could no longer take care of their grandchildren or engage in playing with them, attend sporting events and watch them play.

For Graham AC20 and Alexander AC21 losing their family and job roles led to adverse consequences for their self-confidence. They both could not help at home with repairs, which used to be their responsibility. For Graham AC20 the development of the disease led to an inability to be self-reliant at home, which made him feel redundant. He reflected:

That's because you look at something when you think a couple of years ago and you could do that in five minutes. But you can't anymore. That's what makes you feel redundant that you need people's help to do most things that you used to do without even thinking.

Graham AC20

Alexander AC21 was forced to retire because of his COPD onset, and since his retirement he felt he was not needed anymore, he lost his purpose as the family breadwinner. Alexander AC21 also used to help other people and have friends coming over. The loss of his perceived role in the family and inability to help friends caused anxiety, which could only be controlled with anti-anxiety medications. Similarly, April AC15 and Sarah AC17 were upset about losing their social roles as housewives in household chores such as cooking and cleaning the house and subsequently felt they were burdening their husbands.

Having lost their social life, the participants reflected on the relevance of having social connections. Although participants reported that their social life was restricted, they still benefited from being a part of a community such as their family and neighbourhood. Rachel AC11 used to be a member of a voluntary gardening community group. Giving up this activity and losing her role as a group member led her to develop a feeling of great loss. She recounted:

My social life is basically visiting, seeing family. I used to do voluntary work, voluntary gardening. But I've not been able to do that since last year. And I miss doing that. But I just, I've no' been well enough to do it in the last year. I did that for about six years. I did it for a charity, but I would love to get back to that. And no, my social life is really confined to family at the minute.

Rachel AC11

The opportunity to participate in a gardening potting session during a support group meeting made her realise how she missed that and the craftwork she used to do. Rachel AC11 recalled these activities as something that would cheer her up.

I used to do quite a lot of gardening, and voluntary gardening would pick me up, and like craft work. I used to do quite a lot of craft work, that used to pick me up as well.

Rachel AC11

For Lorna AC10, who was housebound, being a part of a community as a family member gave her a sense of purpose, preventing her from feeling isolated. Daily calls from friends or family contributed to her feeling needed and involved. Also, Nancy AC18 felt cared for by her family, and she appreciated their efforts to meet with her and involve her in most of their family activities. Her family members helped her maintain her role as a grandmother and mother by taking her to family parties, visiting her every day and bringing her grandchildren to see her. However, Nancy AC18 noticed that since having COPD, she became short-tempered, and she was no longer as patient with her grandchildren as she used to be. Consequently, it upset her that she could not spend time with her family in a manner she would prefer:

And I've got ten grandkids and most weekends there's five of them here and I find now I cannot cope with them the same as I used to be able to. I find myself short tempered. I've not got the same tolerance now that I used to have. But one of them usually stays with me at the weekend. If it's only one, it's fine because there's not any bother when it's only one. It's when they all get together.

Nancy AC18

Some participants felt that social life could be substituted by meetings with other people with a similar diagnosis. Being around people with the same issues was reassuring and helped them not feel alone. Support groups in a local surgery, a respiratory clinic, as well as a day hospice or pulmonary rehabilitation, were all opportunities to meet people with COPD or other debilitating diseases. Mike AC22 attended pulmonary rehabilitation early in the diagnosis, and he stated that it did not physically help him as he discontinued

exercises afterwards. However, meeting other people with the same problems helped him psychologically to realise that he was not alone with his diagnosis, as other people were experiencing similar lifestyle limitations. Therefore, being introduced at the beginning of the diagnosis to different people with similar experiences was of paramount importance in accepting his disease, forming adjustments, and developing coping mechanisms. After attending a six-week course in a local hospital, he never felt the need to go to any COPD support group. Mike AC22 explained that it helped him to cope:

It introduced me to people who already... who had what I had and that helped. Knowing that you're not the only person who has this. 'Cause you could be sitting in this house and out there you'd never meet anybody who has the same thing. (...) That helped, that psychologically helped. I'm not the only one with this thing and there were people far worse than me.

Mike AC22

Frances AC4 (45 years old), who recently joined a pulmonary rehabilitation in a hospice, thought it was vital to her to know that she was not alone and that there are other people with this disease. Five participants from this study attended a support group in the out-patient clinic and considered it beneficial. Four of them attended the support clinic for at least a year and had regular meetings once a month. All five participants claimed that they looked forward to the support group as it substituted the social life they had lost as they could meet people with similar problems and share mutual troubles, giving the participants social connectedness. Ellen AC6 expressed:

I enjoy the lung therapy clinic that we're having. I think it's good to see other people in talk to other people or just like you.

Ellen AC6

In addition, Keith AC12 held the view that his social life was improved thanks to the support clinic, where they could normalise their experiences. He attended it monthly with his wife and both looked forward to it. They both agreed:

The support groups.

It's... it's helped.

It's helped.

understand there's other people in the exact same position as we're in. And what they're going through is the same as us. We're not just experiencing this ourself, there's other people out there experiencing the same as us.

Aye, we look forward to going to it. So we do, every month.

Keith AC12 and his wife

Five participants attended the day hospice at the moment of the interview and appraised it for its beneficial aspects. For Beth AC16 the day hospice was valuable because it enabled her not to feel alone with her disease and prevented her from experiencing fears. In the day-care, she was surrounded by people with similar problems; although the vast majority had a different diagnosis, mostly oncological, she felt it was the only place where she was understood. She enjoyed meeting other people and commented:

People think we all come in here and you sit and it's all sad and all that. Wait to you see us out there. We'll be all laughing our heads off. (...) it's the only time you get to be yourself. You could be more relaxed with people because you are all just in the same boat.

Beth AC16

In contrast, some participants felt alone because they did not know other people's experiences or did not see other people with COPD, which upset them. Susan AC8 admitted that she did not see other people with COPD. In addition, she was frightened to

go anywhere and was afraid of what other people would think of her, seeing her so sick. This indicated a fear of stigma about being sick and not fully functional. Susan AC8 noted that:

As much as the doctor will say, "There's hundreds of people like you!" I never see them. I never see them walking about with one of these things, never. And I don't know why I never see them, maybe I don't go out enough. In places I go to I don't see them. So that kinda puts me off a wee bit.

Susan AC8

Attending a support group could also bring motivational and educational benefits. Abigail AC13 and Alexander AC21 attended a local support group soon after diagnosis. These individuals only went there at the beginning and did not feel the need to go to these meetings later in the disease. The local support group assisted Alexander AC21 in coping with the disease and getting information about his condition. Another benefit of the support group was that it helped him quit smoking by educating him on the subject, as was the case for Abigail AC13. Rachel AC11 benefited from seeing other people in more advanced stages, which scared her of what may come and motivated her to quit smoking and take better care of herself.

In contrast, Cynthia AC3, Susan AC8 and Nancy AC18 were uninterested in attending the groups because they took place too far from their homes, and they did not want to inconvenience their carers. Nancy AC18 also reported that she had a well-developed support system among her children and a neighbour; therefore, she did not need to bother them to go to the meetings.

Some individuals chose not to attend support groups as they did not see any benefits. Alastair AC9 and Lorna AC10 did not like to be surrounded by people they did not know, which made them not interested in attending the support groups. Davis AC7 felt he did not need this kind of support because he had been able to manage well by himself for many years, so it was not something he looked for. Davis AC7 explained:

Some people it might help, getting the physiotherapy and joining groups and talking about it and that, but I can cope with it myself.

Davis AC7

After having lost their physical abilities, loss of independence was reported by almost all participants. The only participant who did not lose his independence was Mike AC22, who regained his self-sufficiency after a lung volume reduction surgery a year before the interview was held. The rest of the participants depended on others to go out, go shopping, visit relatives, or go for a consultation. This dependence could increase frustration, as it was in the case of Ellen AC6, who suffered the most from loss of independence. Being physically restricted and dependent on others meant she stopped feeling like herself. Before experiencing the limitations of the condition, she used to have everything under control, so losing that control frightened her. She commented that her current situation varied from the one she was used to:

I was always a person that works. And run here and run there. And that's the hard thing – I can't do that. I mean, I can't. I'm not a person... I've always been always very independent. And that's the thing frightens me most. That's lose the independence I had. That's what terrifies me.

Ellen AC6

Maintaining independence was crucial for some. For instance, being able to manage himself was, for Glen AC19 the most substantial aspect of life. His disabilities forced him to ask his carers for help, although he did not want to. For Glen AC19 and Alastair AC9, informal support was an important factor as they could not leave home without the informal carer's help with Glen AC19 explaining:

I think it's more or less just getting out and about and being able to do the things I used to be able to do without having to carry an oxygen tank on my back. Think that's the most important thing.

Glen AC19

Alastair AC9 felt in a similar way:

Just somebody to help me get out, you know, if she (carer) didn't have a car, I wouldn't get out.

Alastair AC9

Additionally, Alastair AC9 tried to be as independent as possible; however, he believed he was too much of a burden for his carer, his ex-wife, with whom he reconciled. He would like to unburden her from this dependency so that she could have her life as before. Namely, Alastair AC9 did not want her to sacrifice her life and abandon her activities in order to care for him. He suggested he could be more independent when going out with the help of social care staff. Nonetheless, he felt helpless as he believed that he would not be eligible for social workers because of his postcode, i.e., living in a deprived area of Glasgow. He also thought that people from deprived zones could be stigmatised by healthcare professionals such as GPs and thus receive healthcare of worse quality:

I've not got any social workers or that. I'll never, well not that I don't need them...because of my postcode I'm not eligible to get them probably.

Alastair AC9

Similarly, two women, April AC15 and Sarah AC17, were greatly supported by their husbands, and they felt very grateful for their help. However, they mentioned that they felt terrible about being dependent on their spouses.

To sum up, living with COPD had its consequences in social and psychological distress. Worsening health conditions resulted in the loss of social roles of the participants, who viewed themselves as useless. This contributed to increased psychological distress. Health deterioration also led to dependency on others, specifically on caregivers, causing a feeling of being a burden. Patients were worried that the caregivers sacrificed their lifestyle too much because of their condition. Also, attending activities outside their home was sometimes too much for the participant, regarding the physical burden, and some did not want to overburden themselves or their carers. Nonetheless, being a part of a community and having social connections helped the participants feel useful and needed. Support groups, such as a disease-specific support group or day-care in hospice both provided assistance on the social, educational and motivational levels. For instance, being surrounded by people in a worse state motivated some participants to take better care of themselves, exercise and quit smoking. Any form of a community, such as church meetings, brought substantial social and spiritual benefits. Participants suggested that social care staff or volunteers could help with independence by assisting them in leaving home, thus helping them to avoid being solely dependent on their caregivers.

4.5.3. Support

The support covers healthcare experience, involving an empathic attitude of healthcare professionals, opportunities for having social connections, and missing aspects of healthcare. This theme also includes support from family or other informal caregivers.

Participants received palliative care support from different professionals in secondary and primary care. From the secondary care level, specialist palliative care was provided through hospices and healthcare professionals and made a positive impression on the participants. Beth AC16 considered the hospice beneficial, as it allowed her to socialise. She felt it was a place she could relax in and enjoy the time with other people with similar problems:

It's the only time you get to be yourself. You could be more relaxed with people because you are at just in the same boat.

Beth AC16

Lorna AC10 used to attend hospice day care in the past and recalled that experience as enjoyable, relaxing and reassuring. She described the hospice staff as compassionate and very kind:

Very relaxing, very nice people. It's quite extraordinary to be within our kind of medical place that's not in such a rush. There's an incredible amount of kindness there a load of compassion which I find to be very reassuring and of course it's just very beautiful too, it's always lovely to be in a beautiful place. (...) But I think that the staff that they have there top palliative care staff so they know what they're doing. They definitely know what they're doing and the atmosphere is generated by the people who are there.

Lorna AC10

Similarly, April AC15 expressed her profound satisfaction with the service provided by the hospice. She felt that the day hospice was where she could relax and spend time only for herself. She attended relaxation and massage therapy as well as crafting activities, which she thoroughly enjoyed. Her group in day hospice had only two people on oxygen; because of hospice regulations, there were only two people with oxygen therapy,

including herself. However, she enjoyed the company of other people who faced serious diseases:

They're a nice crowd of women, we're all well, we're all basically dying, so it's... you just learn to accept it. (...) But if it's... soul destroying. Made me more... it's made me more peaceful, coming here. I love coming here. 'Cause it's a day away, and it's about me. And I can get my nails done and my hair done. Getting my feet and my legs massaged, which is just absolutely wonderful. And then I have a bit of relaxation.

April AC15

Moreover, attending hospice changed her perception of this place and she did not associate it with death anymore:

When somebody mentions 'hospice,' the first thing you think is death. And it's not like that. It's great.

April AC15

Generalist palliative care, from the secondary care level, provided by the multidisciplinary respiratory team at the Breathe Easy clinic, was assessed as valuable by almost all the participants. They especially appreciated consultants' good and timely treatment management, providing clear information and treatment choices. It was comforting for participants to know that they could have an extra, out-of-calendar consultation with respiratory consultants in the support clinic if they experienced any difficulties.

Having a reassuring and empathic leading doctor was of the utmost importance to many. Cynthia AC3 emphasised the empathy of the respiratory consultant as she felt understood by him and trusted his approach:

He is brilliant. Everybody likes him because he treats you as normal. And he does talk everything you don't understand and it's just really, really good." (...) when you see Dr, who says: "let's try this, let's try that" – great! I just go ahead and try.

Cynthia AC3

Most of the patients shared her opinion. For example, Mark AC5 and Susan AC8 felt they had an excellent rapport with their respiratory consultants and felt free to ask them any questions. They had the impression that they were fully informed about their condition, stage and possible further treatment. Susan AC8 mentioned:

I've been very fortunate that this new consultant that I've got, I go to, is really, he's bent over backwards to try and make life a wee bit more bearable for me and I appreciate that.

Susan AC8

Lorna AC10 was also grateful for being treated as an individual and felt that the doctor knew her and listened to her. She put all her trust in the consultant and valued his sincerity:

I completely trust him to have my best interest me as a person as an individual patient. I completely trust him to have my best interests. (...) he knows the progress of the disease and he knows he doesn't frighten me. He doesn't give me false hope and he's communicative.

Lorna AC10

However, Beth AC16, who attended a day hospice, was not satisfied with the usual care from a respiratory consultant, whom she met only at routine consultations once or twice a year. She attributed this to the fact that her stage was too advanced, which is why she did not see the consultant more often. Beth AC16 commented:

I don't really see him much now. See 'cause you go into this stage, you don't, you don't go to the clinics anymore. Don't really see any doctors. Not unless you're in a hospital with it.

Beth AC16

A few participants mentioned negative experiences when doctors judged them during hospital admissions. Lorna AC10 believed that some doctors judged her for smoking and having a self-inflicted disease. Also, when being admitted, Graham AC20 and Abigail AC13 felt either belittled or approached aggressively. However, they did not experience this with their GPs or respiratory consultants. Abigail AC13 told her experience during a hospital admission:

I have had the odd doctor that has treated me like a child and spoke down to me. Which I don't appreciate. Because, as I say, I am... I'm not a stupid person. I knew when I was smoking how... how bad it was for me. But we don't need to be spoke down to like a child.

Abigail AC13

Also, Graham AC20 was met with unpleasant and aggressive attitude in hospitals:

The way they do ask you when you first go in and get some of that will get very aggressive in terms... "DO YOU SMOKE?!". I mean it doesn't come out only a smoker. No smoke... "DO YOU DRINK?!".

Graham AC20

Primary care is the first level of care in which patients have their medical concerns and needs addressed. Their providers may be nurse practitioners, GPs and allied health professionals such as physical and occupational therapists. While most participants had positive views about respiratory consultants, opinions about GPs' care were mixed. Some participants expressed their preference for a specialised physician regarding managing

COPD. Some would ask for a GP as a primary care physician only when having chest infections or needing prescriptions:

My GP is not qualified really about COPD. (...) My GP writes a prescription.

Mark AC5

Being timely managed was another essential factor in improving satisfaction from the care received. Facilitations, such as contacting healthcare professionals, having a phone number of a nurse or a GP, helped those who had this opportunity. In fact, three participants found it challenging to contact a GP surgery. Alexander AC21 and his wife mentioned that it was hard to get an in-person consultation in their GP surgery and complained that his GP never saw him in person and prescribed his medications only over a phone consultation:

*The thing I don't like, is when you phone your GP, it's hard to get an appointment. But in our practice, the doctor will phone you back that day. (...)
I think he's got an infection again, and it's, I'll send up antibiotics, maybe sometimes steroids... I don't like that, because I think with somebody with COPD, like in Alexander's condition, should be getting examined...*

The... no, the doctor, aye, the doctor should have a look at you, rather than...

*I think the doctor should be, rather than just saying, "I'll send you up antibiotics..."
I don't like that bit of it.*

Alexander AC21 and his wife

Alastair AC9 expressed his dissatisfaction and believed that the GP did not care for him sufficiently. Moreover, he believed that he was discriminated due to his postcode being from a deprived area, and therefore he was not eligible for home visits, which made him feel frustrated. Alastair AC9 complained about the lack of GP or community care support and felt positive only about the support clinic:

If it wasn't for the respiratory consultant, I would be stuck because as I says to you before, I don't feel I was ever getting the support from GP. (...) You phone in a doctor or phone in an ambulance and if you had someone coming up (...). And they're saying you're wasting our time. That's the way you feel as if you're phoning them, am I wasting their time? And nine times out of ten you're not, because you kind of know yourself but if that would happen, I would go for that more support.

More support from the respiratory nurse for example? (Yes). And do you feel at the moment that you can have this care from the nurse?

No, I've not got anything. I've got nothing.

And even if you call and say "I would like a nurse to come to check up because I think something is wrong"

What, the one in my surgery? **(Yes)**. No, I won't get that.

Alastair AC9

Most participants received home visits by respiratory or community nurses after being diagnosed, and almost all knew about the availability of home visits by nurses and how and whom to ask if they needed them. The participants felt that they could trust the nurses, communicate efficiently and ask them questions regarding treatment or the disease. Individuals who had routine home visits seemed more self-confident and more satisfied with the care they received. For instance, Cynthia AC3 spoke of the importance of the nurses, who, in her opinion, helped her immensely to feel cared for, understood her needs and displayed empathy. She and Frances AC4 emphasised the importance of nurses being easily reachable. Nurses were also an enormous help to James AC14 when he needed it during his worse periods and acute episodes involving infections. They also helped him and Frances AC4 develop self-management techniques, i.e. exercises and breathing techniques which they could implement into their routine self-care at home. From Cynthia's AC3 and Abigail's AC13 perspective, it seemed easier to connect with the nurses rather than with doctors due to time-limited doctors' consultations. Cynthia AC3 reflected:

The best thing I've ever had is the support workers. The nurses are brilliant. Explained everything to you. You've got a better understanding what's actually happening there, because a GP doesn't have time to sit and explain.

Cynthia AC3

Likewise, Sarah AC17, who was happy with the care she received when attending day-care every week, praised nurses' commitment and involvement in the care:

The lassies all round about me and that, they get the nurses or day-care come out and then see that I'm fine. They say, "No, this is what we're trying to help you with," I say, "to me, that's pampering me. Which I'm not wanting. I want to be independent,".

Sarah AC17

Participants who tended to be more often admitted to hospitals reported a higher need for routine home visits from a nurse. Namely, Ellen AC6, just as Alistair AC9, noted that they lacked nurse care at home. Alastair AC9, who recently suffered from a lung infection, felt no support from the community level, including his surgery and GP, and he reported that, due to his loss of mobility, he could benefit from the help of a care nurse. Likewise, Ellen AC6 would prefer to have received home visits from a nurse with management support and administration of medications at home rather than be forced to go to a hospital. Both believed nurse visits would help them avoid developing infections and hospital admissions. Alastair AC9 explained:

Just somebody to come up every so often, because you can feel as if you chest infection isn't only a chest infection and you say to yourself, it might just be a wee... you don't feel well and all that, then you leave it for two or three days and then it becomes too late.

Alastair AC9

In fact, receiving extensive care from the community level positively affected patients' condition. At the time of the interview, Graham AC20 received comprehensive care from the community level, which he was extremely pleased with and which unburdened him in various aspects. The care included a physiotherapist or an occupational therapist coming once a week, a home help coming twice a day and a nurse once a week or more, if needed. This more frequent and routine assistance was initiated after Graham AC20 was admitted numerous times to a hospital due to exacerbations and infections in the previous year. He also reflected that the home help reduced his anxiety, as he knew someone was coming in every day to help him with daily chores. Since a nurse started coming over routinely and checked upon him, he did not need to be admitted to a hospital. Graham AC20 voiced concerns about the hospital care he had previously received, which was not of an adequate standard. He reflected that sometimes, not long after discharge, he was readmitted to the hospital with an infection. In his opinion, if he had had such a level of community support before, the hospital admissions could have been avoided.

Other treatments, such as pulmonary rehabilitation, provided from different levels of care, from secondary care level to primary care, brought improvements in patients' lives, both in physical aspects but also in social ones. Physical exercises, which helped the participants build up stamina and feel better, were much appreciated. Frances AC4, who shortly before being interviewed had commenced pulmonary rehabilitation, was optimistic and satisfied with it. She felt physical improvement after exercises and even purchased exercise bands and an arm and leg pedal bike, which she used every day at home. Glen AC19 attended pulmonary group rehabilitation regularly, once a week or as often as possible. He enjoyed the exercises and felt they kept his lungs in shape:

It's an exercise group and we do mad exercises, like steps and things like that. So, as I say, the COPD bit doesn't help you. It's only helping you to keep your lungs moving and not end up like this.

Glen AC19

The participants usually attended the programme only once; they learnt the exercises and tried to repeat them at home. To some, one programme was enough to learn exercises; to others, it was too costly in long-term treatment or physically challenging. For instance, Susan AC8 found it too burdensome to attend pulmonary rehabilitation as she could not go alone and it was troublesome to organise transport by her family members. Although Susan AC8 liked the group pulmonary rehabilitation due to its social aspects, she felt that having it at home could be advantageous due to her mobility loss. She recounted:

I tried to go myself a couple of times. But it was just so hard to do it on my own. Aye, and even when I got there, I found the exercises were just too much for me.

Susan AC8

Similarly, Ellen AC6 wished to have more pulmonary rehabilitation at home as she found physical exercises beneficial, especially in deteriorating periods.

Another treatment which helped the participants were body massages, provided in a Breathe Easy clinic and in hospices, which relaxed the patients and made their muscles less tense. Two participants, Mark AC5 and Alastair AC9, commented on the tension relief the massages contributed to. Additionally, April AC15 and Sarah AC17, having received the massages, felt pampered and it always lifted their mood. Relaxation sessions could be another way to improve well-being. Mike AC22 participated in these sessions soon after his diagnosis, and it was the therapy which helped him substantially to relieve tension and assist in stopping smoking. By the same token, Alexander AC21

stated that relaxation therapy which could be helpful to him considering his high level of anxiety, was missing from his therapy options.

Another additional support were formal social care workers who visited and helped two participants. Lorna AC10 had house visits twice a week to help her with showering, and Graham AC20 received help twice a day with meal preparation. They both stated that having formal carers took a burden off them and they felt less anxious and more supported. For some participants, however, having formal carers meant a perceived lack of control. For instance, April AC15 and Ellen AC6 were reluctant to ask for formal social support as they had great support from their husbands, who were very understanding and sensitive to their needs. April AC15 felt she was not at the stage of asking for additional help yet:

I suppose at the end of the day you can get a nurse to come in and help you get washed and help you get dressed. But I'm not at that stage, yet.

April AC15

Ellen AC6 thought it would mean that she was not in control anymore:

That would mean I'm not in control there. As long as I can keep going to the bathroom and as long as I can keep struggling now, not that bad. I can have it that way. Probably it would make it easier to somebody come and dress me, but, no, that's not what I have. No, I couldn't cope with that.

Ellen AC6

Almost all participants reported having support from informal carers, such as relatives or friends. However, having someone at home did not necessarily mean feeling supported. Participants whose carers did not understand their diagnosis reported they felt alone, frustrated, sad and not supported, regardless of the severity of the disease. The more the

carers were educated about COPD and the more involved they were in their care, the more sensitive to the patients' needs they were. For instance, Keith AC12 and Alexander AC21 had wives with an excellent understanding of the disease, who both participated in the interviews, joined them in every activity and were immense support for the participants. Keith AC12, who had advanced disease (FEV1 27% pred.), was confident, joyful and hopeful. He felt entirely supported by his wife, who understood COPD and Keith's treatment as well as his needs in every detail. She helped him go out in order to maintain his lifestyle, and she listened to his needs, which contributed to Keith's satisfaction with his care and his feeling of being thoroughly cared for. Alexander AC21, living with less severe COPD (FEV1 65% pred.), also put his confidence in his wife, who accompanied him every time he left home. She understood his needs and was interested in knowing more about the disease and its possible treatments. Likewise, April's AC15 carer, her husband, was involved in her care when the diagnosis was made, and she felt entirely supported. He helped her be active within her capacity and did not let her stay at home and feel sorry for herself. Having him so involved in taking care of her, she believed she would not have done so well without him.

Another example is Sarah AC17, who often had cough syncope and needed full-time surveillance. Her husband was deeply involved in the care and tended to her with patience and fondness, eager to take full responsibility for her care. As a result, Sarah AC17 was so concerned about his mental condition and the fact that he did not have his own time that she insisted on having a befriender and attending a hospice so that he could have a break. She reflected:

The lassie here got me a befriender. Of course, the husband wasn't happy with that. "Happy to look after you" the husband wasn't happy, in the beginning (about a befriender) 'cause "that's what I'm here for, to take you out. (...) I said it's just I need a break away from you the same as you're needing a bigger break away from me that's why I go to the hospice.

Sarah AC17

Hence, it was noticed that patients with carers who understood the diagnosis or were empathic, compassionate and sensitive to their needs were less frustrated. For example, Nancy AC18 and Mark AC5 had nurses as family carers, which contributed to their perception of being understood and cared for. In fact, Mark AC5, who had one of the most severe COPD levels of all participants (FEV1 26% pred.), felt very confident regarding the care he received from his carer.

In contrast, five participants felt alone despite living with a family carer. For instance, Glen AC19, although living with his wife and having regular support from a daughter, did not feel understood because they knew little about COPD and his need for oxygen. Glen AC19 tried to explain this issue to his family; however, he did not feel they understood. Additionally, he mentioned that he would feel less anxious if they did. Glen AC19 further explained:

They know I've got COPD, right, and they know I'm on oxygen. I don't get embarrassed in front of my family but they don't understand like I understand because of COPD and what COPD is. It's a lung disease which is never gonna go away anyway. So, I try and sit and explain that and I feel as if they're not taking that in.

Glen AC19

Similarly, Beth AC16 lived with her husband, who did not understand her disease, or her limitations and needs. In her opinion, at the time of the interview, it was too late to involve

him more in the care, and this should have been done early in the diagnosis. If her husband had been introduced to educational programmes from the beginning, he could have become more involved and supportive. Similarly, Colin AC2, who did not have support from any carer and lived in a care home, felt extremely alone because he did not have anyone to whom he could entrust his care.

Summing up, participants reported that healthcare professionals being timely, competent, and empathic was an essential aspect of feeling supported, just as important as the empathic attitude of the informal carers. It gave the patients a feeling of being understood and not alone with their burden. Patients praised compassion from healthcare professionals and it was appreciated when they were interested in their state, asking “how are you?” not only for the sake of asking but also because they meant it. Graham AC20 described the importance of being listened to:

I feel supported because there is not quite few people, much more than I feel that people interested. Not just going through the motions but genuinely interested in how am I doing. And that helps me.

Graham AC20

Therefore, the quality of support from formal healthcare providers played an essential role in the patients’ perception of being cared for, consequently affecting their well-being. Patients expected healthcare professionals to be knowledgeable about their condition and to know how to manage their disease. Supportive management by professionals also motivated the patients to take care of themselves. Participants considered day hospice beneficial in terms of being supported by healthcare professionals and having opportunities for socialising with peers. Having trust in respiratory consultants’ and GPs’

disease management contributed to their feeling of being taken care of. Participants valued and benefited from good communication and easy access to healthcare professionals. Early recognition of the problem was linked with more control over infections and hospitalisations. The empathy of healthcare providers or social workers made the participants feel more understood, lowering their psychological distress. In contrast, some healthcare professionals' judgmental attitude and lack of involvement led to frustration, especially during hospital admissions.

Attending treatments addressed to COPD patients had a beneficial impact on their lives. For example, pulmonary rehabilitation, as well as peer support groups brought motivational, educational and social benefits. Both played an important role in normalising patients' experiences and enhancing self-management, consequently improving their mood. Finally, the informal carers' role was vital in developing proper self-management by boosting their confidence and decreasing psychological distress. Early education of the carers was undeniably crucial to acquire an understanding of the disease, and subsequently, it fostered the involvement of carers in the care of patients. Consequently, the participants experienced less anxiety when they felt understood and well taken care of by their family members or friends.

4.6. Triangulation of Data

Convergence of data was found in the context of experiencing psychological distress. The results from analysing the questionnaires demonstrated that QOL results had a significant relation with psychological distress, concurring with the findings of the interviews, which disclosed that psychological distress was the most influential factor affecting the participants' well-being. Quantitative data results indicated that the severity of the disease

was significantly correlated with psychological distress. The analysis of the questionnaires revealed that neither the disease severity nor oxygen use was significantly associated with QOL results. Nevertheless, the interviews pointed out that the limitations of using oxygen contributed to being housebound and were regarded as an additional restriction of social activities. Oxygen use was connected with physical relief, helping them breathe, walk distances and experience less psychological distress. The interviews indicated that it was not only the physical symptoms which affected the QOL but also the person's attitude towards living with COPD, accepting the new lifestyle and trying to adjust to it. Not understanding well what symptoms they experienced due to COPD could contribute to feeling frustrated. A small number of those interviewed who had minimal knowledge about COPD suggested that the level of understanding the disease and its causes and the consequences it may entail influences patients' experiences, their QOL and psychological distress. Notably, this was evident in those with the lowest QOL and highest anxiety and depression scores, such as Colin AC2 and Rachel AC11. The former knew nothing about COPD, its progressive nature or that it was caused by smoking. Rachel AC11, who adopted a passive strategy, did not want to know specifics about COPD because she was afraid it would distress her more and increase her anxiety.

Participants could adjust and accept their limitations more easily when they understood their disease and learned to live with it. This helped them to develop or discover new ways in which they could still enjoy their life. For instance, attending support groups, where they could find people with similar troubles, was comforting for many, and they could feel like a part of a community. When participants acknowledged their restrictions, they were more able to manage their breathlessness attacks. Additionally, they were

more prepared to control their panic attacks by attending educational sessions or other designed training, which introduced them to techniques that helped cope with intensified anxieties. The role of informal carers in this process is vital, and the results of the present study indicate that participants without educated informal support struggled to cope with anxieties.

One of the beneficial factors affecting the patients' QOL was the high level of support and understanding. Specifically, the qualitative strand showed that these features from healthcare professionals and informal carers were highly relevant to the participants. Participants explained that having an informal carer who was educated about COPD and recognised the needs of people with COPD was a positive factor. In contrast, participants in both service groups without adequate informal support scored lower QOL and higher anxiety and depression. For example, Colin AC2, who scored the lowest in QOL and the highest in anxiety and depression, had no support from any informal carer. This tendency was supported by the experiences of other participants, such as Beth AC16 and Glen AC19, with one of the lowest reported QOL and highest anxiety and depression, without carers' support despite living with them. These findings confirm the tendency which says that if carers comprehended the reason for the participants' feelings and behaving the way they did, the patients' psychological distress could be decreased because their needs for feeling supported could be met. Overall, these results suggest that educating and involving informal carers in the care of the patients play a crucial role in maintaining QOL and reducing anxiety and depression.

The results from the interview analysis indicated that the attitude and coping strategies were affected by other factors, such as education about the disease provided by healthcare professionals or attending interventions in the form of pulmonary rehabilitation, self-management programmes or educational sessions. They all facilitated the process of coping with the disease as they were an opportunity to gain knowledge about the disease, learn ways to cope when experiencing physical and psychological symptoms, and prepare for what their lives could look like. The opportunity for socialising with peers was another beneficial factor that these interventions brought to the participants' lives. They could talk to and see their peers dealing with similar struggles. Participants could compare and exchange their experiences and observe how other people coped. Oftentimes, this allowed them to see that they were not the only ones having these problems, which was comforting to some. This could affect the facilitation of the process of acceptance. To be specific, adaptation usually followed when patients knew what to expect from their disease. As a result, when they accepted what their lifestyle looked like, they could adjust to it, coming to terms with the limitations and finding ways to maintain parts of their lifestyle. Adaptation could also influence participants' way of looking at their disease and their limited lifestyle, developing ways of enjoying their life, such as having new activities performed within their physical limitations.

The interviews also pointed to the need for a holistic overview and agreement that psychological and social aspects of living with COPD were the most conspicuous. Therefore, the focus of care should be on them through potentially beneficial interventions introduced in the early phases after diagnoses, such as self-management programmes, educational sessions, group pulmonary rehabilitation or support groups. Although the

questionnaire data support that attending additional therapies did not significantly affect QOL, the results from the interviews indicated that additional interventions reported benefits. Participants could take more advantage of the additional therapies when they were introduced in the early stages of the disease and when the informal carer was also involved. Having opportunities to participate in the abovementioned interventions gave the participants a chance to learn techniques to cope with struggles as the disease progressed. This helped the participants acknowledge and understand the diagnosis sooner and improve their self-management already in the milder stages of the disease.

In contrast, when patients already had severe and very severe COPD, they did not believe that therapies had any practical use, such as improvements in self-management. For example, the group pulmonary rehabilitation exercises were difficult to perform, and patients believed it was too late for education sessions for them and the carers. People with advanced COPD preferred to do exercises which they had learned in rehabilitation programmes by themselves at home or to have individual pulmonary rehabilitation at home. They still appreciated massages, relaxation therapies and counselling. Also, when being in end-of-life care, peer groups helped with acceptance of their condition and were socially beneficial. Communication with others with the same problems was crucial to adapting to the new circumstances of the disease. Despite the positive aspects of palliative care intervention in advanced stages, it may be assumed that adding new therapies early in the diagnosis would bring more therapeutic benefits than adding them in the advanced stage of COPD.

Turning now to the aspect of healthcare services, the data from questionnaires revealed that people attending specialist palliative care services experienced higher anxiety and depression and lower QOL than people in generalist palliative care (Tables 4.3 and 4.4.). Participants in the hospice presented slightly less severe COPD (Table 4.1.); hence, the disease severity does not seem to play a role in their experiences, and it suggests that other factors could affect hospice participants' experiences. Four of the six hospice participants received their first course of day hospice care, while one received only group rehabilitation sessions. Still, all hospice care receivers had positive impressions of attending this service. Therefore, it is possible that the day hospice care was not provided for a sufficient period to reflect on the participants' lives. Also, when interviewed, some revealed that they were unsure what their treatment would be in the future and when they could attend day hospice again. These results imply that some participants could experience anxiety connected with uncertainty and lack of control of their treatment. Nonetheless, the sample from the hospice was smaller than from the Breathe Easy clinic; therefore, the representation is unequal, and these are only observations based on this sample.

The results suggest an association between the level of understanding about the disease, informal support level, QOL and psychological distress of people with COPD. Empathy from healthcare providers and informal carers, as well as properly provided education, facilitated developing the self-management strategies. In turn, this could further help decrease psychological distress and improve QOL of people with COPD. Finally, the time frame in which participants received initial support from palliative care seemed to play a crucial role in having and developing self-management strategies. Referral to palliative

care or other additional interventions in the early stages of COPD positively affected the self-management competencies of people with COPD and their carers. Together these results demonstrate, confirm and provide an in-depth outlook of factors affecting patients' QOL when living with advanced COPD. The Figure 4.11. presents the results from the triangulation, explaining the process of relieving psychological distress and improving the QOL of the participants.

Figure 4.11: Triangulation of data

Chapter 5: Discussion

The discussion chapter presents the results of this concurrent embedded mixed methods study in the context of the wider literature. Subsequently, the strengths and limitations of this piece of work are outlined and recommendations for future research and practice are discussed.

5.1. COPD and Quality of Life

This study reported that higher psychological distress, measured with HADS, was correlated with QOL, measured with MQOL-R. It is a relatively recent questionnaire published in 2017 (Cohen *et al.*, 2017), and as a consequence, there are few published papers to compare with. So far, this has been the first study which employed MQOL-R to investigate the COPD population. Till now, only Althaus, Borasio and Bernard (2018) conducted a study using MQOL-R with 64 palliative care patients (34 women, mean age of 67), with a primary diagnosis of cancer (n=52), lateral amyotrophic sclerosis (N=7), heart disease (n=2) or other (n=3). The score of MQOL-R was 6.1 (\pm 1.8), and the psychological distress measured with HADS was 14.7 (\pm 6.1), with subscales HAD-A and HAD-D at 7.4 (\pm 3.5) and 7.3 (\pm 4.1), respectively. Comparing their results with this study, it is clear that people with COPD experience poorer QOL (5.84 \pm 2.17) and more pronounced anxiety and depression (18.95 \pm 7.88 HADS total, 10.14 \pm 4.79 for HAD-A and 8.81 \pm 4.29 for HAD-D) than those with cancer or other diagnoses in palliative care. Studies exploring the COPD population which used different instruments, found a corresponding tendency. Namely, a higher QOL positively correlates with psychological well-being (Blinderman *et al.*, 2009; Jang *et al.*, 2019) and physical restrictions substantially limit HRQOL (Hynninen, Pallesen and Nordhus, 2007; Brandl *et al.*, 2018).

This study found that severity, sex, and other sociodemographic factors did not affect QOL. Other authors found analogous results, stating that severity did not affect QOL. Stenzel *et al.* (2015), who evaluated the importance of sociodemographic variables, illness severity, psychological distress and disease-specific anxieties as predictors of end-of-life fears in 131 participants with COPD with FEV1% pred. mean 39.14 (\pm 15.68), aged 65.10 years old (\pm 8.39), reported that severity affected neither QOL nor psychological well-being. Therefore, the results from this study and available literature imply that people with COPD report low scores on QOL and that psychological distress plays a vital role in their QOL. The present study also noticed a difference in QOL between the different types of settings providing palliative care. That is, patients who attended day hospice had lower QOL scores (4.65 ± 2.71) compared to those who attended Breathe Easy clinic (6.29 ± 1.83). However, the sample size for this study was too small to provide calculations with strong power and there was a disproportion of patients from both services, 6 in hospice versus 16 in Breathe Easy clinic. Cochrane, Colville and Conway (2008) found that day hospice is a feasible and a practical option for patients with non-malignant diseases. Yet, research about people with COPD receiving outpatient hospice care is insufficient to date.

5.2. COPD and Psychological Distress

In this research, the HADS total score was higher than in most other COPD population studies, with similar age groups and disease severity. Farver-Vestergaard *et al.* (2018), in a RCT testing the efficacy of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy as an add-on to a standard PR programme, investigated a sample of 84 people with a mean age of 67.2 ± 7.74 and FEV1% pred. 37.64 ± 11.74 pred. which is comparable to the present study

sample (FEV1% pred. 36.9 ± 13.8 pred. and mean age of 67.2 ± 8.7). Their sample had a baseline HADS of 13.72 ± 7.67 , hence much lower than this study (18.95 ± 7.88), suggesting that the sample from this study experienced higher levels of psychological distress. Also, a study by Gore, Brophy and Greenstone (2000), with 50 subjects with severe COPD, reported total HADS of 10.18 ± 3.95 , considerably lower compared to the present study. The participants had severe COPD; however, the exact severity expressed by FEV1 % pred. was not specified in that study. Similarly, Bove, Lavesen and Lindegaard (2020) described the demographics and psychosocial characteristics of people with advanced COPD attending an outpatient clinic ($n = 242$) in a population older than the present study, 72.01 ± 8.40 years, with similar severity that is FEV1 pred. $38.04\% \pm 12.74\%$ pred. The authors analysed HADS with its separate subscales, denoting HAD-A at 5.07 ± 3.92 and HAD-D at 5.77 ± 3.89 , which are lower than in the present study (HAD-A 10.14 ± 4.79 and HAD-D 8.82 ± 4.29). Although HADS and its subscales scores in this study are lower compared to other studies, they are similar to the findings obtained in a retrospective study with 480 participants by Grosbois *et al.* (2020), who reported a HADS total of 17.8 ± 7.7 , HAD-A 9.9 ± 4.6 , HAD-D 8.0 ± 4.2 , after investigating outcomes of home-based pulmonary rehabilitation for people with COPD in a sample with similar severity (FEV1 36% pred., SD not provided) and age (64.2 ± 11.3 years).

In this study, increased psychological distress was correlated with increased severity (p -value = 0.037). However, the effect of lung function on the risk of anxiety and depression is not an obvious outcome. A study in the Netherlands with 118 COPD subjects, with FEV1 pred. $56.0\% \pm 27.2\%$, 57.5 ± 9.0 years, reported no significant results of severity involving general psychological distress (p -value > .05) or depression (p -value = .09)

(Wagena *et al.*, 2005). Similarly, in Norway, Hynninen, Pallesen and Nordhus (2007), in a sample with 58 COPD outpatients with FEV1% pred. 53.79 ± 23.96 , 62.1 ± 8.6 years, showed that the severity of the disease did not affect anxiety (p-value = .110) and depression (p-value = .117). In contrast, a Canadian study with 717 COPD (373 GOLD 1, 259 GOLD 2 and 40 with GOLD 3) and 797 matched non-COPD individuals, aged 66.71 ± 9.83 years, indicated that disease severity influenced depression (p-value < .001) but not anxiety (p-value = .22) (Paine *et al.*, 2019). Likewise, a study in a Chinese population (n = 49,053) with 2600 individuals with GOLD 1, 1717 with GOLD 2, and 369 with GOLD 3 and 4, demonstrated that more severe lung impairment significantly affected the development of anxiety and depression (p-value < 0.001) (Huang *et al.*, 2021). The causal factors of anxiety and depression in COPD have not been fully explored. It is reasonable to expect that patients with severe lung function impairment may have a higher risk of anxiety and depression because they may experience more respiratory symptoms and have other comorbidities, which has not been explored in this study.

In conclusion, participants in this study presented higher anxiety and depression scores measured with HADS, compared to studies with similar populations regarding age and severity. The subjects recruited for this study were people with advanced COPD who attended palliative care services, and despite receiving supportive care, they presented high psychological distress measured with HADS. What is interesting and has never been researched is that those who attended specialist palliative care services presented higher scores in HADS than those who attended generalist palliative care. However, the sample size was relatively small and the number of participants in both services was not equal due to the very small number of patients with COPD in day hospices. This reduced the

generalisability of the results to the extent of what was happening in the recruited hospices. Yet, from 11 eligible patients from 5 hospices, 6 individuals agreed to participate; thus, the findings manifest the majority's experiences. Finally, the quantitative strand of this study was supplementary to the qualitative arm, as per the embedded mixed methods design data from interviews which delivered a richer explanation in the form of a narrative of the participants, complementing the findings.

5.3. Factors of Healthcare Delivery Affecting Experiences of People with Advanced COPD in Palliative Care

People with advanced COPD experience a high physical symptom burden, which leads to a loss of functionality and a high level of psychological distress. Thus, person-centred care is recognised as potentially beneficial for these patients in addition to acknowledging their social support needs (Gardener *et al.*, 2018). British and Scottish strategy documents emphasise the need to stress these patients' physical, psychological, social and spiritual needs through a holistic, supportive and person-centred model of care (Scottish Government, 2019; National Palliative and End of Life Care Partnership, 2021). Kusnanto, Agustian and Hilmanto (2018) highlighted that the management of the long-term conditions could be implemented in integrated and holistic care by addressing the BPS model principles. It may help clinicians understand the interplay of biological, psychological and social constituents of their disease, and it could further lead to advancements in patient care by improving multidisciplinary approaches and the relationship between physicians and patients. Nevertheless, clinical medical guidelines and clinical performance indicators are biomedical-focused, and they suggest that workload and lack of expertise can disadvantage the execution of the BPS model (van

Dijk-de Vries *et al.*, 2012). The traditional medical model of the doctor-patient relationship presents a situation in which a patient comes to an expert, a medical practitioner, for a consultation and supplementation of their knowledge and understanding (Parsons, 1951). However, this tends to be less effective for patients with chronic diseases, who often have a great level of expertise and information (Kelly, 2015). Previous research has also stressed that attention should be paid to using shared decision making and connecting to the goals and motivation of the patient (Elwyn *et al.*, 2012) rather than only providing information and advice, which may fail to contribute to lifestyle changes (Marteau, Hollands and Kelly, 2015). Nevertheless, Hillebrecht *et al.* (2017) showed that patients with COPD and healthcare professionals had problems identifying patient-orientated goals and expectations. A possible explanation for these findings can be that patients were not used to having a proactive role due to being framed in a traditional and medically oriented structure of the consultation.

The BPS model can empower patients to participate more actively in their disease management (Kusnanto, Agustian and Hilmanto, 2018), and it should be given a high priority in providing ideal care (van Dijk-de Vries *et al.*, 2012). This study indicated that proper education of patients and carers could facilitate their engagement in care, resulting in improved coping strategies and treatment adherence. According to the review of Kaptein, Fischer and Scharloo (2014), the way COPD patients perceive their disease helps them adjust self-management in order to improve illness outcomes. Thus, the quality of information provided to the patients is vital. Medical professionals with skills suitable for COPD care and up-to-date knowledge should educate patients using a holistic approach. A study by Siltanen *et al.* (2020), with specialist palliative care services and

primary care health professionals in Finland, suggested that although some areas of patients' education concerning disease management aspects such as smoking cessation, pharmacological treatment, and exercise were usually well covered, there were others which were neglected. These included psychosocial aspects (stress, depression, fatigue, and social life) as well as end-of-life decisions concerning a living will and palliative care. Therefore, the psychosocial aspects of patients' education need to be addressed more thoroughly.

There were several differences in providing patient education, depending on the type of professionals and levels of care. Siltanen *et al.* (2020) showed that specialist medical workers provided education more systematically compared to primary care professionals. Doctors and nurses covered different areas of education, with doctors emphasising the diagnostic procedures and treatment of COPD and nurses focusing on practical management of COPD such as inhalation technique, mouth care and nutrition. Nurses, especially in primary care, were more active than doctors regarding psychosocial aspects of education, such as well-being, fatigue, stress, anxiety and depression management. Hence, their study emphasises the valuable role of primary care nurses. Their findings align with this study, in which patients highly appreciated the input of community nurses. Nonetheless, sometimes participants suggested that the support from the community nurses was insufficient, complained about their infrequent visits and noticed that this aspect required improvements. The present findings seem to be consistent with Candy *et al.* (2007), in a national survey in England and Wales of COPD specialist nurses in the community, which found that there is little service delivery and a mismatch between the

effectiveness of the service and its provision. Therefore, these services seem to require restructuring in order to be more available to the patients and meet their needs.

This study indicated that what positively influenced the psychological well-being of people was the attitude of the healthcare providers, clear communication and patients being well-informed. Patients benefited from a good relationship with nurses or other healthcare workers and social carers, improving their health outcomes such as QOL and psychological burden. What mattered to the participants was being understood and having their needs met. When trusting the healthcare professionals, people with COPD were more willing to express their complaints, knowing that they were heard and often addressed. Thus, proper communication could lead to referrals for other required treatments and activities, such as pulmonary rehabilitation, counselling and changes in medications, which in turn, could directly improve patient's physical symptoms and their coping with the condition. This study emphasises the role psychosocial elements play in the satisfaction of received care previously recorded in the broader literature. A qualitative study by van Mook *et al.* (2012) on healthcare complaints from patients and families revealed that lack of sympathy and empathy, unsatisfactory clarification or insufficient information and impolite communication were three of the most common complaints. Correspondingly, in a study with patients in palliative care, most of whom had a malignant diagnosis, Kiesewetter *et al.* (2016) reported that communication and professionalism determined patients' perception of errors in palliative care. This also coincides with observations of this study, which confirmed that proper communication paved the way for education about the diagnosis.

Previously authors reported the importance of patient satisfaction in communication with physicians (Partridge, dal Negro and Olivieri, 2011; Celli *et al.*, 2017). However, proper communication is still an issue, and Ecenarro *et al.* (2018) identified lack of training in palliative care among pulmonologists as a barrier to improved communication with patients. Lindgren, Storli and Wiklund-Gustin (2014) stated that healthcare professionals should realise that the way the diagnosis is communicated and disclosed evidently affects patient's perception of the disease. Good communication is key to ascertaining if patients linger in negotiation or progress towards acceptance and new understanding. Thus, the diagnosis should be delivered face-to-face, clearly, and with empathy, subsequently giving information about the condition.

The present study indicated that understanding the diagnosis was reported by almost all participants as a factor which facilitated their acceptance of the disease. Participants in the study who were aware of the treatment options and had regular consultations with healthcare providers, such as respiratory specialists and nurses, were usually satisfied with the communication and the education concerning treatment and disease progression. Participants felt that, if necessary, they could ask questions during home visits by a nurse, who could forward them to a GP or a respiratory consultant. Current evidence suggests a concerning lack of COPD-specific information being either shared or retained by people living with COPD. Seamark *et al.* (2004) reported that most people with COPD acknowledged the severity of the illness and its terminal nature and talked about having a good relationship with their GP. In contrast, other authors, such as Hayle *et al.* (2013), evaluating experiences of people with COPD who attended specialist palliative care, reported that they lacked information about their disease, its course and

options of treatment and care. Correspondingly, Habraken *et al.* (2008) and Véron *et al.* (2018) recorded that people with COPD did not regard themselves as sick, which further hampered the identification of their needs due to a lack of understanding of their disease and its symptoms. Patients' limited knowledge concerning the cause, process, and incurability of COPD was linked with physicians' lack of ability to communicate with patients effectively (Marx *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, healthcare professionals should consider listening to patients' complaints, needs and concerns, creating an opportunity to understand the aspects of their everyday life. It is an important issue, and according to the Lithuanian study by Gauronskaite *et al.* (2016), 46% of participants believed their condition would improve or heal completely, and only 1% of participants considered the possibility that it could lead to death, which indicates that patients' perception of their future was poor and they lacked information about their disease and its seriousness. Conversely, in this study, the participants had quite a high level of understanding of their condition and level of treatment, often linking it to the exemplary communication skills of their pulmonologists and nurses and consequently felt they were in control of their care. However, those who complained about a lack of dialogue and information from their healthcare professionals had certain shortcomings in terms of control over their treatment. The findings from this study noticed considerably good information about the disease and high involvement of patients in their treatment. This could be attributed to the fact that most patients attended support groups and educational sessions in their community service or via supportive care clinics, which suggests that proper understanding of the diagnosis empowered patients to involve in their treatment and develop self-management skills. Similarly, Johnson *et al.* (2016) reported that patients' active engagement could

enhance their abilities to self-manage their disease. Hence, positive collaboration with healthcare providers can help improve patients' QOL and reduce psychological distress.

Authors in the past recognised that patient activation and development of self-management skills depend on several factors. Bucknall *et al.* (2012), in their RTC based in the West of Scotland with participants instructed to detect and treat exacerbations promptly, revealed specific characteristics concerning self-management. Successful self-managers were younger and lived with others, while poor self-managers were older and lived alone. Therefore, the latter seem to be the population among COPD patients who require more attention. However, there is a lack of evidence to provide information on successful patients' activation in tailored COPD self-management interventions (Yadav, Hosseinzadeh and Baral, 2018).

The results of this study match those observed in earlier studies with chronic disease patients and indicate that adequate communication skills are crucial to building a good rapport between patients and healthcare professionals, leading to improved patient activation. Greene and Hibbard (2012) and Alexander *et al.* (2012) emphasised the role of patient activation and the doctor-patient relationship and suggested that healthcare personnel spend more time with patients to build a trustful relationship and provide education.

The concept of empathy is a common denominator for many health professionals. For years, the person-centred approach and empathy have been proposed as a shared standard for healthcare workers such as physicians, nurses, therapists and social workers (Ouzouni and Nakakis, 2012; Hasgul and Serpen, 2014; Kerasidou and Horn, 2016;

Deligianni *et al.*, 2017). According to the findings from this study, being skilfully and empathetically cared for by healthcare workers was highly appreciated by people with COPD, who positively commented on these characteristics of the staff. Healthcare personnel interested in their state, asking "how are you?" and listening to what they had to say were highly esteemed as empathic and understanding, and easily approachable medical staff increased patients' confidence. Additionally, being understood by healthcare professionals and having a complete clarification of the diagnosis and its progress gave patients a feeling of reassurance. It was of principal value to participants to be treated as a person with deference and empathy. Similarly, a qualitative study by Gysels *et al.* (2016) with people with refractory breathlessness, presented results comparable to this study, reporting that participants considered healthcare personnel to be specialists in overseeing their disease in person-centred care. They particularly valued being approached with respect to their dignity. The person-centred approach, acceptance and empathy qualities of the healthcare worker has been the scope of focus in the training and delivery of clinical social practice across various healthcare sectors (Deligianni *et al.*, 2017; Santana *et al.*, 2018; Suazo *et al.*, 2020). Moudatsou *et al.* (2020) informed that some professionals found it challenging to adopt an empathetic communication strategy in everyday practice. They associated it with insufficient time in their consultation, a high number of patients, and a lack of academic education about empathy. Therefore, it seems that services for people with COPD require to be redesigned in order to better address the needs of patients. Healthcare professionals should have the opportunity to provide person-centred care, and they require more disease-specific training on how to tackle the important issues for people with COPD.

5.4. Psychosocial Support for People with Advanced COPD

This study explored psychosocial aspects of people with COPD who attended generalist or specialist palliative care services. The findings seem to be consistent with other research which indicated that people with COPD particularly appreciated the psychosocial support received through the palliative care services. The potential of this support for living with chronic illnesses has been previously addressed in the literature. Charmaz (1983) revealed that people with chronic illnesses experience a limited lifestyle, social isolation, a feeling of being discredited and burdening others, all of which contributed to the loss of self. Subsequently, living a limited life might intensify patients' feeling of 'loss of self' due to the lack of chances for self-validation through significant interactions with others. A study by Xiao *et al.* (2021) in older adults with chronic illnesses highlighted the effect of daily living activities and perceived support on psychological distress. Notably, the perceived social support was an element which decreased the psychological distress caused by chronic illnesses. Likewise, this study and Metting, van der Molen and Kocks (2016) found corresponding findings: lack of social support from family and friends caused experiencing anger and sadness and could lead to social isolation.

Social support is a factor that reduces the risks concerning the well-being of patients with chronic illnesses (Heinze *et al.*, 2015). In patients recuperating from myocardial infarction, availability of social support was viewed as strongly connected with presenting fewer depressive symptoms (Lett *et al.*, 2009). It was mentioned previously in the literature that psychosocial resources in the form of social support can contribute to managing and delaying the progression in some chronic progressive conditions. Lenferink, van der

Palen and Effing (2018) indicated that for people with COPD patient-tailored self-management interventions with facilitated social support are advised, as they may introduce opportunities to positively impact self-management behaviours.

Likewise, Fu *et al.* (2021) explored palliative care needs, experiences of attending palliative care services and their integration with COPD services for patients and their caregivers. The study reported that patients who received psychological and educational interventions were more confident about managing their disease. They interviewed 20 patients, 6 carers and 25 health professionals, and reported that patients who received psychological and educational interventions were more confident about managing their disease and exacerbations. These results were achieved thanks to person-centred approaches and frequent home visits, encompassing self-management and monitoring, speedy responses to crises, and post-exacerbation education. There was an upturn in the delivery of pulmonary rehabilitation and smoking cessation services, principally in primary care. This agrees with results from this study, which found that people with early palliative care or education had more self-management skills compared to those who received palliative care only in very severe stages of COPD. This links back to the importance of patient empowerment. As previously reported in a study with people with chronic pain, the multidisciplinary approaches can improve coping resources, and empower patients to manage emotionally related symptoms through self-regulatory, behavioural and cognitive techniques (Roditi and Robinson, 2011).

Previous evidence indicated that non-pharmacological interventions such as psychological support or CBT might improve patients' anxiety and depression (Baraniak and Sheffield, 2011; Smith *et al.*, 2014; Ma *et al.*, 2020). In this study, only a few patients

received psychological interventions or CBT, and they acknowledged its contribution, especially in quitting smoking. Therefore, it would be worthwhile to investigate the possible impact of these non-pharmacological interventions for people with advanced COPD in palliative care.

Providing psychological and educational interventions, e.g. in a form of pulmonary rehabilitation, could further lead to improvements in social aspects of patients' lives, such as meeting with other people in support groups or developing techniques, such as breathing techniques, to cope with physical symptoms. Furthermore, this study revealed that participants attending day hospice and support groups regarded meetings with other people with similar problems as a social asset. It empowered them to leave their home, which in turn, allowed them to socialise, compare their disease experience with other patients, and normalise it. Evidence previously acknowledged that peer support provides an opportunity for sharing and validating patients' experiences with others (Cicutto, Brooks and Henderson, 2004; Ellison *et al.*, 2012; Lindgren, Storli and Wiklund-Gustin, 2014). Engaging in COPD-specific social activities was a mechanism through which psychological distress decreased. In chronic conditions receiving social and emotional support from others can be beneficial by improving the use of social resources and social integration (Barrera *et al.*, 2006).

Similarly, Milanowska *et al.* (2017), in a study investigating factors affecting the QOL of 84 farmers with COPD, suggested that support groups could be a feasible solution for meeting patients' needs, as they could share their experiences and knowledge about the disease and empathically listen to one another's problems. Analogous findings were

presented by Hayle *et al.* (2013). They found that the service provided by specialist palliative care in a hospice seemed to have a positive influence on diminishing the social isolation of COPD patients, as the hospice provides patients with opportunities for social interaction and sharing experiences about their ill-health. Hospice was reported to improve the well-being of people with COPD, enhance their mood and self-esteem and avoid feeling alone with their burden. This is further supported by wider literature in the field, which indicates that social support can be a valuable component of early palliative care for people with COPD and improve their QOL (Bausewein *et al.*, 2018; Sarwar *et al.*, 2021).

The interventions which offer social and psychological support such as support groups, educational sessions, pulmonary rehabilitation and day-hospices, can be provided by various services, through generalist palliative care and specialist palliative care. The present study showed that attending a support group with educational sessions brought positive outcomes, both social and psychological. As patients' social lives were usually restricted, it gave them opportunities to socialise and meet new people. Meeting peers with similar problems helped them normalise their experience and therefore diminish apparent psychological burden. Additionally, having an opportunity of regular contact with healthcare professionals gave them a feeling of being regularly tended to and not left alone. Other studies also demonstrated improvements in attending a breathlessness service due to having more personalised care. That is, Reilly *et al.* (2016), in a study with patients who completed a 6-week breathlessness support service intervention, 52% of whom had COPD, reported high satisfaction with the service, mostly coming from personalised care, nature of the staff, education as well as empowerment and

effectiveness of context-specific breathlessness interventions. Similarly, Higginson *et al.* (2014), investigating breathlessness service in a single-blind randomised trial with patients with various diseases, 54% of whom had COPD, showed that mastery of breathlessness was improved in the group which received the intervention. Hence, personalised programmes dealing with psychological, educational and self-management aspects, delivered from different levels of care, promise to improve patients' disease management and enhance their social lives.

The role of social support from self-management programmes for people with COPD still needs to be explored. To date, few studies have investigated the impact of social networks on COPD patients. This study found that a supportive social network was a positive factor in motivation to quit smoking, elevate mood, and cope with new life challenges.

5.5. Palliative Care Provision and its Influence on Patients' Experiences

National Institute for Clinical Excellence (2004) recommended that people with end-stage COPD and their carers should have access to the full scope of services offered by multidisciplinary palliative care teams. The main objective of palliative care is to improve QOL (López-Campos *et al.*, 2022), and national COPD guidelines should encourage early referrals to palliative care, which can be the best treatment (Strutt, 2020) and should be integrated at all points of trajectory of COPD (Iyer *et al.*, 2022). People with COPD are vulnerable and experience high physical, psychosocial and spiritual burdens; therefore, identification of their needs in the early stages can help provide need-based palliative care (Meffert *et al.*, 2015). Carlucci, Guerrieri and Nava (2012) recommended early palliative care, joined with curative and restorative care, when there is a deterioration of

symptoms such as breathlessness, pain, fatigue and depression. This study confirmed the findings by Iyer *et al.* (2022), namely that early palliative care, in order for patients and their carers to benefit from it, should be promoted and integrated before the end-of-life stage so that they can be better prepared for this stage.

Palliative care can be offered through different levels of care. Available literature presents samples from either generalist palliative care in primary and secondary care or specialist palliative care in secondary care and hospices. One of the eligibility criteria for participation in this study was attending a generalist or a specialist palliative care service. This study suggested that patients should be introduced to palliative care services early in the diagnosis and, within their framework, referred to support groups, pulmonary rehabilitation or educational sessions in order to help them cope with the disease, both physically and mentally. These findings align with Temel *et al.* (2010), who, in a study with people with non-small-cell lung cancer, reported that early palliative care led to improved mood and QOL and prolonged survival by approximately two months. Similarly, Nottelmann *et al.* (2021), in their study with patients with advanced cancer, argued for early palliative care introduction: they reported an improved QOL after a 12-week palliative rehabilitation intervention, which patients attended soon after a diagnosis.

Concerning the results of this study, it did not matter from which sources care was provided; they all brought benefits. Most of the participants in this study were recruited from a respiratory Breathe Easy clinic group provided by a specialist respiratory team. The Breathe Easy clinic offered a disease-specific support group, while patients with a wide range of malignant and non-malignant diseases attended a day hospice.

Nevertheless, both types of care were noted for bringing considerable positive contributions to patients' lives.

Several studies explored ways to incorporate palliative care into the care of patients with COPD. In a review of patients with different diagnoses, receiving specialist palliative care, Gaertner *et al.* (2017) reported a small effect on QOL; however, it was stated that it could be more effective when provided early. Specialist palliative care has potential benefits if it detects through screening those patients with unmet needs and if it is delivered early. Although the provision of specialist palliative care offers improvements, a study evaluating specialist palliative care for people with COPD in a hospital found no major differences between this group and those who received standardised care (Véron *et al.*, 2018).

Studies in the past recognised different ways of introducing breathlessness services into the care of people with COPD. Bausewein *et al.* (2018) stated that breathlessness services can be a source of early access to palliative care and a valuable non-pharmacological approach to developing strategies for self-management. The breathlessness support services can contribute to change in cognitive and behavioural reactions to breathlessness, which can further lead to enhanced self-management through emotional regulation, meaning-based coping and improved problem management (Gysels and Higginson, 2009; Hillebregt *et al.*, 2017; Lockett *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2019). This links back to the emotional distress-related symptoms which could be alleviated by the implementation of the self-regulatory techniques (Roditi and Robinson, 2011).

Habraken *et al.* (2009), investigating HRQOL of people with COPD or lung cancer, suggested that due to challenges of end-stage COPD, such as predicaments in the prognosis of the diagnosis, incorporating palliative care for COPD in general healthcare is more advisable rather than expanding admission to specific palliative care services. Also, Elkington *et al.* (2004) found that community health services may be in demand for end-stage COPD people, considering their high morbidity and being housebound. Their study also noticed that a respiratory nurse may have beneficial potential in the care of patients with advanced COPD and may be a helpful link between the GP, the chest physician, and the palliative care team. Similarly, the present study indicated that having good contact with a district nurse gave patients a feeling of comfort. Those patients who did not have frequent contact with community nurses felt that it was missing in their healthcare. They also mentioned that having more frequent in-home visits from these nurses could help to identify a chest infection sooner. Likewise, Seamark *et al.* (2004) argued for more improvements in day-to-day care. The study participants found hospital clinics' surveillance and monitoring of the disease with respiratory nurse specialists impersonal and considered it an exhausting and challenging experience. Some felt that contact with hospital clinics and having other strangers involved in care induced additional distress.

Previous studies suggested that day-to-day palliative care is more likely to be provided by primary healthcare rather than a specialist respiratory nurse or clinic-based health professionals. It seems feasible for new interventions, such as supportive clinics, to provide more personal, regular check-ups and contact with healthcare workers and peers. The present mixed methods study confirmed previously reported positive influence of this

intervention on patients with non-malignant conditions (Farquhar *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, regarding Wagg (2012) five-factor spectrum of support for people with COPD, the sample in this study lacked integration of the last step, that is integrative care, which includes ongoing support and a long-term supervised exercise or maintenance programme. Not all participants had long-term exercise guaranteed; however, most had maintenance programmes provided by day hospice or supportive care clinic service.

5.6. Carers Involvement in the Care

Caregivers play a vital role in the management of people with COPD and an absence of a carer is a risk factor for the increased need for palliative care (Meffert *et al.*, 2015). According to this study, carers' participation and involvement in patients' additional interventions are highly appreciated by the recipients. Primarily because carers being well informed about the disease facilitated supporting the needs of the patients, developing empathy and taking better care of the patients. This finding supports previous research into this area and accentuates the importance and helpfulness of family networks while living with a severe condition (Heinze *et al.*, 2015; Benkel, Arnby and Molander, 2020). In line with the results of Benkel, Arnby and Molander (2020) this study demonstrated that emotional support and carers' help with everyday tasks can contribute to patients adjustment to the new life situation.

Pinto *et al.* (2007) suggested that that the quality of the relationship affected the quality of care received from the carer. The current study found that having a close relationship with a caregiver prior to or after diagnosis allowed patients to be more open about their needs. Essentially, when patients did not have a close relationship with their carers, it was more difficult to involve them in the care and expect them to assist. This finding is in

agreement with findings of Dinicola *et al.* (2013), which showed that the quality of the relationship with the person who provided care played a role in how people with COPD perceived interaction and support. This study promotes the idea that informal carers' attendance in the support groups should be encouraged as it facilitates their involvement in patient care and consequently improves the patients' self-management. Furthermore, the findings of the current study are consistent with those of Dinicola *et al.* (2013), who stated that the support from informal carers was of vital importance for the patients. Consequently, people with COPD who had strong support from their informal carers, who were highly involved in their care, noted that having no barriers in communication helped them be open with their informal carers, contributing to improved self-management and decreased perceived anxiety.

Other authors found additional positive contributions from caregivers. Scheerens *et al.* (2018b) observed that involving informal caregivers can enhance early integrated palliative care. Furthermore, Aasbø *et al.* (2016) concluded that caregivers could have a crucial role in the improvement of patients' self-care, which corroborates with findings from the present study. Additionally, Aasbø *et al.* (2016) observed that caregivers assisted in maintaining disease stability and in preventing emotional distress and breathlessness, especially when acquiring knowledge about COPD. Caregivers also helped to limit dyspnoea by keeping their homes clean of dust, learning breathing techniques and assisting patients with activities which could induce breathlessness. Likewise, caregivers were reported to help prevent patients' emotional distress by avoiding making them feel a burden, controlling triggers that could provoke distress and bringing joy and a sense of purpose to their lives. Caregivers could contribute to

unburdening patients by contacting healthcare professionals on their behalf (Aasbø *et al.*, 2016; Strang *et al.*, 2018), when patients were sometimes not sure of their need for consultation or did not recognise that the deterioration of their condition required a physician's opinion (Essue *et al.*, 2010). Finally, caregivers play a role in motivating the patients to take their medications properly (Schafheutle, Fegan and Ashcroft, 2018).

All in all, the role of caregivers appears to be critical in maintaining and improving patients' self-management and, as such, should receive more attention, especially when introducing carers into the care of patients from the early diagnosis. Their involvement in the care of patients should be encouraged and facilitated. However, there is a lack of interventions which support informal caregivers in aspects such as education and there should be more focus on the potential of informal caregivers' role (Marques, Cruz and Brooks, 2021).

5.7. Strengths and Limitations of the Study

This mixed methods design was a novel study investigating the QOL as well as psychological and social aspects of life of people with advanced COPD in palliative care. It added to the growing body of evidence-based literature around the factors which affected the QOL of people in palliative care with COPD and provided a rich understanding of their needs. This research brought together patients' experiences and views and then supplemented their voices with an objective measurement of psychological distress and QOL from validated questionnaires.

The mixed methods design was a distinctive feature of this study. It was demonstrated that using both methods can accomplish a desired aim by employing an embedded

design. The strength of this mixed methods research design was triangulation in order to find agreement and validation between the two study strands. Nevertheless, there were several limitations to the study.

Firstly, data came from interviews with a limited group of participants in the West of Scotland. Therefore, the views are not generalisable to all patients. As patients were only recruited from a single secondary care service and three hospices, the sample is inadequate to portray the full spectrum of patients, particularly those who are not referred to the services or have not been doctor-diagnosed.

Another limitation seems to be the fact that the number of participants from specialist palliative care (n=6) was considerably lower than that from generalist palliative care services (n=16); hence, the results are predominantly represented by patients from the latter. This could lead to a standpoint bias and the findings cannot represent people who received care from other services. However, six other participants were recruited from 3 different services in an attempt to provide data from a varied sample.

Participation in this study was voluntary; thus, the presented sample could be a group of patients less affected physically and psychologically. Although all participants attended palliative care services, some other patients, who were in poorer health, in more deteriorating condition or immobile, could not have been interested in participating in the study as it could have been too big an effort for them, either psychologically or physically. Hence, the findings cannot be generalised to all patients with advanced COPD.

The sample size (n=22) was large enough for no new themes to emerge. As the final sample size was determined based on data saturation, further data collection was considered unnecessary. Although the sample size was sufficient for this mixed methods concurrent study, a more diverse sample, including participants from other services or regions, could be informative.

In the sample, there was one outlier, a male from hospice. He was the only male representative from the hospice group. Even though he scored the highest in HADS (34) and lowest in MQOL-R (1.7), he was not removed from the study because it was not an exclusion criterium. Although he may have skewed results in some respects, particularly when comparing females and males, this participant provided a rich, unique narrative in the interview and his characteristics, such as not having a carer, were unique against all the sample. Consequently, based on the chosen embedded mixed methods design, the priority was the qualitative arm of the study while the quantitative strand was supplementary.

Finally, in the case of two participants, there was a lapse of time between the questionnaire completion and the interview. However, this was carried out according to the wishes of the participants, respecting their needs and being person-centred.

5.8. Conclusion

Palliative care is beneficial for patients with advanced COPD and it is recommended to be implemented from the early stages of the disease to help them develop disease self-management. Early introduction to palliative care and education positively affected patients' self-management abilities, which were crucial considering the progressive and

chronic nature of the disease. Having developed these abilities after the diagnosis helped patients' self-management in more advanced stages of COPD.

People with COPD live with a high psychological burden, low QOL and some factors can improve their living experience with this disease, such as a positive attitude and empathy from healthcare workers. It was essential for the patients to feel understood and have their needs addressed in their care. Moreover, patients' good understanding of the disease was a crucial factor, which further affected the development of coping strategies, and it points to the importance of introducing education in the early stages of the disease. Carers' awareness of the disease burden and their involvement in the care played an essential role in supporting patients. Their engagement in the care of patients should be encouraged and promoted. Therefore, healthcare providers' skilled communication, good information provision, and education are essential in improving patients' and carers' involvement in care, which is critical in developing confident disease self-management.

Interventions which enabled social interactions helped patients normalise their experiences, positively affecting their psychological distress and providing them with opportunities to have a social life. Likewise, attending palliative care services, receiving regular support, and personalised care were beneficial for patients in terms of being satisfied with care, maintaining QOL and diminishing their psychological burden.

5.9. Practice Implications

The findings of this study produced several important implications for future practice. The principles of the BPS model of care should be considered in order to redesign palliative care services for patients with COPD. This study has demonstrated clear associations

between biological, psychological and social aspects of living with advanced COPD. The person-centred approach should be encouraged and none of these aspects should be overlooked in the care of these patients. Addressing the BPS framework could produce beneficial consequences in improving self-management of physical symptoms and decreasing psychological distress.

To fulfil palliative care needs in the population with COPD and subsequently diminish both life and death anxiety, efforts should be made in order to gain deeper insight into this field. Moreover, education for patients should be available to provide them with knowledge about their condition and treatment options, improve their self-management, and help diminish apparent vulnerability. There is, therefore, a definite need for action in developing psychosocial support and early education, which may positively affect patients' action strategies, that is, developing coping strategies such as trying to live every day to the degree that their physical abilities allow.

The findings support strong recommendations to integrate informal carers, such as spouses, children or others being primary support in care, in the early stages of the disease and provide them with guidance from healthcare personnel in order to enhance their capability in the patient's support system. This information can be used to develop targeted interventions aimed at carers' participation in patients' care.

Current reports advocate that the efficacy of palliative care in symptom control should be known to all COPD clinicians and implemented in their work (GOLD, 2022). Over the course of the last decade, there has been a steady rise in the use of palliative care, indicating a shift in awareness and utilisation of palliative care in COPD (Halpin, 2018).

Another important practical implication of this study is that patients should be referred to palliative care services early in the diagnosis in order to facilitate self-management and diminish psychological distress. Furthermore, early palliative care from diagnosis should be more available, as early intervention would bring more benefits than introducing palliative care at advanced stages. Group pulmonary rehabilitation or support groups could bring social benefits at any stage, including advanced COPD. Additionally, therapies such as relaxation or massages could considerably relieve muscle stress or pain.

5.10. Directions for Further Research

Diverse models of care are available for people with advanced COPD. Nevertheless, it is unknown which is the most suited to manage psychological and social burdens and improve QOL. More research exploring psychological distress is advised. Namely, it would be recommended to explore the role of socioeconomic factors, such as social deprivation, both in the QOL and in psychological distress. Further investigations are needed to estimate the possible impact of non-pharmacological interventions recognised by GOLD (2022), such as psychotherapy, counselling, self-help groups, self-management programmes, relaxation, music therapy, and pulmonary rehabilitation for people with advanced COPD attending palliative care services. By applying quantitative findings and supplementing the participants' voices, this study indicated that psychological distress affects the QOL of people with advanced COPD. Anxiety and approaching death are rarely addressed in COPD care, and patients often are left alone to cope with their burden. That is why various examples of service provision should be considered for this underserved population. Team-centred and person-centred

approaches may enhance the quality of patients' information about their disease and help them understand and accept their condition, therefore improving patients' self-management.

For this reason, to give strong evidence about the most advantageous structure of palliative care services for people with COPD, well-planned investigations examining the relation between dynamic components and patient-focused outcomes are required. Another possible future research would be identifying the most suitable time to refer patients with COPD to palliative care. Patients who attended specialist palliative care in this study had lower scores of QOL and higher psychological distress than those who received generalist palliative care. People with COPD are underrepresented in specialist palliative care and more research is required about people attending this service. Due to the small number of people with COPD in specialist palliative care services, such as day hospice, conducting a nationwide study is suggested so as to recruit a sample which would allow running more quantitative analysis about factors affecting the psychological burden.

Likewise, it would be valuable to conduct more qualitative studies to explore the perspectives of caregivers and professionals in specialist palliative care with a view to broadening early palliative care administration for people with COPD. Further research is needed on the specifics of carers and the quality of the patient-caregiver relationship and its effect on the quality of care provided to people with advanced COPD.

5.11. Reflection

I recognise that this study was conducted before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. People with COPD are considered a high-risk group, and therefore I expect that the psychosocial burden of these patients increased due to pandemic restrictions, overall social isolation and fear of being infected. However, the COVID-19 pandemic caused an increased focus on respiratory care, resulting in enhanced remote access and monitoring, and more accessible home visits. It also supported the effective implementation of digitally enabled pathways which may suit a proportion of patients. In the light of the recent developments in care of respiratory medicine, this study is timely and has a potential to further improve the care of people with advanced COPD.

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Appendix 1: Ethics Approval from UWS

17/01/2019 (Dr WG Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear Barbara Goncalves,

You may now proceed to submit your application 6463: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease of those attending two different models of palliative care services., 5061 to IRAS. Before you do, please ensure that you deal with the change request detailed below.

Title	Comment
Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application	Change request: Please note you have a correction needed in the letter of invite to participants. There is content within brackets that does not make sense.

Personal details
withheld.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 2: Ethics Approval from NHS

Health Research Authority

London – Stanmore Research Ethics Committee

Health Research Authority
Skipton House
80 London Road
London
SE1 6LH

Telephone: 020 7972 2561

17 April 2019

Dr Caroline Sime
Stephenson Place Hamilton International Technology Park South Lanarkshire
School of Health and Life Sciences,
UWS Lanarkshire Campus
G72 0LH

Dear Dr Sime

Study title:	Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care services.
REC reference:	19/LO/0383
Protocol number:	not applicable
IRAS project ID:	255972

Thank you for your letter of 17 April 2019 responding to the Proportionate Review Sub-Committee's request for changes to the documentation for the above study.

The revised documentation has been reviewed and approved by the sub-committee.

We plan to publish your research summary wording for the above study on the HRA website, together with your contact details. Publication will be no earlier than three months from the date of this favourable opinion letter. The expectation is that this information will be published for all studies that receive an ethical opinion but should you wish to provide a substitute contact point, wish to make a request to defer, or require further information, please contact please contact hra.studyregistration@nhs.net outlining the reasons for your request.

Under very limited circumstances (e.g. for student research which has received an unfavourable opinion), it may be possible to grant an exemption to the publication of the study.

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation as revised.

Conditions of the favourable opinion

The REC favourable opinion is subject to the following conditions being met prior to the start of the study.

Management permission must be obtained from each host organisation prior to the start of the study at the site concerned.

Management permission should be sought from all NHS organisations involved in the study in accordance with NHS research governance arrangements. Each NHS organisation must confirm through the signing of agreements and/or other documents that it has given permission for the research to proceed (except where explicitly specified otherwise).

Guidance on applying for HRA and HCRW Approval (England and Wales)/ NHS permission for research is available in the Integrated Research Application System, at www.hra.nhs.uk or at <http://www.rdforum.nhs.uk>.

Where a NHS organisation's role in the study is limited to identifying and referring potential participants to research sites ("participant identification centre"), guidance should be sought from the R&D office on the information it requires to give permission for this activity.

For non-NHS sites, site management permission should be obtained in accordance with the procedures of the relevant host organisation.

Sponsors are not required to notify the Committee of management permissions from host organisations.

Registration of Clinical Trials

All clinical trials (defined as the first four categories on the IRAS filter page) must be registered on a publicly accessible database. This should be before the first participant is recruited but no later than 6 weeks after recruitment of the first participant.

There is no requirement to separately notify the REC but you should do so at the earliest opportunity e.g. when submitting an amendment. We will audit the registration details as part of the annual progress reporting process.

To ensure transparency in research, we strongly recommend that all research is registered but for non-clinical trials this is not currently mandatory.

If a sponsor wishes to request a deferral for study registration within the required timeframe, they should contact hra.studyregistration@nhs.net. The expectation is that all clinical trials will be registered, however, in exceptional circumstances non registration may be permissible with prior agreement from the HRA. Guidance on where to register is provided on the HRA website.

It is the responsibility of the sponsor to ensure that all the conditions are complied with before the start of the study or its initiation at a particular site (as applicable).

Ethical review of research sites

The favourable opinion applies to all NHS sites taking part in the study, subject to management permission being obtained from the NHS/HSC R&D office prior to the start of the study (see "Conditions of the favourable opinion" above).

Approved documents

The documents reviewed and approved by the Committee are:

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Confirmation of any other Regulatory Approvals (e.g. CAG) and all correspondence [Letter from UWS ethics]	1	17 January 2019
Confirmation of any other Regulatory Approvals (e.g. CAG) and all correspondence [Marie Curie Hospice letter]		
Confirmation of any other Regulatory Approvals (e.g. CAG) and all correspondence [GDPR certificate]	1	28 January 2019
Confirmation of any other Regulatory Approvals (e.g. CAG) and all correspondence [Letter from the director of studies]	1	11 February 2019
Confirmation of any other Regulatory Approvals (e.g. CAG) and all correspondence [e-mail from the sponsor William Gordon MacKay]	1	12 February 2019
Covering letter on headed paper [Changes in ethics submission]	1	27 March 2019
Evidence of Sponsor insurance or indemnity (non NHS Sponsors only) [Insurance]	1	25 January 2019
GP/consultant information sheets or letters [GP notification letter]	1	05 March 2019
Interview schedules or topic guides for participants [Interview schedule]	2	05 March 2019
Interview schedules or topic guides for participants [Interview schedule highlighted]	2	05 March 2019
IRAS Application Form [IRAS_Form_13022019]		13 February 2019
IRAS Application Form [IRAS_Form_09042019]		09 April 2019
IRAS Application Form XML file [IRAS_Form_09042019]		09 April 2019
IRAS Checklist XML [Checklist_09042019]		09 April 2019
Letter from sponsor	1	17 January 2019
Letters of invitation to participant [Letter of invitation]	3	05 March 2019
Letters of invitation to participant [Letter of invitation highlighted]	3	05 March 2019
Non-validated questionnaire [Demographics questionnaire]	2	28 January 2019
Other [Cover letter in response to further information requested]		
Participant consent form [Consent form]	5	05 March 2019
Participant consent form [Consent form version 5 highlighted]	5	05 March 2019
Participant consent form [Consent form]	6	05 March 2019
Participant consent form [Consent form version 6 highlighted]	6	05 March 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant Information sheet 8]	8	30 January 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant Information sheet 9]	9	30 January 2019

Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant debrief sheet 4]	4	28 January 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant debrief sheet 5]	5	28 January 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant debrief sheet 6]	6	28 January 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Privacy Notice]	1	28 January 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant Information sheet 12]	12	18 March 2019
Participant information sheet (PIS) [Participant debrief sheet 7 highlighted]	5	05 March 2019
Research protocol or project proposal [Research proposal]	4	12 March 2019
Research protocol or project proposal [Research proposal]	5	01 April 2019
Summary CV for Chief Investigator (CI) [CV Barbara Gonçalves]	1	28 January 2019
Summary CV for student [CV Barbara Gonçalves]	1	28 January 2019
Summary CV for supervisor (student research) [CV Caroline Sime]	1	28 January 2019
Summary CV for supervisor (student research) [CV Eileen Harkess-Murphy]	1	28 January 2019
Summary CV for supervisor (student research) [CV Joanne Lusher]	1	28 January 2019
Validated questionnaire [Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale]	1	28 January 2019
Validated questionnaire [McGill Quality of Life- Revised]	1	28 January 2019

Statement of compliance

The Committee is constituted in accordance with the Governance Arrangements for Research Ethics Committees and complies fully with the Standard Operating Procedures for Research Ethics Committees in the UK.

After ethical review

Reporting requirements

The attached document "After ethical review – guidance for researchers" gives detailed guidance on reporting requirements for studies with a favourable opinion, including:

- Notifying substantial amendments
- Adding new sites and investigators
- Notification of serious breaches of the protocol
- Progress and safety reports
- Notifying the end of the study

The HRA website also provides guidance on these topics, which is updated in the light of changes in reporting requirements or procedures.

Feedback

You are invited to give your view of the service that you have received from the Research Ethics Service and the application procedure. If you wish to make your views known please use the feedback form available on the HRA website: <http://www.hra.nhs.uk/about-the-hra/governance/quality-assurance>

HRA Learning

We are pleased to welcome researchers and research staff to our HRA Learning Events and online learning opportunities– see details at: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/learning/>

19/LO/0383

Please quote this number on all correspondence

With the Committee's best wishes for the success of this project.

Personal details withheld.

Enclosures: *"After ethical review – guidance for researchers"*

Copy to: *Mrs Barbara Goncalves*

Appendix 3: Research Passport

Personal details withheld. Pages 254 - 259 redacted. Original document is a completed research passport form.

Appendix 4: R&D Greater Glasgow and Clyde

Personal details withheld.

13 May 2019

Mrs Barbara Gonçalves
University of the West of Scotland
School of Health & Life Sciences
UWS Lanarkshire Campus
Stephenson Place
Hmailton Int Tech Park
South Lanarkshire G72 0LH

Dear Mrs B Gonçalves,

Letter of Access for Research

This letter confirms your right of access to conduct research through **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde** for the purpose and on the terms and conditions set out below. This right of access commences on **13/05/2019** and ends on **31/01/2020** unless terminated earlier in accordance with the clauses below.

You have a right of access to conduct such research as confirmed in writing in the letter of permission for research from this NHS organisation. Please note that you cannot start the research until the Principal Investigator for the research project has received a letter from us giving permission to conduct the project.

The information supplied about your role in research at **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde** has been reviewed and you do not require an honorary research contract with this NHS organisation. We are satisfied that such pre-engagement checks as we consider necessary have been carried out.

You are considered to be a legal visitor to **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde** premises. You are not entitled to any form of payment or access to other benefits provided by this NHS organisation to employees and this letter does not give rise to any other relationship between you and this NHS organisation, in particular that of an employee.

While undertaking research through **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde**, you will remain accountable to your employer **the University of the West of Scotland** but you are required to follow the reasonable instructions of **Dr Ewen Ross** in this NHS organisation or those given on her/his behalf in relation to the terms of this right of access.

Where any third party claim is made, whether or not legal proceedings are issued, arising out of or in connection with your right of access, you are required to co-operate fully with any investigation by this NHS organisation in connection with any such claim and to give all such assistance as may reasonably be required regarding the conduct of any legal proceedings.

You must act in accordance with **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde** policies and procedures, which are available to you upon request, and the Research Governance Framework.

You are required to co-operate with **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde** in discharging its duties under the Health and Safety at Work etc Act 1974 and other health and safety legislation and to take reasonable care

for the health and safety of yourself and others while on **NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde** premises. You must observe the same standards of care and propriety in dealing with patients, staff, visitors, equipment and premises as is expected of any other contract holder and you must act appropriately, responsibly and professionally at all times.

If you have a physical or mental health condition or disability which may affect your research role and which might require special adjustments to your role, if you have not already done so, you must notify your employer and the health board's HR department prior to commencing your research role at the Health board.

You are required to ensure that all information regarding patients or staff remains secure and *strictly confidential* at all times. You must ensure that you understand and comply with the requirements of the NHS Confidentiality Code of Practice (<http://www.dh.gov.uk/assetRoot/04/06/92/54/04069254.pdf>) and the Data Protection Act 1998. Furthermore you should be aware that under the Act, unauthorised disclosure of information is an offence and such disclosures may lead to prosecution.

You should ensure that, where you are issued with an identity or security card, a bleep number, email or library account, keys or protective clothing, these are returned upon termination of this arrangement. Please also ensure that while on the premises you wear your ID badge at all times, or are able to prove your identity if challenged. Please note that this NHS organisation accepts no responsibility for damage to or loss of personal property.

We may terminate your right to attend at any time either by giving seven days' written notice to you or immediately without any notice if you are in breach of any of the terms or conditions described in this letter or if you commit any act that we reasonably consider to amount to serious misconduct or to be disruptive and/or prejudicial to the interests and/or business of this NHS organisation or if you are convicted of any criminal offence. You must not undertake regulated activity if you are barred from such work. If you are barred from working with adults or children this letter of access is immediately terminated. Your employer will immediately withdraw you from undertaking this or any other regulated activity and you **MUST** stop undertaking any regulated activity immediately.

Your substantive employer is responsible for your conduct during this research project and may in the circumstances described above instigate disciplinary action against you.

NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde will not indemnify you against any liability incurred as a result of any breach of confidentiality or breach of the Data Protection Act 1998. Any breach of the Data Protection Act 1998 may result in legal action against you and/or your substantive employer.

If your current role or involvement in research changes, or any of the information provided in your Research Passport changes, you must inform your employer through their normal procedures. You must also inform your nominated manager in this NHS organisation.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 5: R&D Lanarkshire

Personal details
withheld.

Dear Dr Sime

Project title: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care services

R&D ID: L19038

NRS ID Number: NRS19/255972

I am writing to you as Chief Investigator of the above study to advise that R&D Management approval has been granted for the conduct of your study within NHS Lanarkshire as detailed below:

NAME	TITLE	ROLE	NHSL SITE TO WHICH APPROVAL APPLIES
Dr Sally Boa	Head of Palliative Care Education	Local Contact	Strathcarron Hospice

For the study to be carried out you are subject to the following conditions:

Conditions

- You are required to comply with Good Clinical Practice, Ethics Guidelines, Health & Safety Act 1999 and relevant UK and EU Data Protection legislation.
- The research is carried out in accordance with the Scottish Executive's Research Governance Framework for Health and Community Care (copy available via the Chief Scientist Office website:

<http://www.cso.scot.nhs.uk/> or the Research & Development Intranet site: <http://firstport2/staff-support/research-and-development/default.aspx>

- You must ensure that all confidential information is maintained in secure storage. You are further obligated under this agreement to report to the NHS Lanarkshire Data Protection Office and the Research & Development Office infringements, either by accident or otherwise, which constitutes a breach of confidentiality.
- Clinical trial agreements (if applicable), or any other agreements in relation to the study, have been signed off by all relevant signatories.
- You must contact the Lead Nation Coordinating Centre if/when the project is subject to any minor or substantial amendments so that these can be appropriately assessed, and approved, where necessary.
- You notify the R&D Department if any additional researchers become involved in the project within NHS Lanarkshire
- You notify the R&D Department when you have completed your research, or if you decide to terminate it prematurely.
- You must send brief annual reports followed by a final report and summary to the R&D office in hard copy and electronic formats as well as any publications.
- If the research involves any investigators who are not employed by NHS Lanarkshire, but who will be dealing with NHS Lanarkshire patients, there may be a requirement for an SCRO check and occupational health assessment. If this is the case then please contact the R&D Department to make arrangements for this to be undertaken and an honorary contract issued.

I trust these conditions are acceptable to you.

Yours sincerely,

Personal details withheld.

PERIOD of ACCESS	
From: 20.06.19	To: 30.11.19

DECLARATIONS / SIGNATURES

1. EMPLOYER / PLACE OF STUDY REPRESENTATIVE (e.g. Line Manager / HR Department representative)

- I confirm that the necessary pre-engagement checks have been carried out, are satisfactory, and that the Researcher is suitably trained and experienced to undertake the duties associated with the research activities outlined in their Research Passport Application.
- As the Representative of the Researcher's Employer I confirm that we retain responsibility for ensuring that the Researcher has appropriate Occupational Health Clearance for the research activities that they will undertake within NHS Lanarkshire, including, but not limited to, appropriate immunisation. Health clearance has been undertaken in line with Scottish Government Health Clearance document - Health Clearance for Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV for New Healthcare Workers with Direct Clinical Contact with Patients (2008) / or where relevant; Department of Health England Health Clearance document - Health Clearance for Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV: new healthcare workers (2007). Immunisation screening has been undertaken in line with Immunisation against Infectious Disease – The Green Book (2013).
- As the Representative of the Researcher's Employer I agree that we will inform **NHS Lanarkshire** if we become aware of any issues that impact on their suitability or ability to carry out their agreed research activities within **NHS Lanarkshire**. This includes, but is not limited to, situations where PVG Scheme/Disclosure Scotland/CRB Disclosure vetting information suggests that the Researcher may have become unsuitable to do regulated work.
- I confirm that we retain full responsibility for ensuring compliance with all applicable clauses in the attached Letter of Access, and in particular for ensuring that your **Employee** is aware of, and agrees to comply with the terms contained therein.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 6: R&D Forth Valley

Dear Dr Sime

Study title: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care services
NRES number: 11/LO/0383

Following the favourable opinion from the London-Stanmore Research Ethics Committee on 17 April 2019, I am pleased to confirm that I formally gave Management Approval to the study above on 03 July 2019.

I note that this study will take place in Strathcarron Hospice and there is therefore no cost or activity within NHS Forth Valley itself.

This approval is granted subject to your compliance with the following:

1. Any amendments to the protocol or research team must have Ethics Committee and R&D approval (as well as approval from any other relevant regulatory organisation) before they can be implemented. Please ensure that the R&D Office and (where appropriate) NRS are informed of any amendments as soon as you become aware of them.
2. You and any local Principal Investigator are responsible for ensuring that all members of the research team have the appropriate experience and training, including GCP training if required.
3. If someone working within NHS Forth Valley is recruiting participants, those figures **MUST** be recorded on the EDGE research management system. If you have not used EDGE before, you should already have been offered training on the system. If recruitment is all being handled outside Forth Valley, you will be contacted monthly for the latest recruitment figures.
3. All those involved in the project will be required to work within accepted guidelines of health and safety and data protection principles, any other relevant statutory legislation, UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care Research and IHC-GCP guidelines. A copy of the Framework can be accessed at: http://www.nhsresearchscotland.org.uk/uploads/tiny_mce/uk-policy-framework-health-social-care-research%20v1.1.pdf and ICH-GCP guidelines may be found at <http://www.ich.org/LOB/media/MEDIA482.pdf>

Personal details withheld.

4. As custodian of the information collected during this project you are responsible for ensuring the security of all personal information collected in line with NHS Scotland IT security policies, until the destruction of this data.

5. You or the local Principal Investigator will be required to provide the following reports and information during the course of your study:

- A progress report **annually**
- Report on SAEs and SUSARs if your study is a Clinical Trial of an Investigational Medicinal Product
- Any information required for the purpose of internal or external audit and monitoring
- Copies of any external monitoring reports
- Notification of the end of recruitment and the end of the study
- A copy of the final report, when available.
- Copies of or full citations for any publications or abstracts

The appropriate forms will be provided to you by the Research and Development office when they are needed. Other information may be required from time to time.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Continued

Appendix 7: Demographics Questionnaire

Version 2, 28/01/2019

Demographics questionnaire

Project Title: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) on those attending two different models of palliative care services.

Barbara Gonçalves (PhD Student),

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland Lanarkshire Campus, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire G72 0LH
Telephone: 01698 283100 Extension 8311, Email: barbara.goncalves@uws.ac.uk

Participant's number (filled by the investigator):

Please answer the questions:

1. Gender – are you: (please circle)

- a) Male
- b) Female

2. What is your age:

3. What is your marital status? (please circle)

- a) Married/partnership
- b) Single
- c) Divorced/separated
- d) Widowed
- e) Other (please specify _____)
- f) Prefer not to say

4. How would you describe your current employment status? (please circle)

- a) Employed
- b) Self-employed
- c) Retired
- d) Unemployed
- e) Other (please specify _____)
- f) Prefer not to say

5. How would you describe your current smoking status? (please circle)

- a) Active smoker
- b) Ex-smoker
- c) Never smoked
- d) Other (please specify _____)
- e) Prefer not to say

Please turn the page

Page 1 from 2

Version 2, 28/01/2019

6. What is your level of education? (please circle)

- a) Primary
- b) Secondary
- c) Vocational
- d) Higher
- e) Other (please specify _____)
- f) Prefer not to say

**7. Who would you describe as your main support in everyday activities?
(please circle more than one answer, if appropriate)**

- a) spouse
- b) children
- c) siblings
- d) grandchildren
- e) neighbours/friends
- f) someone else
- g) no one
- h) Other (please specify _____)
- i) Prefer not to say

**8. What therapies if any, from the list below do you or have you experienced?
(please circle more than one answer, if appropriate)**

- a) Group pulmonary rehabilitation
- b) Individual pulmonary rehabilitation
- c) Self-management programmes
- d) Self-help group
- e) Relaxation therapy
- f) Psychological therapy (if you know what therapy, please specify _____)
- g) None of above
- h) Other (please specify _____)

9. Are you currently taking any medications?

- a) Yes (please specify _____)
- b) No
- c) Prefer not to say

Appendix 8: McGill Quality of Life – Revised Questionnaire

McGILL QUALITY OF LIFE QUESTIONNAIRE Revised[©]

Instructions

This questionnaire contains statements that are each followed by two opposite answers. Numbers extend from one extreme answer to its opposite. Please circle the number between 0 and 10 which is most true for you. There are no right or wrong answers. Completely honest answers will be most helpful.

EXAMPLE:

I am hungry:

not at all	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	extremely
------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-----------

- If you are not even a little bit hungry, you would circle 0.
- If you are a little hungry (you just finished a meal but still have room for dessert), you might circle a 1, 2, or 3.
- If you are feeling moderately hungry (because mealtime is approaching), you might circle a 4, 5, or 6.
- If you are very hungry (because you haven't eaten all day), you might circle a 7, 8, or 9.
- If you are extremely hungry, you would circle 10.

START

Please answer for how you have been feeling **JUST IN THE PAST TWO (2) DAYS**.

PART A Overall Quality of Life

A. Considering all parts of my life (for example, physical, emotional, social, spiritual, and financial) over the past two days (48 hours) the quality of my life was:

very bad	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	excellent
----------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-----------

Please continue on the next page...

PART B Physical

1. Over the past two days (48 hours) my physical symptoms (such as pain, nausea, tiredness and others) were: *

not a problem	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a tremendous problem
----------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-----------------------------

**If, over the past two days, you had no physical symptoms or problems, please circle '0 - not a problem' and go to statement # 2.*

Please list the physical symptoms that were a problem (please write clearly).

List:

2. Over the past two days (48 hours) I felt:

physically terrible	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	physically well
----------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	------------------------

3. Over the past two days (48 hours), being physically unable to do the things I wanted was:

not a problem	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a tremendous problem
----------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-----------------------------

Please continue on the next page...

PART C *Feelings and thoughts*

4. Over the past two days (48 hours), I was depressed:

not at all	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	extremely
-------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	------------------

5. Over the past two days (48 hours), I was nervous or worried:

not at all	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	extremely
-------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	------------------

6. Over the past two days (48 hours), I felt sad:

never	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	always
--------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	---------------

7. Over the past two days (48 hours), when I thought of the future, I was:

not afraid	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	terrified
-------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	------------------

8. Over the past two days (48 hours), my life was:

utterly meaningless and without purpose	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	very purposeful and meaningful
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	---

9. When I think about my whole life, I feel that in achieving life goals I have:

made no progress whatsoever	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	progressed to complete fulfillment
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	---

Please continue on the next page...

10. Over the past two days (48 hours), I felt that the amount of control I had over my life was:

not a problem	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a tremendous problem
----------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-----------------------------

11. Over the past two days (48 hours), I felt good about myself as a person.

completely disagree	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	completely agree
----------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-------------------------

PART D Social

12. Over the past two days (48 hours) communication with the people I care about was:

difficult	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	very easy
------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	------------------

13. Over the past two days (48 hours) I felt my relationships with the people I care about were:

more distant than I would like	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	very close
---------------------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-------------------

14. Over the past two days (48 hours), I felt supported:

not at all	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	completely
-------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	-------------------

Thank you very much.

Appendix 9: Permission the author of the McGill Quality of Life – Revised

Monday, July 5, 2021 at 22:36:19 British Summer Time

Subject: MQOL-R and original MQOL
Date: Thursday, March 22, 2018 at 12:19:38 AM Greenwich Mean Time
From: Robin Cohen, Dr.
To: Barbara Goncalves
Attachments: MQOL-R.pdf, MQOL and MQOL-R Explanation and Scoring Apr 4 2017.pdf, Cohen Sawatzky et al MQOL-R Palliat Med-2017.pdf, MQOL and MQOL-R user form.docx, MQOL original.pdf

Hello.

Thank you for your interest in MQOL-R and/or MQOL. We have recently created a revised version, MQOL-R, which I suggest you use. However, if you want to use the original it is also attached. A brief explanation about MQOL-R and MQOL, along with instructions for scoring, is attached.

I have attached the article for MQOL-R.

Please complete the attached "user form" and return to me. If you are using the questionnaire for coursework and don't intend to publish a study, or for a literature review, there is no need to complete the form.

If you are interested in our measure of the quality of life of family caregivers, The **Quality Of Life in Life-Threatening Illness -Family caregiver Questionnaire (QOLLI-F)**, please let me know.

I wish you good luck with your project.

Take care,

Robin

Personal details
withheld.

Appendix 10: Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale Questionnaire

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS)

Name: _____ Date: _____

FOLD HERE

Clinicians are aware that emotions play an important part in most illnesses. If your clinician knows about these feelings he or she will be able to help you more.

This questionnaire is designed to help your clinician to know how you feel. Read each item below and **underline the reply** which comes closest to how you have been feeling in the past week. Ignore the numbers printed at the edge of the questionnaire.

Don't take too long over your replies, your immediate reaction to each item will probably be more accurate than a long, thought-out response.

FOLD HERE

	A	D			A	D
			I feel tense or 'wound up'	I feel as if I am slowed down		
	3		Most of the time	Nearly all the time		3
	2		A lot of the time	Very often		2
	1		From time to time, occasionally	Sometimes		1
	0		Not at all	Not at all		0
		0	I still enjoy the things I used to enjoy	I get a sort of frightened feeling like 'butterflies' in the stomach		
		1	Definitely as much	Not at all		0
		2	Not quite so much	Occasionally		1
		3	Only a little	Quite often		2
			Hardly at all	Very often		3
			I get a sort of frightened feeling as if something awful is about to happen	I have lost interest in my appearance		
	3		Very definitely and quite badly	Definitely		3
	2		Yes, but not too badly	I don't take as much care as I should		2
	1		A little, but it doesn't worry me	I may not take quite as much care		1
	0		Not at all	I take just as much care as ever		0
		0	I can laugh and see the funny side of things	I feel restless as if I have to be on the move		
		1	As much as I always could	Very much indeed		3
		2	Not quite so much now	Quite a lot		2
		3	Definitely not so much now	Not very much		1
			Not at all	Not at all		0
			Worrying thoughts go through my mind	I look forward with enjoyment to things		
	3		A great deal of the time	As much as I ever did		0
	2		A lot of the time	Rather less than I used to		1
	1		Not too often	Definitely less than I used to		2
	0		Very little	Hardly at all		3
		3	I feel cheerful	I get sudden feelings of panic		
		2	Never	Very often indeed		3
		1	Not often	Quite often		2
		0	Sometimes	Not very often		1
			Most of the time	Not at all		0
		0	I can sit at ease and feel relaxed	I can enjoy a good book or radio or television programme		
		1	Definitely	Often		0
		2	Usually	Sometimes		1
		3	Not often	Not often		2
			Not at all	Very seldom		3

Now check that you have answered all the questions

	A	D
TOTAL		

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Agreement Dated : 04/12/2018.....

1. LICENSEE'S NAME *Please type all details and send back as Word doc attachment*

LICENSEE : : Barbara Gonçalves (note 1)

Address : School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland Lanarkshire Campus, Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire, G72 0LH

Country : United Kingdom

VAT Number (if applicable) : (note 2)

Contact Name if Different from above:

Name :

2. CONTEXT OF HADS USE

PROJECT (note 6): ... Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD).

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	<p>If you require a purchase order number, study number, anything in particular to appear on the invoice in order to get it processed, please include the information in this line.</p> <p>The invoice can not be sent elsewhere/changed once it has been created.</p> <p>All payments must be made in £ sterling by credit card or cheque drawn on a UK bank or sterling funds transferred directly to the GL Assessment bank account – details of which will be included on the invoice.</p> <p>For payment enquiries ONLY please contact Credit Control Email: Credit_Control@gl-assessment.co.uk (UK) 0330 1235375 (International) +44 1793 516316 For all other enquiries please email: permissions@gl-assessment.co.uk</p>
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<p>Note 5. University Course and Supervisor's Name/Supervisor's GL Reader Code. / qualification code</p>	<p>Complete only if you are an undergraduate student and not qualified to register with GL Assessment yourself. Your supervisor must register and sign an agreement on your behalf.</p>
<p>Note 6. Details of project</p>	<p>Ensure you include study title, project title, name of study group.</p>
<p>Note 7. Total number of Administrations</p>	<p>Administrations mean the number of times the scale is to be used not the number of participants in the study i.e. test to be administered 3 times to 50 participants = 150 administrations.</p> <p>If the study is international it should include the total number of administrations, whatever number of countries/languages involved (excluding those administered in the German language; see below).</p>
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Appendix 12: Interview Schedule

Interview schedule

Understanding the diagnosis and everyday life

- Can you please tell me what a typical day is like for you living with COPD?
- Can you tell me what symptoms you experience during a normal day?
- What do you understand about your illness?

Social life and relationships

- How would you describe your social life lately?
- Could you tell me how the disease has influenced your social life (for example contact with relatives, friends)?
- What do you do to make yourself feel better?
- What do you think could be done in order to change and improve your social life?

Psychological needs

- How would you describe mood recently?
- How does living with COPD affect your mood and emotions?
- If you experience periods of anxiety, how do you manage it?
- Do you receive any psychological and social support? If yes, could you please describe what support is it?
- How would you describe the support that you receive and your satisfaction with it?
- Do you have some suggestions that could be done in order to change and improve your mood and emotions?

Experience and satisfaction from the healthcare service

- Who helps you decide on what treatment and care you want to have?
- What decisions have you made about your treatment and care?
- What brought you to the hospice/hospital (asked appropriately)? Could you please detail the process that led you to this service?
- What suggestions could you make to improve the process?
- What do you think about the service that is being provided to you?

Version 2, 05/03/2019

- Is there any type of therapy or treatment that you feel that helps you the most to feel better?
- What professionals would you consider help you the most?

Needs of patients

- What do you feel is the most important thing in helping you to feel supported when you have COPD?
- How would you describe your satisfaction with the support provided by the service that you attend?
- Do you feel you have been given enough information about your illness? If you had any questions about your disease, who would you think could answer them?

Extra information

- Is there anything else you would like to add about the care you receive?
- Is there anything else you would like to add about the study?

Appendix 13: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Personal details withheld.

Project: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care.

You are being invited to take part in a research study run and funded by the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Before you decide to participate in this study, it is essential that you understand why the research is being carried out and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and ask the research student if there is anything that is not clear or you need more information.

What is the purpose of the study?

Daily life for people living with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) may include living with many symptoms that may reduce their ability to take part in physical and social activities, which may lead to social and well-being difficulties. We know that depending on where people with COPD live they may receive different healthcare services.

We are looking to explore the experience of patients with advanced COPD who receive care from a specialist respiratory clinic (hospital) and from a hospice and how this may reflect on their quality of life and emotional needs.

Why have I been chosen?

We have invited you to take part in this study as your healthcare team has identified you as having advanced COPD.

Do I have to take part?

No, your participation in this study is voluntary. If you decide not to participate, this will not affect your care now, or in the future. Even if you choose to participate now, you can change your mind at any time and withdraw from the study.

What will taking part involve?

Once you have had time to read this information and think it over, if you agree, your contact details will be passed on to the research student by your healthcare team. If you have received this information sheet in the post, there is a prepaid envelope to return your contact details indirectly to the student. On receiving your details, the research student who will phone you within 48 hours to ask if you would still like to participate. If so, a meeting will be arranged when the research student will go through this information sheet with you, and answer any questions you may have. If you still agree to participate, you will then be asked to sign a consent form.

The study is divided into two parts: questionnaires and interviews. You can choose if you want to take part at all, in one part or both. It will take around 10 to 20 minutes to complete the questionnaires and between 30 minutes to 1 hour for the interview. The interview will be audio recorded. During the course of taking part, if you start feeling unwell, the interview or questionnaire can be stopped at any moment, ended or rescheduled.

Benefits

There will be no direct benefit to you for your participation in this study. However, it is hoped that the information obtained from this study may impact the future development of healthcare services offered to people living with advanced COPD.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

No risks are expected in this research.

Will my details be kept confidential?

Yes, all information obtained from you will be kept strictly confidential. You will be assigned a unique identifier that will be used later in the study so no identifying information will be used.

Involvement of your medical team

The clinician responsible for your care has reviewed details of the study and agreed for us to ask if you would like to take part. Your medical team will not be involved in any further part of this study. With your consent, your GP will be informed about your participation.

What if there is a problem?

If you have any concerns about any aspect of this study, you should ask to speak to the research student who will do their best to answer your questions. If you remain unhappy and wish to complain formally, you can do this by the standard NHS Complain Procedure (NHS helpline 0800224488). If participation in this study causes you any feelings of anxiety or distress, you may wish to contact your medical team or the British Lung Foundation helpline 03000030555. Alternatively, you can send an e-mail for support through the form on the website www.blf.org.uk/support-for-you/helpline.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

At the end of the study, results will be published in a PhD dissertation and a scientific journal. Key findings will also be made available to you once the study is completed, through the service you attend. No personal information will be used in any publications or reports.

Who has reviewed the study?

All research in the NHS is looked by the independent group of people, called a Research Ethics Committee, to protect your interests. This study has been reviewed and passed by the University of the West of Scotland's Ethics Committee, and the NHS London-Stanmore Research Ethics Committee (Reference: 19/LO/0383).

Who can I contact for more information?

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for your time.

Page 2 of 2

Version 12, 18/03/2019

Appendix 14: Lone Worker Procedure

POLICY TITLE		
LONE WORKER PROCEDURE		
DOCUMENT AUTHOR AND DEPARTMENT		POLICY OWNER
James McDonald Head of Health and Safety Services		Donna McMillan Secretary to Court
APPROVING BODY		DATE OF APPROVAL
Health, Safety & Sustainability Committee		October 2015
REVIEW DATE	POLICY NUMBER	VERSION NUMBER
		1
EITHER For public access online (internet)? <i>Tick as appropriate</i>		OR For staff access only (intranet)? <i>Tick as appropriate</i>
Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Impact on Other University Policies <i>Tick as appropriate</i>		If Yes – Please List
Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Who should be aware of this Policy?		Included within Central Induction Process?
All Staff		Yes

Lone Working Procedure

CONTENTS

1. Introduction
2. Scope of Procedure
3. Foundation in Policy
4. Procedure
5. Knowledge and Skills
6. Sustainability
7. Appendices

1. INTRODUCTION

- 1.1 The Health and Safety at Work etc Act 1974, Section 2, sets out a Duty of Care on employers to ensure the health, safety and welfare of employees whilst at work.
- 1.2 Although there is no specific legislation in respect of working alone, the Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999, Regulation 3, states that every employer shall make a suitable and sufficient assessment of the 'foreseeable' risks that employees might face in the course of their duties. Following risk assessment, control measures must be put in place to manage those risks.
- 1.3 Risk assessments must devise safe working arrangements for all workers considered to be lone workers. Special attention is required when assessing lone working as the risks inherent in such work are exacerbated by the lack of normal channels of support. Training is particularly important, as there will be no direct supervision of work. Monitoring procedures also need to be established to ensure that lone workers are following safe systems of work.

2. SCOPE OF PROCEDURE

- 2.1 This Procedure applies to all Schools and Departments of the University and applies on all campuses. It also applies to any activities of the University occurring in areas outside of the University; e.g. University Staff visits to other workplaces and field trips. The procedure also includes those situations where UWS staff and students are on overseas locations while on University Business.
- 2.2 This procedure applies to all staff, students and visitors to the University, including contractors as appropriate.

3. FOUNDATION IN POLICY

- 3.1 The University Health and Safety Policy: Organisation and Arrangements states as Section 4.2.2.1 that it will provide '....equipment and systems of work that are safe and without risks to health.... in the use of articles....'. This Lone Working Procedure expands on the Safety Policy in this area of risk.
- 3.2 The Health & Safety at Work Act 1974, the Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999, the Workplace (Health, Safety and Welfare) Regulations 1992 (as amended) and the Provision and Use of Work Equipment Regulations 1998 (as amended), to take reasonable care for their own health and safety, and to use correctly all work items in accordance with the training and instructions they receive to enable them to use the items safely.
- 3.3 The main tool to ensure compliance with the Health and Safety at Work etc Act 1974 and with this Procedure is the Lone Working Risk Assessment form. The requirement to carry out a suitable and sufficient of risk assessment is set out in the Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999. Compliance with this Procedure and the procedure below will assure staff of compliance with the University's Health and Safety Policy, and, that there is no breach of legislation and they are protected from the risk of harm when undertaking Lone Working activities.

4. PROCEDURE

- 4.1 The responsibility to ensure compliance with health and safety legislation and this Procedure rests with the University, the School/Support Department and all individuals involved. The responsibility to ensure compliance at departmental level rests with the Head of School/Support Department. While the function of ensuring compliance may be delegated to one or more members of staff within the Department/Unit, the responsibility for the Procedure cannot be delegated.
- 4.2 Employees are required by the; Health & Safety at Work Act 1974, the Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999, the Workplace (Health, Safety and Welfare) Regulations 1992 (as amended) and the Provision and Use of Work Equipment Regulations 1998 (as amended), to take reasonable care for their own health and safety, and to use correctly all work items in accordance with the training and instructions they receive to enable them to use the items safely.
- 4.3 University employees have a responsibility to co-operate with the University to enable the University to comply with its statutory duties. They are also required to notify the University of any shortcomings in the Health and Safety arrangements in order to allow the University to remedy such shortcomings.
- 4.4 The Head of Department/Unit has the responsibility to ensure that Lone Working risk assessments are completed and ensures any actions required to be taken to mitigate risks to health from Lone Working activities are implemented.
- 4.5 Lone working activities should routinely be reassessed, at intervals of no greater than two years, even though there may be no reason to suspect that there has been any change to the activity.
- 4.6 Risk assessments must be shared with the individuals undertaking Lone Working activities, and they must sign to confirm that they have read and understood the content of such assessments.

5. KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS

- 5.1 Lone Working is work which is specifically intended to be carried out unaccompanied or without immediate access to another employee.

Lone working can occur:

- During normal working hours at a remote location either within the normal workplace or during a fieldtrip; and
- When working outside normal working hours.

- 5.2 Departmental procedures need to take account of the possibility of both situations arising and should define what constitutes 'normal working hours'. Flexible working hours are a valuable and necessary component of the working environment. However, the argument for working outside normal working hours should not be used to justify poor planning and undisciplined working arrangements. Wherever reasonably practicable, work should be contained within recognised working hours.

- 5.3 Working alone is specifically prohibited by law only in a small number of well established dangerous situations such as working with live electrical conductors, entry into confined spaces, etc.
- 5.4 The hazards associated with the task are likely to be the same whether it is carried out alone or accompanied, although the possibility of violence towards the lone worker should always be considered. Those carrying out assessments should therefore use the techniques they normally use for hazard identification when considering the hazards of lone working.
- 5.5 Although working alone may not introduce any new hazards, the risks may differ significantly when a task is carried out unaccompanied.
- 5.6 Medical fitness should not be a significant factor when considering typical office activities conducted outside normal hours. However in other situations it may be necessary to check that lone workers have no medical conditions that may make them unsuitable for working alone. When medical advice is necessary, the Occupational Health Nurse should be contacted.
- 5.7 Lone workers should not be placed at more risk than other employees and extra control measures may be required. Precautions should take account of normal work and foreseeable emergencies such as fire, equipment failure, illness and accidents. Those with responsibility for carrying out risk assessments should ask questions such as:
- Does the workplace present a special risk to lone worker?
 - Is there safe access and egress?
 - Can one person safely handle all plant, substances and goods involved in the work?
 - Is there a risk of violence?
- 5.8 Lone workers need to be sufficiently experienced and be able to understand the risks and precautions fully. Schools/Departments must establish clear procedures and set the limits to what can and cannot be done while working alone. There should be an agreement as to the circumstances in which it is reasonable to stop work and seek advice. It is a management responsibility to ensure employees are competent to carry out the work unaccompanied and are competent to deal with circumstances that are new, unusual or beyond the scope of training.
- 5.9 Contingency plans should specify the action to be taken if a pre-arranged contact cannot be reached, or an alarm device operate, and should be included as part of the risk assessment.
- 5.10 The risk assessment will have identified the physical controls, systems of work, training and supervision necessary to ensure the safety of the lone worker. If all of these arrangements are not already in place, they will need to be implemented in a structured way before the lone working can be permitted to commence. An action plan with target dates for completion of the outstanding work is often the most appropriate way of ensuring that the necessary arrangements are put in place effectively.

- 5.11 Once the safe working arrangements have been implemented they need to be regularly monitored and reviewed to ensure they remain effective. Monitoring the way in which people are working is a routine day-to-day management function. More formal monitoring of the arrangements will also take place as part of the health and safety audit programme. Lone workers must be actively encouraged to report any incidents which could affect their safety, to allow a proper review of the adequacy of the working arrangements.

6. SUSTAINABILITY

- 6.1 It is recommended that all copies of the assessment be stored electronically in a shared drive, available to all individuals who may be affected, thus reducing the University's paper consumption and assisting it to meet its published sustainability targets.

Assessment Ref Number:	
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Appendix 1

Lone Worker Risk Assessment

School/Department:	Health and Life Sciences
Campus:	Lanarkshire
Date completed:	07/01/18
Date review due:	
Risk assessment carried out by:	Barbara Gonçalves

Personal details withheld.

Section 1:			
What is the work activity?			
Recruitment of potential participants from the respiratory clinic at the Queen Elizabeth University Hospital (QEUH), Marie Curie Hospice, Prince and Princess of Wales hospice, St Vincent's Hospice, Ardgowan Hospice, and in-depth qualitative interviews and quantitative questionnaires undertaken either in the hospital setting, or in the participants home.			
Section 2:			
Where will lone working activities occur? (tick all that apply)			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Fieldwork	<input type="checkbox"/> Working Alone in Buildings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Transiting between sites	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):
Section 3:			
What work activities will be undertaken whilst lone working?			
In-depth interviews and questionnaires with people living with advanced COPD			
Section 4:			
What are the hazards associated with lone working? (tick all that apply)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Access/Exit of building or premises	<input type="checkbox"/> High Crime Risk Area	<input type="checkbox"/> Isolated Area	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Breakdown (equipment)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Medical problems/health concerns	<input type="checkbox"/> Moving and handling	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Breakdown (vehicle)	<input type="checkbox"/> Travel between sites on isolated roads	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Unsociable hours	
<input type="checkbox"/> Cash Handling	<input type="checkbox"/> Violence and/or Aggression	<input type="checkbox"/> Working at Height	
<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity			
<input type="checkbox"/> Exposure to chemicals or substances including asphyxiants and explosive			

atmospheres	
Other (please specify): Accessing participant's homes and undertaking in-depth interviews which may cause distress to the participant and/or researcher.	
Section 5: What control measures do you currently have in place to manage the risks? (tick all that apply)	
Measure	Provide Specific Detail
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Ability to contact base if stranded	Lone working flowchart devised with contact details attached.
<input type="checkbox"/> Access/Exit routes maintained/clear from obstruction	
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental Conditions managed (e.g. ice/gritting etc)	
<input type="checkbox"/> First Aid provision available	
<input type="checkbox"/> Incident reporting system (including for near misses)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Lighting (including security lighting)	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Local management of whereabouts (diaries)	Location & time of interview shared with line manager.
<input type="checkbox"/> Man down alarm	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Mobile Telephone/Telephones	The researcher will have their mobile fully charged and on at all times during the interview. The line manager will also ensure their phone is fully charged and on during the interview so the researcher can make contact at any time and will log in pre and post interview.
<input type="checkbox"/> Monitored CCTV	
<input type="checkbox"/> Panic buttons (linked to manned system)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Personal attack alarms	
<input type="checkbox"/> Regular contact systems	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Safe System of Work (SSOW) (e.g. what to do in the event of alarm sounding or failure to return from field trip etc)	Flowchart developed.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> X Are the above systems/procedures communicated to staff?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Security access systems e.g. digilock, swipe access	
<input type="checkbox"/> Training on personal safety/aggression/violence	
<input type="checkbox"/> Two person working for high risk activities e.g. working with asphyxiants or electricity	
<input type="checkbox"/> Two way radios	

<input type="checkbox"/> Other (provide detail):			
Section 6: <i>Do further control measures require to be implemented to manage these risks? (refer to section 5 – are there any gaps in the control measures which would assist in reducing the risk to as low as is reasonably practicable?)</i>			
<i>Control Measure</i>	<i>Who will action this?</i>	<i>By When</i>	<i>Date Completed</i>

1	August 2015	New - 1 st iteration		KB

Appendix 15: Flowchart of Personal Safety

Appendix 16: Consent Form

Personal details withheld.

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: **Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care services.**

Name of PhD student: Barbara Gonçalves

Please write your initials in each statement that applies:

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet dated (version.....) for the above study.
2. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time.
4. I understand that relevant sections of my data collected during this study may be looked at by individuals from the University of the West of Scotland. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.
5. I understand that the information collected about me may be shared anonymously with other researchers.
6. I understand that an interview will be audio recorded and I consent use of anonymised quotes in a dissertation and academic publications.
7. I agree to inform my GP about my participation.
8. I agree to take part in the above study.

initials

<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Patient,

Date,

Signature

Name of Person
taking consent,

Date,

Signature

Appendix 17: Participant Debrief Sheet

Participant Debrief Sheet

Project Title: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care.

That is the end of your participation in the study. Thank you very much for the information you provided and for giving up your time.
The key findings from this study will be available at the service that provides your care, once it is finished.

The research student's contact details are below:

Please bear in mind that if you wish to withdraw from the research at any point or you have any questions about the study, you can contact the research student who will be more than happy to talk to you.

Should you have any complaints regarding your treatment during the study or any aspect of the study, please contact the research student directly or the Post Graduate

Thank you again for participating in this study.
Barbara Gonçalves

Personal details
withheld.

Version 7, 05/03/2019

Appendix 18: Privacy Notice

Privacy Notice

The University of the West of Scotland (the "University" or "we") is the sponsor for this study- *Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease of those attending two different models of palliative care*- based in the United Kingdom. The University is committed to looking after any information that you make available to us and we aim to be clear about what we will do with your data. This privacy notice explains when and why we collect personal information about you and how we will use this information.

We will use the information you have provided to us in order to carry out the research study and our basis for doing this is that it is in the public interest for us to do so. We will act as the data controller in relation to the information you provide. We will not share your information with any third parties that are not part of the research group mentioned in this Participant Information Notice. We will keep identifiable information about you for one year after the study has finished.

The information you have provided to us will not be transferred out of the EEA.

You can find information about:-

- The details of our data protection officer
- How we will keep your information safe
- What choices you have in relation to your information
- How you can complain about the use of your information.

in our privacy notice which you can read here - <https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-our-website/privacy/>

Some of the rights you have in relation to your information that are set out in the privacy notice are limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you withdraw from the study, we will delete the information about you that we have already obtained, where it is possible for us to do so. To safeguard, your rights, we will use the minimum personally-identifiable information possible.

Appendix 19: GP Notification Letter

GP Notification letter

Study: Exploring the psychosocial impact of living with advanced Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease on those attending two different models of palliative care services

Dear Dr.

Your patient has been diagnosed with severe or very severe COPD and has agreed to take part in the presented research. The study is being coordinated by the University of the West of Scotland.

This PhD study will use a mixed method approach that will provide insight into the experiences of patients with advanced COPD accessing two different models of palliative care services- specialised palliative care (hospice) and non-specialised palliative care (respiratory clinic) in the West of Scotland. This study aims to investigate the quality of life and psychosocial aspects (such as burden, distress, anxiety and depression) of patients with advanced COPD, attending palliative care services. The presented research will compare two models of healthcare, specify the similarities and differences between them, patients' experiences of care settings and scores on QoL, depression, and anxiety. Possible factors influencing patients' QoL, depression and anxiety, will be investigated. This study will involve interviewing and/or administering validated questionnaires. To receive information about patients scores on QoL, depression and anxiety, two validated questionnaires will be administered to the patients: The McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire-Revised (MQOL-R) and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) and scored in line with authors instructions. Semi-structured interviews will explore experiences of advanced COPD patients at a hospice and a respiratory clinic. The aim is to investigate the little understood phenomenon of patients with COPD in palliative care, identify essential categories of meaning and to generate hypotheses for further research. It is hoped that the information obtained from this study may improve the services that are offered to people with advanced COPD.

Should you have any questions or require further information about this research, please do not hesitate to contact the person in a clinical governance role, in charge of the local study.

Your contact:

Tel:

You may also contact PhD student, Barbara Gonçalves, responsible for data collection, analysis and interpretation.

Barbara Gonçalves

Personal details
withheld.

Version 1, 05/03/2019

Appendix 20: Coding Strategy

DIAGNOSIS

The story of being diagnosed and experiences of quitting smoking. The knowledge and awareness of symptoms.

TREATMENT

Experience of a referral to current service and any discussion connected with the treatment they underwent. Any decisions about treatment, including life support stages. Effect of medications or any additional therapy such as pulmonary rehabilitation and other.

COPING

Any stages of adjustment, such as looking for purpose, adjusting to a different lifestyle and acceptance.

SUPPORT

Support received by formal and informal carers. Also, use of support groups and day hospices.

SOCIAL LIFE

Discourse that included loss of social life, social isolation and its consequences.

EVERYDAY STRUGGLES

Discussing predicaments of everyday life and symptoms they encountered on a daily basis. Thoughts on changes in lifestyle imposed by these symptoms.

EMOTIONS

Experiencing anxiety, fears of the future, panic attacks and depression linked with breathlessness and other mood changes inflicted by the disease.

EXPERIENCE OF HEALTHCARE

Positive and negative experiences of interactions with medical, nursing, and allied health professions. Patients' satisfaction with care and what was missing

Appendix 21: Biographies of the Participants

<p>Jane AC1 79 years Female White British Hospice Ex-smoker Widowed</p>	<p>Jane lives alone but is supported by her son, who visits her when needed. She does not recall the exact moment of diagnosis and has very little understanding of the disease. She has not received any additional therapy, such as pulmonary rehabilitation or self-management programmes. She mainly stays at home but occasionally goes out with her best friend. Tiredness restricts her from walking any distance or doing chores. She feels hopeless about the future; nothing can make it better. She attends the hospice day care and appreciates the personal approach there. She is deeply satisfied as it improves her social life because other than that, her social life is non-existent due to the physical restrictions caused by COPD.</p>
<p>Colin AC2 85 years Male White British Hospice Ex-smoker Widowed</p>	<p>Colin does not understand what COPD is and what causes it. He does not have any support from his family and only contacts his attorney. He has not received any additional therapy for COPD, such as rehabilitation, education or self-management programmes. He moved to a care home because of COPD and his inability to take care of himself. Colin spends all days in his room and emphasised his opinion about the incompetence of the staff who think he has dementia. He is not satisfied with the healthcare he receives from the community level; he only sees a GP, who, in his opinion, has no knowledge about COPD. He likes the staff's approach in the day hospice, and it gives him a unique opportunity to socialise. He feels cared for in the hospice as well as he enjoys activities with his occupational therapist who helps him to relax and feel fulfilled.</p>

<p>Cynthia AC3 63 years Female White British Clinic Smoker Married</p>	<p>Cynthia struggles with tiredness, breathlessness and pain in the hip joints. She is satisfied with the care she receives, especially from community nurses. She feels that she can call them any day and ask for help if needed. Cynthia has not received any additional programmes offered for COPD patients. Leaving home only for appointments she has a limited social life due to COPD. Nevertheless, she has visitors at home every day, so she does not feel alone. Empathy from healthcare professionals as well as relatives is the most important to her and makes her feel supported. Cynthia still smokes, knowing it deteriorates her health, but she struggles to give it up. Smoking is also, in her opinion, one of the pleasures in life she still has.</p>
<p>Frances AC4 45 years Female White British Hospice Ex-smoker Single</p>	<p>Frances was admitted to the hospital for COPD exacerbation when she was in critical condition. She got scared and started to take care more of herself with her school age sons in mind. She understands a lot about her disease and has adjusted to the limitations it brings. Frances reads a lot about the condition she has. Because of COPD, she gave up her work due to physical incapacities. Since the hospital admission, terrified of losing her life and leaving her sons, she suffers from anxiety and depression. The consultant thought that additional support would be helpful to her and referred her for pulmonary rehabilitation in the hospice. She is pretty satisfied with the healthcare she receives and feels that the healthcare professionals are only a phone call away. Frances does stationary cycling and arm bike at home, to maintain her condition in the best state possible. What makes her feel optimistic and happy are vacations with her children; she chose to go on a cruise because of having the opportunity to rest whenever she needs.</p>

<p>Mark AC5 67 years Male White British Clinic Ex-smoker Partnership</p>	<p>Mark was diagnosed seven years ago and fully understands his diagnosis. His partner is a nurse and takes care of him, being his only carer. All his family died, and he has a brother in a terminal stage in another city, whom he had just visited, which upset him and influenced his sad mood during the interview. In general, he considers himself a happy and lucky person. Mark tries to be active as much as possible and goes out daily with his partner and dogs to a neighbourhood park. He has moved to a more residential area, and he does not go to pubs etc anymore. He received various additional therapies and he attends monthly support groups which he values and enjoys participating in. He feels completely supported by his partner, a consultant and the support group.</p>
<p>Ellen AC6 62 years Female White British Clinic Hospice Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>Ellen was diagnosed 10 years ago while she was hospitalised for an ear infection. She has attended various programmes and therapies as well as day-care in hospice. For years she has been housebound, with every movement she makes she is at risk of being breathless which is why she taught her body to use the toilet only twice a day. She stays in bed all day, and morphine helps her leave it. Ellen is terrified of hospitals and avoids going out due to being paranoid about sharing oxygen with other people. She is also scared of bacteria in the hospital which could contribute to her developing another lung infection. Moreover, she gave up going out to a restaurant because her appetite is minimal. She does not see a point in a life so limited and with so many restrictions. Next time she has a breathless attack, she does not want her husband to call an ambulance but wants him to let her go. Despite feeling supported by her husband and her consultant, she wishes she had home visits from the community care, in order to void going to a hospital, which she is terrified of. She</p>

	regularly frequents the support group and is friends with its members, such as Mark AC5. She has also attended day care in a hospice, which she enjoyed. However, the physical burden of going there was too high and she feels it is not for her at the moment. She is considering end-of-life care in hospice when the time comes and has signed a DNR.
<p>Davis AC7</p> <p>78 years</p> <p>Male</p> <p>White British</p> <p>Clinic</p> <p>Ex-smoker</p> <p>Widowed</p>	<p>Davis was diagnosed 20 years ago. COPD is a consequence of smoking and working in a steel factory. He has a complete understanding of his disease and initially attended additional programmes for COPD patients, such as rehabilitation and management programmes, but he believes they are not for him anymore. Davis is quite hopeless about any improvement in his life because there is no cure for his condition. Still, he feels confident about his knowledge about the disease, and if he has questions, he can check by himself or ask a doctor. At this moment, he thinks he does not need any additional therapy or a support group because he manages just fine. Davis suffered more anxiety when his wife died 4 years ago, and this was more difficult to cope with than COPD. He is housebound and this is the most challenging limitation for him. Davis has support from his family and feels confident with healthcare professionals. A nurse from a hospital once every six months comes to his home to check upon him.</p>
<p>Susan AC8</p> <p>66 years</p> <p>Female</p> <p>White British</p> <p>Clinic</p> <p>Hospice</p> <p>Ex-smoker</p> <p>Divorced</p>	<p>Her lifestyle has changed; she needs to plan everything and is dependent on others. She asks a neighbour to clean and family (children, grandchildren and a cousin) to do groceries. The disease and dependence on oxygen prevent her from going out. She has recently missed out on an opportunity to go to the cinema because of oxygen therapy, problems with lifting the heavy weighted bottle or with having access to oxygen from, e.g., outlets in hotel walls. Understanding her</p>

	<p>disease symptoms and struggles both by family and healthcare professionals is most relevant to her. She considers pulmonary rehabilitation the most beneficial to her and would like to do exercises at home but did not know how and whom she could ask to have it. She does not see nurses at home; they have come only twice, and she lacks the systematical check-ups by nurses. She was hoping for a lung transplant but was not eligible for it. She attended a day hospice, but it was too much of a burden to her, because preparing to leave home was too stressful. Not seeing other people like her makes her feel alone with COPD. Prayers help her when feeling blue or anxious.</p>
<p>Alastair AC9 68 years Male White British Clinic Smoker Partnership</p>	<p>Alastair was diagnosed 15 years ago after repetitive chest infections. He was interviewed during hospital admission for a chest infection. He is satisfied with the knowledge about his diagnosis. His carer is his ex-wife, with whom he is back now. She takes care of him just fine, but he does not want to abuse it and wants her to maintain her social life and lifestyle, instead of only caring for him. Alastair lost independence, and this is the most substantial loss for him. He cannot leave his house on his own, as he used to the disease became so burdensome. Every activity which needs planning, such as taking a bath, makes him frustrated. Although he tries to be most independent within his capacities. He has attended only a pulmonology rehabilitation. Satisfied with the respiratory consultant, Alastair has a negative opinion about his GP, who in his view stigmatises him and does not do his best to treat him. Alastair feels discriminated as he thinks he is not eligible to get any nurse care or social support because of his postcode in a more deprived area. He needs more local help, someone who could assist his ex-wife.</p>

<p>Lorna AC10 63 years Female White British Clinic Hospice Ex-smoker Divorced</p>	<p>Lorna understands her disease in the smallest detail. She was a very sociable person with a responsible job, an essential part of her life which she had to let go. Her hobbies were travelling abroad, meeting people from different cultures, activities she cannot do anymore. She used to do sports such as horse riding and she misses this part of her life. She finds the purpose of living with this disease in being a part of a community; in her case, it is being a family member and a neighbour. Her support system is well developed, and she can rely on them and call them when she needs help her. She noticed that her cognitive capacities are not as good as before. She used to have a rich vocabulary, while now she struggles to find some words, sometimes forgetting them. Lorna also used to read, but currently, she lacks concentration, so instead, she watches movies. Her abilities to move are pretty restricted. She needs to plan all the activities she wants to do during the day. Her lifestyle has been curtailed by not going out to a theatre or a cinema because of oxygen, carrying bottles of oxygen with her and the noise it generates. She has been attending a support clinic for some years, and used to go to a day care hospice. Nevertheless, it was too much burden to go there, and she still has home visits from a hospice nurse. Lorna used to receive individual rehabilitation at home. She is very content with the care she receives, having support workers who come and wash her. She does not want to be seen as sick or in any way disabled, so she adopted a strategy of always having full makeup, being well dressed in order to look "normal" because she is not wedded to her disease as she is too vivid for that. She has grand hopes in future research about COPD and reads about it.</p>
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<p>Rachel AC11 64 years Female White British Clinic Ex-smoker Divorced</p>	<p>Rachel does not fully understand COPD, its nature, and how it actually began, but she is afraid at the moment to learn more because it would make her more depressed. She attended a support group once and saw people with oxygen, which motivated her to quit smoking. Straight after the meeting, she went to a consultant for the advice of weaning off cigarettes and have used vapes and patches since then. She has depression, not related to COPD, and has received CBT for two years. She also attended pulmonary rehabilitation. Rachel used to be a part of a voluntary community, where she did gardening but needed to quit that one year ago because of physical condition and she still misses it. Her social life is connected only to her family. They have an excellent relationship; they call her and give her lifts. Being incapable of leaving home freely makes her feel isolated. Attending the support group made Rachel more hopeful about her future in matters with respect to having contact with people with struggles like hers.</p>
<p>Keith AC12 73 years Male White British Clinic Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>Keith worked for thirty years with chemicals. He has attended a clinic and a support group for 1.5 year. His wife, with whom he is very close, is his most prominent support. He also has support from his children, grandchildren, and neighbours. When feeling breathless, he tends to have panic attacks and his wife calms him down. Keith, especially initially, attended numerous therapies, of which rehabilitation helped the most. He receives home visits from respiratory nurses and values their care very much. Keith tries to stay as independent as he can, e.g., still cooks for himself. He cannot go on holidays by plane anymore because the last time he was on a flight, he had a breathlessness attack, and an ambulance was waiting for him at the airport. Keith has adjusted to his constraints and</p>

	<p>goes with his wife to the seaside in a wheelchair. When it comes to shopping, they choose only shops with benches.</p>
<p>Abigail AC13 61 years Female White British Clinic Ex-smoker, passive smoker Partnership</p>	<p>Abigail was diagnosed 9 years ago. She has a partner in a terminal cancer stage, and she is mainly concerned with him, neglecting her needs. There were both smokers and the local support group helped her to quit smoking. Yet, her partner, after being diagnosed with cancer, decided to take up smoking again. Since Abigail quit smoking, she has been feeling much better. Every day she feels limited by the disease, immobile, slower and needs to plan to avoid stairs every time she goes somewhere. Abigail sometimes goes with her partner to a golf club, where they socialise. She meets her girlfriends in the city centre once a month for lunch. Furthermore, she emphasises that retirement money is a problem and after paying the bills she can hardly afford to go out. Abigail is very trusting and believes both her GP and the consultant. She was satisfied with the nurses paying for them half price. However, the last nurses were not a good fit for her; she did not feel comfortable with them. She attended local rehabilitation and does yoga for relaxation at home.</p>
<p>James AC14 54 years Male White British Clinic Ex-smoker Single</p>	<p>James was diagnosed around 10 years ago with asthma and 5 years ago with COPD. He was sent off sick but asked a GP to be cleared to work because he could not stay at home. Staying at home would make him less mentally acute. James has been working all his life, and it helps him to be active and is not distressed. He wants to work for as long as it will be possible. James takes oxygen to his work and walks with it when needed, although he mostly sits in front of a computer. Another respiratory team used to manage him, but through his colleagues, he heard about the New Victoria team and asked to be transferred there. He trusts the new team entirely</p>

	<p>and is fully satisfied with it. It took him years to accept the disease, but finally, he is at peace with it. The disease and oxygen therapy took away his activities (concerts), and he does not go out to pubs anymore. James has 2 children and lives with his son. The son gives him some help, for example by walking a dog or shopping for groceries. Nonetheless, James does not want the son to help him more as he wants his children to have their lives. James is aware that he will need their help, but not yet. He talks about his problems with understand COPD, especially those working at NHS. Still, James cannot share everything he would want to. In recent months, he noticed that he has slowed down and has problems getting from point A to point B. In the past, he attended individual rehabilitation and self-management programmes and soon James will join a group pulmonary rehabilitation.</p>
<p>April AC15: 73 years Female White British Hospice Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>April was diagnosed 5 years ago. She has osteoporosis and put DNR in place because resuscitation would break her ribs, and she does not want that. For one year April has been using oxygen and it has been very beneficial, albeit it led to mobility restrictions. She tries to be independent within her capacities and dislikes being dependent on others. April accepted her disease and her limited lifestyle, taking her life as it is. She travels with her husband in a caravan, and it is the only form of social life they have. Nevertheless, she has hearing problems, so she would not socialise much or go out to a pub anyway. Her husband is very supportive, motivates her to move and not to feel sorry for herself. All in all, April feels very well supported by her carer and healthcare professionals. She attended group pulmonary rehabilitation, relaxation therapy and has home visits from a nurse. The day care was</p>

	<p>her first programme in the hospice and she was delighted with it.</p>
<p>Beth AC16 64 years Female White British Hospice Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>Beth's mother had COPD and died of it. Beth has immense pain in the back, which considerably lessens her QOL. She does not want to be resuscitated. She is not on oxygen now but wants to ask talk about it with her consultant next time she sees her. Her GP makes individual home appointments, and she has district nurses coming over once a fortnight. Initially, she attended a self-help group and received group pulmonary rehabilitation and relaxation therapy. Her husband is not a good carer for her and he does not understand COPD. He is involved in care, but he does not show his emotions so she cannot open in front of him. Beth had support from a daughter, but she cannot be her carer anymore because her payment for being a carer is too small. Beth feels she has nobody who could help her and now it is too late for her husband to be more engaged in care. Beth believes that she does not have proper support and is frustrated about being unable to do the activities she used to do, which contributed to her feeling miserable for many months. She lost confidence because she cannot go out. She lacks patience now because she is very irritated, for example, when someone with authority lets her down. She has no close friend to talk to about her disease and misses having the right person whom she can trust. She feels the need to be understood by someone. The only social life Beth has is at the hospice. She likes the atmosphere there, where is much laughter. However, it has been the first time she is referred to it, and she does not know what will happen next. Beth would like to meet peers even twice a week. She feels hopeless about her future and would like to have a break from her life, going</p>

	<p>somewhere and just forgetting about it. She has sleeping problems, lies at night thinking. Breathlessness together with pain make it difficult for her to fall asleep.</p>
<p>Sarah AC17 66 years Female White British Hospice Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>Sarah was a heavy smoker. After the diagnosis, she was in negation a long time, thinking that tablets would get her out of it. She finally accepted her disease and is upset about how deteriorating the condition is. Sarah even sold her car, knowing that with her disease she will never be able to drive. She has syncope when she coughs. Sarah feels very supported by her family carers and healthcare professionals, especially in managing syncope. She also has a befriender, a retired nurse, and it is a tremendous support to her. The most important to her is to have someone next to her, who understands COPD. She frequented two programmes of exercises; they were tough but most helpful in the COPD treatment. Sarah has been attending the hospice weekly for years because other patients asked the hospice to bring her back after a 12-week programme. Her being a sociable person benefited the dynamics of the group. Sarah is a happy person who laughs a lot and she has not lost her spirit, being the centre of attention and the life and soul of a party. Her husband is happy to look after her, but she feels she is too much burden for him. Hence, she also decided to attend day care so that he has some time off. She would like to be independent to go out and a befriender helps with these issues. Sarah uses an electric buggy but still needs someone to walk with her. Loss of her independence was upsetting to her as she does not like to ask others for help. Sarah feels terrible for embarrassing or upsetting others because of her syncopes. She is exhausted all day, unable to sleep well at night, and experiencing urinary incontinence. At 6 in the</p>

	<p>afternoon, Sarah is ready to go to bed with pads below her body as in hospital.</p>
<p>Nancy AC18 70 years Female White British Clinic Ex-smoker Divorced</p>	<p>Nancy quitted smoking 16 years ago, before COPD was diagnosed which was 10 years ago. Later she had lung cancer and a lobectomy. Her lifestyle is restricted, and she is slowed down, unable do as much as before e.g., carry shopping bags. Nancy attended the support clinic for 2 years after her first hospital admission. She has received four rehabilitation programmes and repeats the exercises at home. Nancy is not interested in support groups as she has developed a support system at home. She considers herself a fortunate person; she is neither nor depressed, taking every day as it is, not overthinking about the future. She has a lot of family support; just needs to call they will come and help or take her wherever she wants. Her support system well is developed with family around her as well as friends. She has a neighbour helping her, also with COPD but in a better condition, and her family is just a phone call away.</p>
<p>Glen AC19 62 years Male White British Clinic Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>Glen was diagnosed with COPD 7 years ago and continued smoking until exacerbations repeated. In the past he had a bad fall in his work, when he broke his clavicle and damaged one lung, diminishing his lung capacity. Glen needed to ask for sick leave as he could not work any longer due to his COPD. Glen's biggest problem used to be panic attacks. He feels he had support from healthcare professionals only for the panic attacks, not the daily needs or everyday issues. Occupational therapists recognised when panic attacks started and help him to control them. The decline of independence was a substantial loss for him. Glen used to go to charity shops but cannot do it anymore. He received CBT before and after his COPD diagnosis. He is oxygen-</p>

	<p>dependent and feels embarrassed because of it, not in front of family but with neighbours and strangers. Oxygen helps him a lot; he cannot breathe and walk without it. The family knows that he needs oxygen, but he feels they do not understand much about the reason behind it. Glen does not have any social life anymore and does not want anyone to see him with oxygen tanks and cannulas. He would like to know other people's experiences to cope better. However, not meeting other people with similar problems makes him feel isolated. He goes to pulmonary rehabilitation but does not see an interaction between the participants. During the sessions, patients only do exercises. They received leaflets but did not discuss it between themselves. Moreover, he wants to share his views so that others can cope better with this disease. Every day he takes morphine, lorazepam for panic attacks, which they make him drowsy. It is thought that taking lorazepam long-term caused tremors that significantly affect him. He will be tested for Parkinson's in the future after the interview. He takes Trazadone to help him sleep at night. Glen tends to feel frustrated and grumpy but takes life day by day, which prevents him from having fears. He needs more programmes that would help him to cope with the disease. He does not attend a support group, but he misses being surrounded by people like himself.</p>
<p>Graham AC20 75 years Male White British Clinic Smoker Widowed</p>	<p>Graham was diagnosed three years ago. COPD is a consequence of having contact with asbestos during his work and unhealthy lifestyle. He worked in the navy abroad in the building sector, and he says he had an exciting life. He receives regular support from the council and community level from physiotherapists, occupational therapists, CBT therapist and respiratory nurses. For one year, he has</p>

	<p>received this high level of care and is very happy with it. House help makes meals which helped him reduce his anxiety. Nurses are most important to him because they are responsible for the daily care. To make patients feel supported by healthcare professionals, it is vital to they should show interest in the patients and ask questions about how he is doing. Graham does not think that enough was done for him in hospitals. Sometimes he was discharged too soon and returned after a short period. He does not trust hospital doctors but he trusts the consultant's care and decisions in the outpatient clinic. Graham accepted that there is no cure and that he needs to learn to cope with the disease. He believes that managing the disease depends on his mental control. He has adjusted to the disabilities that the condition brought and accepted them. Graham's social life has diminished due to disease adjustments. He has two children, but they have their own life, and he does not want to bother them with his problems. His children are both academics, and he feels wrong asking them to help with his at-home repairs because it used to be his responsibility. Notwithstanding, he can count on them if he needs any help. He regrets smoking and that it took him so long to quit. Graham blames tv adverts and the generation of tobacco-smoking trends for his problems. He would like to help other people with COPD so that something beneficial could be found for them.</p>
<p>Alexander AC21 67 years Male White British Clinic</p>	<p>Alexander was diagnosed 10 years ago, after working years with dust and paint. He needed to give up his work because of experiencing tiresome breathlessness. Since then, he has suffered from anxiety as a consequence of having a gap in his life and missing his old life. The most challenging</p>

<p>Ex-smoker Married</p>	<p>adjustment was retirement and not working. Staying at home is odd for him, something he had never done before. He was a very active, social person and his phone always rang. After COPD diagnosis his social life diminished. Friends do not come over anymore and he talks with them over the phone. Only family members come to visit him, but still, he misses family parties. Alexander cannot spend much time with his grandchildren because they can be tiring. He meets people in the chapel down the road where he can talk to monks and other people and has much support down there. He lacks concentrations and tends to forget what he or others said 10 minutes ago. Alexander also feels uncomfortable using inhalers next to others. With COPD, everything has changed. He mostly stays at home, and when he leaves it, he needs a long preparation, so he has to be at a place one hour in advance. He accepted the progressive nature of the disease. Early in the diagnosis, he attended rehabilitation and a local support group. Alexander believes it was helpful to get informed about the disease and to meet people with similar problems. Because of the costs of these programmes, he attended local rehabilitation only for eighteen months. Alexander adjusted to the disabilities that the disease brings and takes life day-by-day. His wife, who is understanding and sensitive to his needs, has significant input in it. He has a good relationship with her, so being dependent on her, he does not feel that he is a burden to her.</p>
<p>Mike AC22 74 years Male White British Clinic</p>	<p>Mike was a journalist and smoked as a consequence of environmental influence (work and family). Twenty-five years ago, while working abroad he had an x-ray where changes in his lungs were visible. Smoking was tough to quit. He tried counselling, hypnosis, acupuncture (which helped but only</p>

<p>Ex-smoker Divorced</p>	<p>temporarily), patches, relaxation. Finally, he read a book, which helped for a year. Then he smoked again until a close friend, a heavy smoker, passed away, and it shook him. Since then, he has not smoked. He compares smoking to other addictions and thinks more in-depth about it, and he would like people to stop smoking. Mike is glad that nowadays people tend to smoke less than in his generation. He had prostate cancer and since then has been suffering from bladder incontinence. Consequently, he needs to prepare before going somewhere because he needs a place close to a toilet and without stairs due to of breathlessness. Last year he had lung volume reduction surgery. Every day Mike feels grateful for feeling better after the surgery. He does not worry about the future as there is no control over it, accepts the situation, lives one day at a time which helps him not to feel panicky. Mike gained more independence after the surgery and has not had panic attacks since then. He would like more people to know about COPD. Mike also benefited from an exceptional network between both a surgeon and a respiratory consultant. He has a great social life; he goes out fishing, on holidays abroad, even for a month. His children do not understand much about his disease, but it does not bother him. He went to a rehabilitation programme and a psychologist after the diagnosis. Next, he attended a six-week course of relaxation through music and body manipulation to calm him down. At the end both therapist and he agreed it was sufficient.</p>
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Appendix 22: Characteristics of the Participants

Part 1

<u>IDNr</u>	<u>Synonym name</u>	<u>Service</u>	<u>Gender</u>	<u>FEV1% pred.</u>	<u>Age</u>	<u>Marital status</u>	<u>Employment status</u>	<u>Smoking status</u>	<u>Education level</u>
AC1	Jane	Hospice	Female	N/D	79	Widowed	Retired	Ex-smoker	Secondary
AC2	Colin	Hospice	Male	N/D	85	Widowed	Retired	Ex-smoker	Secondary
AC3	Cynthia	Clinic	Female	27	63	Married	Unemployed	Smoker	Secondary
AC4	Frances	Hospice	Female	34	45	Single	Unemployed	Ex- smoker	Higher
AC5	Mark	Clinic	Male	26	67	Partnership	Retired	Ex- smoker	Vocational
AC6	Ellen	Clinic	Female	21	62	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC7	Davis	Clinic	Male	44	78	Widowed	Retired	Ex- smoker	Vocational
AC8	Susan	Clinic	Female	20	66	Divorced	Retired	Ex- smoker	Vocational
AC9	Alastair	Clinic	Male	41	68	Partnership	Retired	Smoker	Secondary
AC10	Lorna	Clinic	Female	33	63	Divorced	Retired	Ex- smoker	Higher
AC11	Rachel	Clinic	Female	51	64	Divorced	Unemployed	Ex- smoker	Did not say
AC12	Keith	Clinic	Male	27	73	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC13	Abigail	Clinic	Female	33	61	Partnership	Retired	Ex-smoker	Secondary
AC14	James	Clinic	Male	21	54	Single	Employed	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC15	April	Hospice	Female	44.9	73	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC16	Beth	Hospice	Female	42.6	64	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC17	Sarah	Hospice	Female	36.8	66	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC18	Nancy	Clinic	Female	72	70	Divorced	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC19	Glen	Clinic	Male	35	62	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Secondary
AC20	Graham	Clinic	Male	28	75	Widowed	Retired	Smoker	Secondary
AC21	Alexander	Clinic	Male	65	67	Married	Retired	Ex- smoker	Vocational
AC22	Mike	Clinic	Male	36	74	Divorced	Retired	Ex- smoker	Vocational

Part 2

<u>IDNr</u>	<u>Synonym name</u>	<u>Informal support</u>	<u>Additional therapies</u>	<u>Oxygen therapy</u>	<u>Antidepressants</u>
AC1	Jane	Children	None	Yes	No
AC2	Colin	No one	None	Yes	No
AC3	Cynthia	Children Grandchildren Friends Neighbours	None	No	No
AC4	Frances	Mother	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Relaxation therapy	Yes	Yes
AC5	Mark	Partner	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-management programmes Self-help group Relaxation therapy Massage	Yes	No
AC6	Ellen	Husband Children Friends	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Self-management programmes Self-help group	Yes	No
AC7	Davis	Children Grandchildren	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Self-management programmes	Yes	Yes
AC8	Susan	Children Grandchildren Friends	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Relaxation therapy	Yes	Yes
AC9	Alastair	Partner Children	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Massage	No	No
AC10	Lorna	Cousins Grandchildren	Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-help group	Yes	Yes
AC11	Rachel	Children Grandchildren	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Self-help group Counselling	No	Yes
AC12	Keith	Wife Children Grandchildren Friends	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-management programmes Self-help group Relaxation therapy	No	No

AC13	Abigail	Partner Children Friends	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Relaxation therapy	No	Yes
AC14	James	Children Friends	Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-management programmes	Yes	No
AC15	April	Husband	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Relaxation therapy	Yes	Yes
AC16	Beth	Husband	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Self-help group Relaxation therapy Massage	No	Yes
AC17	Sarah	Husband Children	Individual pulmonary rehabilitation	Yes	Yes
AC18	Nancy	Children Neighbours	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Relaxation therapy	No	Yes
AC19	Glen	Spouse	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-management programmes Counselling	Yes	Yes
AC20	Graham	Children	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-management programmes Counselling	No	Yes
AC21	Alexander	Spouse	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation	No	Yes
AC22	Mike	Children Cousins, Grandchildren Friends	Group Pulmonary Rehabilitation Individual pulmonary rehabilitation Self-management programmes Self-help group Relaxation therapy Counselling	No	No

Appendix 23: Test of Normality for HADS total

Test of Normality (n=22)				
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		Shapiro-Wilk	
	Statistic	P	Statistic	P
HADS total	.139	.200	.970	.704

Appendix 24: HADS total Range

Appendix 25: HADS total Range Scatter Plot

Appendix 26: HADS total Grade and Point Chart

Appendix 27: Test of Normality for MQOL-R total

Test of Normality (n=22)				
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		Shapiro-Wilk	
	Statistic	P	Statistic	P
MQOL total	-.121	.200	.940	.202

Appendix 28: MQOL-R total Range

Appendix 29: MQOL-R total Range Scatter Plot

Appendix 30: MQOL-R total Grade and Point Chart

